

ISMEC 2016

INTERNATIONAL SYMPOSIUM OF METAL COMPLEXES.

A TOTAL BROKERAGE EVENT

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

ISMEC GROUP SERIES

Volume: 6

Year: 2016

Symposium Edition: XXVII

<https://www.ismecgroup.org/ismec-acta/>

ISSN: 2239-2459

ISMEC 2016

INTERNATIONAL SYMPOSIUM OF METAL COMPLEXES.
A TOTAL BROKERAGE EVENT

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

Casa convalescència
ALBA Synchrotron

7-10 June 2016
Barcelona

ISMEC 2016

INTERNATIONAL SYMPOSIUM OF METAL COMPLEXES.

A TOTAL BROKERAGE EVENT

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

Casa Convalescència
ALBA Synchrotron
7-10 June 2016
Barcelona

Welcome to ISMEC2016 in Barcelona

Dear colleagues and Friends,

The International Congress on Metal Complexes, ISMEC2016, on its 43th edition becomes a reality in Barcelona. It has been a long way since our Italian friends begun and our meetings did provide the opportunity to many of us not only to learn on metal complexes, their roll and growing applications in several fields including environment, health, food, energy, but to meet wonderful people that this yearly sharing created a nice friendship. I have to mention our master friends that were at the start of ISMEC initiative and already left us, thus Carunchio, Casassas, Ferri, Ostacoli, Portanova, Pulidori, Romano, between others, made us in their way to love the study of chemical species.

In Barcelona, ISMEC2016 wants not only to continue our friendly way of growing in science and knowledge transfer but also to develop the personal interactions between participants, because we believe that personal contributions are of key to success or failure and here personal communications and personal interactions will positively support our professional and personal success that will also be the success of our community. There are no many instruments that can provide such interactions in an extensive way, but we will try the best having your collaboration to make a success our planned brokerage session. This session is intended to take the best of us to share with colleagues, students and innovators that participate at ISMEC2016. Thus, I invite you to collaborate in this special session to take place on June 8th afternoon at the ISMEC2016 venue of Casa de Convalescencia in Barcelona.

On the other hand, I want also to highlight that ISMEC2016 will bring us back to the lab, a particular and specific lab as it is our ALBA Synchrotron. Thus, on Thursday June 9th we will move to visit and work our sessions at ALBA, where we will be in a proper atmosphere to share experiences, to know specific developments and to touch the possibilities to add new values to your research and specific applications.

To encourage you in these activities, we will have with us specialists and well known scientist to highlight with different advanced techniques the possibilities of getting deeper in the knowledge and applications of chemical complexes, including metals and non-metal complexes.

The program that you find here would not have been possible without the contribution of all of you and in particular, I want to recognize the contribution of the GTS people from UAB and the people from ALBA, who is providing all possible efforts to make ISMEC2016 an useful nice event for all of us in a period where there is no financial support from our public Administration. Agència de Promoció d'Activitats i Congressos from UAB and the company Reunions i Ciència, RiC, are acknowledged for their contribution to the logistics and management of ISMEC2016.

We wish to all of you the best profit from your participation at ISMEC2016 and a pleasant stay in Barcelona.

Manuel Valiente

ISMEC2016 Chair

COMMITTEES

SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE

Manuel Valiente, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain.
Montserrat López-Mesas, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain
Cristina Palet, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain.
Enrique García-España, Universidad de Valencia, Spain
Guido Crisponi, Università Degli Studi di Cagliari, Italy.
Henryk Kozłowski, Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Poland.
Raffaella Biesuz, Università Degli Studi di Pavia, Italy.
Tarita Biver, Università Degli Studi di Pisa, Italy.
Antonio Bianchi, Università Degli Studi di Firenze, Italy.
Etelka Farkas, Debreceni Egyetem, Hungary.
Juan Nicolás Gutierrez, Universidad de Granada, Spain.
María Ángeles Olazabal, Euskal Herriko Unibertsitatea, Spain.
Maurizio Remelli, Università Degli Studi di Ferrara, Italy.
Maria Amelia Santos, Instituto Superior Técnico de Lisboa, Portugal.
Peter Gans, Protonic Software, Leeds, England.
Michel Meyer, Université de Bourgogne, France.

ORGANIZING COMMITTEE

Manuel Valiente, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain.
Montserrat López-Mesas, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain
Cristina Palet, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain.
Laura Simonelli, ALBA Synchrotron, Spain
Gustavo Pérez, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain
Albert Pell, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain
María Jesús Sánchez-Martín, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain
Montserrat Resina, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain
Carlo Marini, ALBA Synchrotron, Spain
Maria Dolors Mir, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ORAL PRESENTATIONS

<i>PLENARY LECTURE</i> . Novel nanocomposite for high efficiency. Solid oxide fuel cell.....	1
Polymer inclusion membranes as a new tool for zinc speciation studies.....	2
Stabilization of copper(II) coordination environment using branched peptides: towards artificial metalloenzymes	3
<i>KEY NOTE</i> . Metal Organic Frameworks. From coordination chemistry towards composites, advanced nano-materials and drug delivery	5
<i>PULIDORI PRIZE WINNER</i> . Ag ₂ and Ag ₃ Clusters: Synthesis, Characterization, and Interaction with DNA.....	7
Solution coordination chemistry as a mean to qualify new chelators designed for nuclear medical applications	9
Criteria for the best Cu(II)-chelator in the context of Alzheimer's disease	11
Metal-catalyzed oxidation of the A β peptide in Alzheimer's Disease: characterization of oxidation sites and consequences on ROS production and copper coordination	13
Design of liposomes as theranostic nanoparticles.....	15
Factors affecting metal binding ability of the trihydroxamate-based siderophore, desferricoprogen, and interference caused by cobalt(III) – desferricoprogen on iron-uptake of selected microbes	17
<i>PLENARY LECTURE</i> . Redox and coordination environment: Controls over uranium behavior in complex natural sediments	19
Sulfur XANES analysis of Atlantic Oysters and Mediterranean Mussels.....	21
Selenium enrichment of wheat plants: characterization by synchrotron techniques...	23
<i>KEY NOTE</i> . X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy and its application to biomarkers identification.....	25
Using mass spectrometry to monitor the interaction of metallic compounds with biomolecules.....	27
Studies on mutants of Colicin E7 metallonuclease - Crystal structures vs. aqueous solution	28
Targeting G-quadruplex DNA with fluorescent perylene derivatives	30
Efficient Fluoride Adsorption by mesoporous Hierarchical Alumina Microspheres	32
Influence of organic ligands on the sorption and solubility of radionuclides	34
<i>PLENARY LECTURE</i> . Metal Imaging at Nanometer Level in Biological Cells by Nano Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry (NanoSIMS)	35
Alizarine red's immobilized on triacetylcellulose film tapes for metal ions sensing.	36

The Chemistry of Metal-Organic Non-Trivial Structures.....	38
Kinetics of the Formation of a Rotaxane from the End-Capping Process of a Pseudorotaxane.....	40
Nanoparticle systems for future sensing and (bio)targeting applications.....	42
Perylene-bisimide (PBI) metal complexes as stabilizers of carbon nanotubes mixtures for temperature sensing.....	44
An(III) and Ln(III) complexation with TPAEN: selectivity quantification for an americium(III) separation process.....	46
Halogenide Anion Complexes with a Tetrazine-based Ligand	48
Novel bridging μ_2 -N7,O6-ayclovir mode in a tetranuclear complex having a cubane-like core $[\text{Ni}^{II}_4(\mu_3\text{-methanolato})_4]^{4+}$	50
New polytopic ligands from pyridine-based -macrocycles and open chain bipodal chelator moieties.....	52
Modelling the dependence on medium and ionic strength of molybdate acid-base properties, and its interactions with phytate.....	54

POSTERS PRESENTATION

Platinum complexes with antiproliferative activity	57
Thermodynamic and structural characterization of transition metal complexes of peptides with thiolate and other binding sites	59
Photocleavage and Chemical Properties of Arene-Organometallic Complexes depend of the Metal Center	61
Magnetic Metal Organic Frameworks - from synthesis to applications	63
Coordination, redox properties and SOD activity of Cu(II) complexes of multihistidine peptides.....	64
Luminescent Eu^{3+} complexes in acetonitrile solution: effect of water on speciation and anions sensing	66
A Novel Octasubstituted Zinc Phthalocyanine Containing 4-(trifluoromethoxy)-thiophenol Groups.....	68
Non-peripherally Pyrrole-substituted Phthalocyanines.....	69
Synthesis, Characterization, and Spectral Properties of a Novel Tetrasubstituted Zinc Phthalocyanine	71
Tetra Substituted Phthalocyanines with Morpholinoethanol Moieties	72
Complex-Formation Ability of Thiosemicarbazones towards Cu(II) Ions.....	73
Sequestration of Different M^{n+} Cations by MGDA in Natural Fluids.....	75
Some aspects on the evaluation of the adsorption properties of two trihydroxamic acid hybrid materials.....	77

Assessment of different sorbents for metal removal from aqueous samples.....	79
New molecularly imprinted polymer for diclofenac removal from water	81
Recovery of acidic pharmaceutical compounds via molecularly imprinted polymers from water.....	83
DNA-Binding Properties of Pyridin-3-yl Substituted Water Soluble Phthalocyanines...	85
Dna binding of organotin(IV) complexes of meso-tetra (4 sulfonatophenyl) porphine showing cellular activity	87
Coordination of Zn(II) with human and murine Amyloid- β	89
Interaction of Cu(II) ions with human serum amyloid A	91
Metal complexes of cysteine containing peptides	92
Analysis of the binding of commercial stains to protein materials used in artworks....	94
Synthetic hexa-His-tags vs. natural His-tag peptides - differences and similarities in metal ion coordination and structural properties.....	96
Metallophores as Mediators for Metal Cycling: L- α -amino-acid residue ligands as new molybdenum buffers	98
Evaluation of the adsorption capacity of antimony from aqueous solution by using cork as bio(adsorbent).....	100
Study of the effect of the pyrolysis and post-treatment procedures in the adsorption of heavy metals by biomass application to soil.....	102
New photo-switchable Pt-azobenzene complexes as potential anticancer drugs	104
“Old” Cu(II) complexes with “new” anticancer properties. An interesting approach .	105
Two new zinc folates derivatives useful for the preparation of Tc-99m radiopharmaceuticals with high specific activity	107
Biomimetic siderophores for iron(III) tracking and sensing purposes	109
Segregation of metal ions in multimetallic solutions by using sorption/desorption cycles. A green separation process	111
Evaluation of the adsorption capacities of elements from polluted aqueous solutions by food wastes.....	113
Effective removal of antimony from aqueous solution using Forager Sponge [®] and SPION-loaded onto Forager Sponge [®]	115
Analysis of Isothermal Titration Calorimetry data with ITC_Cal	117
Positive influence of metal complexing properties of surface chemical functions of carbon nanotubes on the preparation of metal nanoparticles.....	119
Rh(III) and Ir(III)-ciclopentadienyl-pyridinyl-quinoline complexes: solution properties and polynucleotides binding	120
Advanced oxidation processes for the tooth bleaching enhancement	122

Synthesis of reference samples of kidney stones for synchrotron studies.....	124
Determination of the distribution of Selenium chemical species in wheat plants to elaborate functional food.....	126
Interaction of Human Serum Albumin (SHA) with an Ir(III) complex.....	128
Leaching Processes of Beachrock outcrops located close to estuarine areas	130
Multianalytical methodology based on in situ spectroscopic assessment to diagnose the chemical attack in building materials: DRIFT implementation	132

ORAL PRESENTATIONS

PLENARY LECTURE

Novel nanocomposite for high efficiency. Solid oxide fuel cell

Mamoun MUHAMMED^{a)}

a) Royal Institute of Technology (KTH) 164 40 Kista (Stockholm) Sweden
Mamoun@kth.se

There are world-wide interest for developing alternative energy sources that are highly efficient and environmentally friendly. Fuel cells, electrochemical conversion devices, are considered as one of the promising power-generation technologies. Their advantages lie in the high energy conversion efficiency (up to 60%), the possibility to use different fuels, environmental compatibility, and modularity.

There several types of fuel cells suitable for different applications. Solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs) are interesting for high throughput power generation. However, current SOFCs need to be operated at relatively high temperatures (900-1100°C) which represent major challenges on the material's selection, degradation, changes in morphology and phase, etc., resulting in lower performance efficiency. To make them more competitive with other energy sources, there is a need to develop SOFCs capable of operating at much lower temperature range.

Current SOFCs require high operating temperature in order to achieve reasonable oxygen ion conductivity in the electrolyte. Yttria-stabilized zirconia (YSZ) is normally used as the electrolyte material, as it is stable at high temperature and can conduct oxygen ions at a reasonable level but only at these temperature ranges.

In this talk, we present some of our research on the development of novel nanocomposite materials as an electrolyte in SOFCs with good ionic conductivity at much lower temperatures. The nanocomposite consists of doped cerium oxide and sodium carbonate. The sodium carbonate, immiscible with the doped ceria, is present at the interface between the ceria nanoparticles. The nanocomposite has shown to have good thermal stability at temperature as high as 600°C with high oxygen-ions conductivity. Moreover, this nanocomposite has shown to be able to simultaneously conduct protons across the electrolyte barrier resulting in an overall increase of the efficiency of the solid oxide fuel cell performance, yet at much lower temperature.

Polymer inclusion membranes as a new tool for zinc speciation studies

Ruben VERA^{a)}, Eline MICHIELSEN^{a)}, Clàudia FONTÀS^{a)}, Enriqueta ANTICÓ^{a)}

^{a)}*Departament de Química. Universitat de Girona. Spain*
enriqueta.antico@udg.edu

Polymer inclusion membranes (PIMs) are a kind of functionalized membranes presently used for different separation purposes, mainly metal preconcentration, removal of pollutants, and elimination of interferences [1].

A PIM consists of a carrier entrapped in polymer matrix, which confers the mechanical strength to the membrane. In some cases a plasticizer is included in the formulation to provide the necessary elasticity. The carrier is the active component responsible for the transport of the target analyte from the donor solution to the acceptor solution (facilitated transport).

We have investigated the usefulness of PIMs in zinc speciation studies. The PIM designed for Zn transport consists of PVC as a polymer and di-(2-ethylhexyl) phosphoric acid (D2EHPA) as carrier. The membrane is placed in a glass device [2] with 0.01M nitric acid as acceptor solution. The composition of the donor phase was fixed as 0.01M potassium nitrate solution.

The flux of zinc through the membrane was measured for a time period of 24 hours for different total metal (15 μ M, 35 μ M, 50 μ M and 70 μ M) concentration, and we could observe a linear relation between both variables. We also tested the influence of the presence of different organic ligands by adding to the donor solutions ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA), nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA), citrate, histidine, and humic acid. The correlation of the fluxes with the free metal concentration calculated using Visual MINTEQ will allow us to discuss the different species that contribute to the metal transport.

Acknowledgements

The financial support of the research project CTM2013-48967-C2-2-P and the doctoral grant ref. BES-2014-068316 (R.V.) are acknowledged.

References:

- [1] Almeida, M. I. G. S.; Cattrall, R.W.; Kolev, S.D., Recent trends in extraction and transport of metal ions using polymer inclusion membranes (PIMs). *J. Membr. Sci.* 2012, 415-416, 9-23.
- [2] Fontàs, C.; Vera, R.; Batalla, A. ; Kolev, S.D. ; Anticó, E., A novel low-cost detection method for screening of arsenic in groundwater. *Environ Sci Pollut Res* 2014, 21, 11682-11688.

Stabilization of copper(II) coordination environment using branched peptides: towards artificial metalloenzymes

Monica PERINELLI^{a)}, Maurizio REMELLI^{b)}, Remo GUERRINI^{b)}, Nicola MARCHETTI^{b)}, Matteo Tegoni^{a)}

^{a)}Department of Chemistry, University of Parma, Parma, Italy; ^{b)}Department of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of Ferrara, Ferrara, Italy
maurizio.remelli@unife.it

Branched peptides can be obtained from a central scaffold (core) to which a variable number of peptide sequences are linked. These macromolecules have been described in the preparation of novel promising antibacterial agents, vaccines and anticancer drugs [1]. In this contribution we describe the study of two Cu(II)-binding oligopeptides, and of their tetrameric branched forms. The peptide sequences AAHAWG-NH₂ (**P**¹) and HAWG-NH₂ (**P**²) were synthesized using solid phase synthesis. Their tetrameric branched forms were obtained starting from the corresponding one amino acid longer sequences (AAHAWGC-NH₂ and HAWGC-NH₂), bearing a cysteine at the C-terminus. The cysteine SH group allowed to bind the peptides to a maleimide-functionalized cyclam platform via a thiol/Michael reaction, yielding the desired tetrameric branched peptides [2] (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Schematic representation of the tetrameric peptide constructs.

Monomeric peptide **P**¹ binds Cu(II) at its ATCUN site (Ala-Ala-His-) [3]. Potentiometry showed that [Cu(**P**¹H₂)] is the major species in the 4-9 pH range, while [Cu(**P**¹H₃)]⁻ forms at higher pH values. For both species, spectroscopic data are fully consistent with a 1:1 Cu:peptide binding stoichiometry through a (4N) donor atoms set. Consistently, spectroscopic data for the tetrameric (**P**¹)₄cyclam/copper(II) system showed that the tetrameric construct binds 4 eq. of Cu(II) at the ATCUN sites (Scheme 2).

Monomeric peptide **P**² forms [Cu(**P**²)₂]²⁺ as the major species at pH 7. Spectroscopic data are consistent with a mixed Gly-like (N, O) and histamine-like (N, N) coordination to the copper ion, in the equatorial plane of the complex. The involvement of the second imidazole,

KEY NOTE

Metal Organic Frameworks. From coordination chemistry towards composites, advanced nano-materials and drug delivery

Josef HAVEL^{a)}

^{a)}Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Kamenice 5/A14, 625 00
Brno, Czech Republic;
havel@chemi.muni.cz

Coordination metal-ligand complexes were intensively studied in the past, both in solution and in solid state. When crystallized, in solid state, created nanometer-sized spaces induce novel phenomena and these porous compounds have attracted high attention of materials scientists. Porous materials such as zeolites are known for a long time and the first synthetic zeolites were described already in 1862 [1]. New initiation of further progress in the field came with “coordination polymers” (CP); the term was introduced by Bailar in 1964 when he compared organic polymers with inorganic compounds which can be considered as polymeric species [2].

Metal Organic Frameworks (MOFs) are defined as “crystalline compounds consisting of metal ions or clusters coordinated to often rigid organic molecules to form one up to three-dimensional structures that can be porous” [3]. Both, MOFs and CPs are new challengers on the porous materials scene. The difference between CPs and MOFs is discussed in [3], but generally, both of them are containing metal ions and organic spacer ligands.

Illustrative scheme of MOF synthesis is given in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1 Illustrative scheme of MOFs synthesis from suitable bridging ligands (e.g. trimesic acid) and metal ions (Cu^{2+}) or metal clusters.

 represents a drug molecule in MOF pores

There are extensive studies and applications of MOFs. Porous structure, with nanometer size of pores, makes such materials very attractive for various purposes: MOFs

were found useful in gas storage, including hydrogen, methane, or carbon dioxide, in separation science, esp. in gas chromatography, in catalysis, molecular recognition, and in medicine, for example. Also nanoscale metal-organic frameworks (NMOFs) have been developed and they found use especially for drugs delivery, similarly as magnetic MOFs [4] which are suitable for contaminants separation in magnetic field or drugs delivery, as well. [5-6]

In this work (i) fundamentals of MOFs synthesis and/or design will be reviewed (ii), survey of applications in nanomedicine and their use as drug carriers will be shown, (iii) future trends will be discussed, and (iv) several case studies will be demonstrated and discussed.

E.g., interaction of nano silver with MOFs was studied and it was found that removal of this emergent contaminant from waters is possible [7]. On the other hand, MOFs-nano silver (or nano gold) composites are a suitable MALDI matrices for pre-concentration of peptides and proteins and thus more sensitive MALDI TOF mass spectrometric detection is possible. Such MOFs composites were also found as excellent SERS material for highly sensitive surface enhanced Raman spectroscopy for biomolecules detection, e.g. for retinoic acid and retinoids. Use of MOFs in nanomedicine for drug delivery was discussed [8] and it was studied here for several drugs. Moreover, synthesis of core-shell magnetic MOFs suitable for contaminants separation or drugs delivery was performed, as well. Concluding, MOFs, NMOFs and/or core-shell MOFs represent exciting high-tech material with wide applications in science, technology, and in medicine.

Acknowledgements

Profs. Dr. E.M. Peña-Méndez and dr. J.E. Conde-González, University of la Laguna, Tenerife, Spain, via Grant MAT2014-57465-R (Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness, Spain) are thanked for collaboration. J. Havel acknowledges Masaryk University for support.

References:

- [1] H. de Sainte Claire Deville; Hebd, C. R., *Seances Acad. Sci.* **1862**, *54*, 324.
- [2] Bailar, J. C., Jr. *Prep. Inorg. React.* **1964**, *1*, 1–57.
- [3] Biradha, K.; Ramanan, A.; Vittal, J., Coordination Polymers Versus Metal-Organic Frameworks, *Crystal Growth & Design* **2009**, *9*, 2969-2970.
- [4] Huang, Y.; Keller, A. A., Magnetic Nanoparticle Adsorbents for Emerging Organic Contaminants. *ACS Sustainable Chem. Eng.* **2013**, *1*, 731–736.
- [5] Keskin, S.; Kizilel, S. Biomedical applications of metal organic frameworks. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research* **2011**, *50*, 1799-1812.
- [6] Huxford, R. C.; Rocca, J. D.; Lin, W., Metal-Organic Frameworks as Potential Drug Carriers. *Current Opinion Chem. Biol.* **2010**, *14*, 262–268.
- [7] Conde-González, J.E.; Peña-Méndez, E.M.; Rybáková, S.; Pasán, J.; Ruiz-Pérez, C.; Havel J., Adsorption of silver nanoparticles from aqueous solution on copper-based metal organic frameworks (HKUST-1). *Chemosphere* **2016**, *150*, 659-66.
- [8] Kolářová, L.; Vaňhara, P.; Peña-Méndez, E.M.; Hampl, A.; Havel, J., Tissue visualization mediated by nanoparticles: from tissue staining to mass spectrometry tissue profiling and imaging. In: Seifalian A, editor. *Nanomedicine*. Manchester, UK: One Central Press; **2014**, 468-82.

PULIDORI WINNER

Ag₂ and Ag₃ Clusters: Synthesis, Characterization, and Interaction with DNA

David BUCETA^{a)}, Natalia BUSTO^{b)}, Giampaolo BARONE^{c)}, José M. LEAL^{b)}, Fernando DOMÍNGUEZ^{d)}, Lisandro J. GIOVANETTI^{e)}, Félix G. REQUEJO^{e)}, Begoña GARCIA^{b)}, M. Arturo LÓPEZ-QUINTELA^{a)}

^{a)}Departamen of Physical Chemistry, University of Santiago de Compostela; ^{b)} Department of Chemistry, University of Burgos; ^{c)} Department of Biological, Chemical and Pharmaceutical Sciences and Technologies, University of Palermo, ^{d)} Department of Physiology and Centro de Investigaciones en Medicina Molecular y Enfermedades Crónicas (CIMUS), University of Santiago de Compostela, ^{e)} Instituto de Investigaciones Físicoquímicas Teóricas y Aplicadas (INIFTA), Universidad Nacional de La Plata-CONICET, La Plata (Argentina)

Subnanometric samples, containing exclusively Ag₂ and Ag₃ clusters, were synthesized for the first time by kinetic control using an electrochemical technique without the use of surfactants or capping agents. By combination of thermodynamic and kinetic measurements and theoretical calculations, we show herein that Ag₃ clusters interact with DNA through intercalation, inducing significant structural distortion to the DNA. The lifetime of Ag₃ clusters in the intercalated position is two to three orders of magnitude longer than for classical organic intercalators, such as ethidium bromide or proflavine.

Ag₂ and Ag₃ Clusters: Synthesis, Characterization, and Interaction with DNA^{†‡}

David Buceta, Natalia Bustos, Giampaolo Barone, José M. Leal, Fernando Domínguez, Lisandro J. Giovanetti, Félix G. Requejo, Begoña García,* and M. Arturo López-Quintela*

Abstract: Subnanometric samples, containing exclusively Ag₂ and Ag₃ clusters, were synthesized for the first time by kinetic control using an electrochemical technique without the use of surfactants or capping agents. By combination of thermodynamic and kinetic measurements and theoretical calculations, we show herein that Ag₂ clusters interact with DNA through intercalation, inducing significant structural distortion to the DNA. The lifetime of Ag₂ clusters in the intercalated position is two to three orders of magnitude longer than for classical organic intercalators, such as ethidium bromide or proflavine.

The interaction of Ag clusters with DNA has been used as a template method to prepare luminescent Ag clusters (see, for example, Refs. [1–6]), which have in turn been further developed as highly sensitive fluorescent sensors (see Ref. [7] for an example). In spite of the large number of studies carried out in this area, the nature of the interactions between Ag clusters and DNA remains largely unknown. Additionally, it has been recognized that the chemistry of clusters very much depends on the cluster size. For example, narrow cluster size windows have been reported for clusters with catalytic properties (see, for example, Refs. [8–10]), showing that the cluster size is a very important parameter which has a major influence on their physicochemical properties. Therefore, to shed light on the interaction of DNA with clusters, one should use stable cluster samples with the narrowest possible size distribution. At the same time, because the capping agent can also have a large influence on such an interaction, one should use clusters without surfactants or other types of strong binding ligands. These requirements render the synthesis of such cluster samples a major challenge. We will show herein that this objective can be achieved using kinetic control

techniques,^{11,12} allowing us to synthesize for the first time the smallest reported naked Ag clusters (Ag₂ and Ag₃). Using UV/Vis absorption, fluorescence, and circular dichroism spectroscopies, viscosity and kinetic (stopped flow) measurements, and quantum mechanics/molecular mechanics (QM/MM) calculations, we studied the interaction of these clusters with DNA. Results show that Ag₂ clusters (unlike Ag₃) interact with DNA through intercalation, inducing significant structural distortion to the DNA.

The synthesis of atomic quantum clusters (denoted Ag-AQCs) without any surfactant was carried out by modification of a previously reported electrochemical method (see the Experimental Section in the Supporting Information).^{7,8} It has been shown that the nanoparticle size can be controlled with electrochemical techniques by changing the current density.¹³ However, this method needs some modifications in order to prepare stable clusters. Key to the production of small Ag clusters is the use of very slow kinetics with a very low concentration of Ag ions in solution, as previously reported.¹⁴ To achieve the formation of stable, small Ag clusters, it is required that: a) the current densities should be much lower than those normally achieved using supporting electrolytes, requiring the use of milliQ water with no added electrolytes for the synthesis; b) the concentration of Ag ions must be kept at very low levels, ensuring that the clusters will grow very slowly.¹⁵ After the electrochemical synthesis, it is also very important to remove any excess of Ag ions which have not been reduced because the presence of such ions causes the Ag cluster solution to become unstable, and further growth of clusters takes place until all Ag ions have been taken up. With this in mind, excess Ag ions in the solution are eliminated by precipitation with NaCl immediately after the

[*] Dr. D. Buceta,^{††} Prof. Dr. M. A. López-Quintela
Department of Physical Chemistry
University of Santiago de Compostela
15782 Santiago de Compostela (Spain)
E-mail: malopez.quintela@usc.es

Dr. N. Bustos,^{†††} Prof. Dr. J. M. Leal, Prof. Dr. B. García
Department of Chemistry, University of Burgos
9001 Burgos (Spain)
E-mail: bugar@ubu.es

Dr. G. Barone
Department of Biological, Chemical and Pharmaceutical Sciences
and Technologies, University of Palermo, 90128 Palermo (Italy)

Prof. Dr. F. Domínguez
Department of Physiology and Centro de Investigaciones en
Medicina Molecular y Enfermedades Crónicas (CIMUS)
University of Santiago de Compostela
15782 Santiago de Compostela (Spain)

Dr. L. J. Giovanetti, Prof. Dr. F. G. Requejo
Instituto de Investigaciones Físicoquímicas Teóricas y Aplicadas
(INIFTA), Universidad Nacional de La Plata CONICET
Sucursal 4 Casilla de Correo 16 (1900) La Plata (Argentina)

[†] These authors contributed equally to this paper.

[††] This work was supported by Obra Social “la Caixa” (CSIC-2012-007), the European Commission through the FEDER and FP7 programs (08E1_InvoDNA_1_E_FutureNanofuels, FP7-Grant 604602), the MCI Spain (MAT2010-20442 and MAT2011-28673-C02-01), MINECO Spain (MAT2012-36754-C02-01, CTQ2014-58812-C2-2-R), Xunta de Galicia Spain (GRC2013-048, FEDER Funds), D.B. is grateful for the postdoctoral grant from Xunta de Galicia Spain (POS-A/2013/018), F.G.B. and L.J.G. thank the CONICET for grant 01005 and the SX5 Beamline (LNLS, Campinas, Brazil) for partial support.

Supporting information for this article is available on the WWW under <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/anie.201502917>.

Solution coordination chemistry as a mean to qualify new chelators designed for nuclear medical applications

Michel MEYER^{a)}, Nicolas ROLLET^{a)}, Trong-Hung VU^{a)}, Stéphane BRANDES^{a)}, Peter GANS^{b)}

^{a)} Institut de Chimie Moléculaire de l'Université de Bourgogne (ICMUB), UMR 6302, CNRS, Université de Bourgogne – Franche-Comté, 9 avenue Alain Savary, 21078 DIJON, France

^{b)} Protonic Software, 2 Templegate Avenue, Leeds, LS15 0HD, W. Yorkshire, England
michel.meyer@u-bourgogne.fr

Molecular imaging plays a steadily growing role in medical diagnosis and evaluation of therapeutic effects of new drugs. Among the widely-used techniques, positron emission tomography (PET) and single-photon emission computed tomography (SPECT) are most-useful non-invasive imaging modalities for detecting tumors or providing insights into physiological processes. Since most of the useful radionuclides are metal cations, they are injected into organisms as radiotracers that combine a bifunctional chelating agent and a biological vector. Development of new high-affinity chelators is still an ongoing task as the optimal ligands should form highly-stable and inert complexes to prevent in-vivo dissociation, but exhibit at the same time fast binding kinetics at room temperature and optimal pH to reduce loss of activity and radiation exposure for the manipulators. Moreover, in case of copper(II)-based radiotracers, the redox potential should be well below those of physiological reducing agents in order to prevent the release of the radioelement by a reductive pathway.

Currently, most of the research efforts are focused on azamacrocyclic ligands of various topologies because they fulfill more or less the above-mentioned criteria. The lecture will review the impact of several structural factors of *N*-substituted tetraazamacrocyclic ligands on their copper(II) and gallium(III) binding properties determined by crystallography, UV-vis and EPR spectroscopies, solution thermodynamics, electrochemistry, and kinetics.

The metal uptake affinity of ligands at physiological pH is classically gauged by the so-called pM value defined in the late seventies by Raymond *et al.* ($pM = -\log [M(H_2O)_n]_{free}$) [1]. After discussing some major caveats of this widely-used parameter, which can lead to misleading conclusions, the relative affinity criterion, denoted $A_{L/M}$, will be introduced as a new, but universal mean for the reliable assessment and comparison of the complexing power of any kind of ligand. Relative affinities are straightforwardly computed with the general speciation program Hyss2009 by using the apparent constant functionality.

$$A_{L/M} = -\log\left(\frac{\sum [M]_{unbound}}{[M]_{Tot}}\right) = -\log\left(\frac{[M]_{Tot} - \sum [M]_{bound}}{[M]_{Tot}}\right) = -\log\left(\frac{[M]_{Tot} - \sum m\beta_{mhl} [M]^m [L]^l [H]^h}{[M]_{Tot}}\right)$$

Finally, a detailed investigation of the copper(II) binding performances of the cross-bridged cyclam derivative CB-TE2A²⁻ will be presented. Owing to the extraordinary inertness of the corresponding metal complexes, this ligand was sought as one of the most promising ⁶⁴Cu²⁺ chelator by the community of radiopharmacists [2]. Beside speciation studies, the complex formation mechanism was investigated by combining classical and stopped-flow UV-vis absorption spectrophotometry and EPR measurements. A multistep process was evidenced in the presence of a large excess of ligand. Parametrization of the corresponding rate laws allowed estimating the reaction time under radiolabelling conditions.

References:

- [1] Raymond, K. N.; Carrano, C. J., Coordination chemistry and microbial iron transport. *Acc. Chem. Res.* **1979**, 12 (5), 183-190
- [2] Anderson, C. J.; Wadas, T. J.; Wong, E. H.; Weisman, G. R., *J. Nucl. Med. Mol. Imaging* **2008**, 52, 185.

Criteria for the best Cu(II)-chelator in the context of Alzheimer's disease

Amandine CONTE-DABAN^{a) b)}, Peter FALLER^{c)}, Christelle HUREAU^{a)}

a) Laboratoire de Chimie de Coordination, CNRS, 31077 Toulouse Cedex 4, France b) Université Paul Sabatier, 31077 Toulouse Cedex 4, France c) Institut d'Etudes Avancées, Université de Strasbourg, 67008 Strasbourg Cedex, France
amandine.conte-daban@lcc-toulouse.fr

Alzheimer's disease is the most common neurodegenerative disease, with no known cure. Brain of Alzheimer's patients exhibits intracellular neurofibrillary tangles as well as extracellular senile plaques, consisting of insoluble fibrillar aggregates of the amyloid- β peptide ($A\beta$). The amyloid cascade hypothesis describes this aggregation; where monomeric $A\beta$ aggregates first into oligomers, then into fibrils. In the presence of metal ions, this aggregation is modified.[1] Coordination of $A\beta$ with Cu(II) generally favours the formation of oligomeric species, whereas Zn(II) generally induces fibrillisation of the peptide. $A\beta$ -Cu(II) oligomers are considered to be more toxic than $A\beta$ -Zn(II) fibrils,[2] because of their capability to produce Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS).

One therapeutic strategy in tackling Alzheimer's disease is to reduce the formation of these toxic oligomeric species, by retrieval of Cu(II) from $A\beta$, through the use of a Cu(II) chelator (Fig 1). The ideal chelator must be able to (i) effectively retrieve Cu(II) from $A\beta$, (ii) stop or reduce the production of ROS, (iii) inhibit the formation of toxic oligomeric $A\beta$ -Cu(II) species. In this study, we will present different criteria for a Cu(II)-chelator to remove the metal from the peptide. The thermodynamic and kinetic parts will be approached. Different [N,O] chelators are tested.[3] However, it is important to investigate the role of Zn(II), which is also present in high concentrations in the synaptic cleft[4] and can thus interfere in the Cu(II) removal process.

Figure 1. Scheme of the amyloid cascade hypothesis.

References:

- [1] Hureau, C., Coordination of redox active metal ions to the amyloid precursor protein and to amyloid- β peptides involved in Alzheimer disease. Part 1: An overview. *Coordin. Chem. Rev.* **2012**, 256 (19-20), 2164.
- [2] Cuajungco, M.P.; Goldstein, L.E.; Nunomura, A.; Smith, M.A.; Lim, J.T.; Atwood C.S.; Huang X.; Farrar Y.W.; Perry, G.; Bush A.I., Evidence that the β -Amyloid Plaques of Alzheimer's Disease Represent the Redox-silencing and Entombment of A β by Zinc. *J. Biol. Chem.* **2000**, 275, 19439-19442.
- [3] Noë, I. S.; Perez, F.; Pedersen, J.T.; Alies, B.; Ladeira, S., A new water-soluble Cu(II) chelator that retrieves Cu from Cu(amyloid- β) species, stops associated ROS production and prevents Cu(II)-induced Ab aggregation. *J. Inorg. Biochem.* **2012**, 117, 322-325.
- [4] Faller, P.; Hureau, C.; Berthoumieu, O., Role of Metal Ions in the Self-assembly of the Alzheimer's Amyloid- β Peptide. *Inorg. Chem.* **2013**, 52, 12193-12206.

Metal-catalyzed oxidation of the A β peptide in Alzheimer's Disease: characterization of oxidation sites and consequences on ROS production and copper coordination

Clémence CHEIGNON^{a,b,c)}, Peter FALLER^{d)}, Christelle HUREAU^{a,b)}, Fabrice COLLIN^{a,b)}

^{a)} LCC (Laboratoire de Chimie de Coordination), CNRS UPR 8241, 205 route de Narbonne, 31062 Toulouse Cedex 09, (France) ; ^{b)} Université de Toulouse ; UPS, INPT, 31077 Toulouse (France) ^{c)} UMR 152 Pharma Dev, Université de Toulouse, IRD, UPS (France) ; ^{d)} Institut de Chimie (UMR 7177), 4 rue B. Pascal, F-67000 Strasbourg (France)
clemence.cheignon@lcc-toulouse.fr

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is the most frequent form of dementia in the elderly. One of the features of AD is the formation of senile plaques in brain, mainly composed of the 40/42-residue Amyloid-Beta peptide (A β). The A β peptide is present in soluble form in healthy brain and found aggregated in AD brain. Furthermore, some metals such as copper are present in high levels of concentration in senile plaques, and form complexes with A β . In the presence of a reducing agent, Cu-A β complexes can catalyze the production of Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS), including the hydroxyl radical (HO \cdot) [1,2]. The latter is highly reactive and can cause oxidative damages to surrounding neuronal biomolecules and to the A β peptide itself.

The amino acid residues of A β undergoing oxidative damages were characterized by using High Resolution Mass Spectrometry (HRMS) and Tandem Mass Spectrometry (MS/MS) [3] and identified as being involved in the copper coordination sphere [4,5]. With this in mind, we studied the impact of metal-catalyzed oxidation of A β regarding the ROS production, by using fluorescence spectroscopy with 3-CCA oxidation as a probe, and the coordination of Cu(I) and Cu(II) to the oxidized A β species, by using X-Ray Absorption Near Edge Spectroscopy (XANES) and Electron Paramagnetic Resonance (EPR). The results showed a change of the fluorescence rate as the peptide get oxidized, due to an increase amount of ROS exiting Cu-A β and being scavenged by 3-CCA. This latter phenomenon was linked to a change in Cu-A β coordination, leading to loosely bound copper. Thus, ROS production and A β oxidation seem to play together, in what could be an important mechanism involved in the etiology of Alzheimer's disease, leading to neurodegeneration.

References:

- [1] Hureau, C.; Faller, P., A β -mediated ROS production by Cu ions : Structural insights, mechanisms and relevance to Alzheimer's disease. *Biochimie* **2009**, 91 (10), 1212.
- [2] Chassaing, S.; Collin, F.; Dorlet, P.; Gout, J.; Hureau, C.; Faller, P., Copper and Heme-Mediated Abeta Toxicity: Redox Chemistry, Abeta Oxidations and Anti-ROS Compounds. *Curr. Top. Med. Chem.* **2012**, 12 (22), 2573

- [3] Cassagnes, L.-E.; Hervé, V.; Nepveu, F.; Hureau, C.; Faller, P.; Collin, F., The Catalytically Active Copper-Amyloid-Beta State : Coordination Site Responsible for Reactive Oxygen Species Production. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2013**, 52 (42), 11110.
- [4] Alies, B.; Eury, H.; Bijani, C.; Rechinat, L.; Faller, P.; Hureau, C., pH-Dependent Cu(II) Coordination to Amyloid- β Peptide: Impact of Sequence Alterations, Including the H6R and D7N Familial Mutations. *Inorg. Chem.* **2011** 50 (21), 11192.
- [5] Hureau, C., Coordination of redox active metal ions to the amyloid precursor protein and to amyloid- β peptides involved in Alzheimer disease. Part 1: An overview. *Coordin. Chem. Rev.* **2012**, 256 (19-20), 2164.

Design of liposomes as theranostic nanoparticles

Isabel PONT^{a)}, M. Teresa ALBELDA^{b)}, Enrique GARCÍA-ESPAÑA^{a)}

^{a)} *Supramolecular Chemistry Group, Institute of Molecular Science, University of Valencia*

^{b)} *Biomedicine Imaging Research Group, IIS La Fe*

Isabel.pont@uv

Alteration or inhibition of DNA function as a result of the interaction of it with certain molecules has attracted a great deal of attention in recent years. This interest lies in the ability of these compounds to disrupt or halt the DNA function since they can be used for the treatment of some diseases like cancer.

Previous studies at the Supramolecular Chemistry Group have shown that some polyamines have high selectivity towards DNA. Therefore, they could be valuable compounds to act as antitumor novel drugs. [1]

Currently, one of the most promising vehicles used for drug delivery are liposomes since they are biocompatible, biodegradable and offer targeted drug delivery. [2] Our work consists on the design of this type of nanoparticles achieving highly efficient drug encapsulation of one polyamine derivate and the functionalization of their surface with a fluorophore unit and a contrast agent based on a gadolinium complex. Afterwards, we will obtain an integrated platform to diagnose and treat cancer, ultimately, a theranostic nanoparticle.

Their characterization will be performed by means of electronic microscopy, DLS, UV-visible spectrophotometry and MRI. Finally, we evaluated their cytotoxicity and the release into different line cells.

Scheme 1: Illustration of the polyamine N2222N encapsulated inside a liposome.

References:

- [1] Lomadze, N.; Gogritchiani, E.; Schneider, H.; Albeda, M. T.; García-España, E., Interactions of diaryl-polyamines with nucleic acids. Allosteric effects with dinuclear copper complexes. *Tetrahedron Letters* **2003**, 43, 7801-7803.
- [2] Allen, M.; Cullis, P., Liposomal drug delivery systems: From concept to clinical applications. *Advanced Drug Delivery Reviews* **2013**, 65, 36-48.

Factors affecting metal binding ability of the trihydroxamate-based siderophore, desferricoprogen, and interference caused by cobalt(III) – desferricoprogen on iron-uptake of selected microbes

Etelka FARKAS^{a)}, Zsuzsa SZABÓ^{b)}, István PÓCSI^{c)}

^{a)}Department of Inorganic and Analytical Chemistry, University of Debrecen, Egyetem tér 1, Debrecen, Hungary ^{b)}Szent István University, PhD School of Biology, Gödöllő, Hungary, ^{c)}Department of Microbiology and Biotechnology, University of Debrecen, H-4032 Debrecen, Hungary
efarkas@science.unideb.hu

There are many reasons, why results, what can be obtained by investigation of the different factors, determining the interaction of biogenic metals, including cobalt, with different hydroxamate-based ligands are interesting. For example (i) cobalt ions can be involved in catalytic centers of metalloenzymes and, it is without doubt that the significant inhibitory effect of hydroxamate-based compounds is in direct correlation with the coordination of the hydroxamate function to the metal ion, situating in the active centre of the metalloenzyme. As a consequence, if the main factors determining the cobalt binding ability of hydroxamate based compounds are known, those provide valuable help during development of new effective inhibitor molecules. Also the results can help to get deeper insight into the mechanism of inhibition. (ii) Monohydroxamate-containing ternary Co(III)-complexes were developed as pro-drug candidates [1,2]. The above mentioned reasons initiated our investigation on cobalt complexes (binary and ternary ones) of numerous hydroxamic acids, including synthetic compounds and natural siderophores. In the present case, cobalt(II/III) binding ability of a trihydroxamate-based microbial siderophore, desferricoprogen, DFC (see its formula below), in comparison with analogous molecules, is planned to discuss. Likewise, some results relating the effect of Co(III)-DFC on iron-uptake of selected strains of fungi is also planned to provide.

Out of the structural factors of the chains (each of them is connecting two hydroxamates), the double bonds in β -positions to the chelating functions play a crucial role in the metal binding ability of DFC. According to the results obtained, this siderophore forms high stability complexes with Co(II), but, in fact, the really strong interaction exists in Co(III)-

DFC complex. The latter species can be obtained via oxidation of the corresponding Co(II)-complex and it remains stable under basic condition. The thermodynamic stability of the Co(III)-DFC complex was found to be even higher than the stability of the corresponding Fe(III) species [3]. The extremely high stability of the complex initiated investigation for the possibility of disruption of the microbial iron-uptake in the presence of cobalt(III)-DFC under certain conditions. The examination has been performed via testing of the antifungal effect of the Co(III)-DFC complex on selected fungi with biomedical or agricultural importance. In this project, the following species have been studied: *Fusarium verticillioides* (FGSC 7603), *Penicillium brevicompactum* (SzMC 2180) and *Aspergillus fumigatus* (AF 293/FGSC 1100). The results obtained in this work show that the complex decreased the growth rates in all the fungi tested and the details are planned to display at the conference. .

Acknowledgments

The authors thank members of the EU COST CM1105 for motivating discussions. The research was supported by the Hungarian Scientific Research Fund (OTKA K112317).

References:

- [1] Failes, T.W.; Hambley T.W., Models of hypoxia activated prodrugs: Co(III) complexes of hydroxamic acids. *Dalton Trans.* **2006**, 1895-1901.
- [2] Failes, T.W.; Cullinane, C.; Diakos, C.I.; Yamamoto, N.; Lyons, J.G.; Hambley, T.W., Studies of a Cobalt(III) Complex of the MMP Inhibitor Marimastat: A Potential Hypoxia-Activated Prodrug. *Chem. Eur. J.* **2007**, 13 (10), 2974 – 2982.
- [3] Farkas, E.; Szabó, O., Co(II) and Co(III) hydroxamate system: A solution equilibrium study. *Inorg. Chim. Acta* **2012**, 392, 354-361.

PLENARY LECTURE

Redox and coordination environment: Controls over uranium behavior in complex natural sediments

John R. BARGAR^{a)}, Sharon E. BONE^{a)}, Juan LEZAMA-PACHECO^{b)}, Daniel S. ALESSI^{c)}, Jose M. CERRATO^{d)}, Harish VEERAMANI^{e)}, Vincent NÖEL^{a)}, Elena SUVOROVA^{f)}, Rizlan BERNIER-LATMANI^{f)}, Daniel E. GIAMMAR^{g)}, Philip E. LONG^{h)}, Kenneth H. WILLIAMS^{h)}

*a) SLAC National Accelerator Laboratory b) Stanford University c) University of Alberta
d) University of New Mexico e) University of Glasgow f) Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de
Lausanne g) Washington University h) Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory
bargar@slac.stanford.edu*

Uranium is a globally common and deleterious groundwater contaminant, arising from uranium mining and milling operations, as well as nuclear materials processing and fabrication activities. Once present in the subsurface, it is often highly mobile and can create groundwater contamination plumes that can extend for kilometers. Uranium groundwater cleanup efforts have failed more often than they have succeeded, emphasizing the continued need for knowledge about fundamental controls over uranium behavior.

Uranium mobility in complex natural subsurface systems is profoundly affected by uranium coordination chemistry, as well as by the physical and electronic structure of natural mineral and organic surfaces. Uranium mobility and bioavailability is also moderated by redox conditions; U(VI) is highly mobile in groundwater in the presence of complexing ligands such as bicarbonate, whereas U(IV) is relatively insoluble and therefore typically immobile. Redox conditions within natural aquifers can vary spatially and temporally, giving rise to a range of transport properties. Interfaces between anoxic and oxic zones in natural sediments, which occur at centimeter to meter length scales, are therefore regions of interest for understanding uranium coordination chemistry and mobility. Our group is studying interfacial processes and coordination chemistry of uranium in complex multi-component (mineral-organic-water) redox-variable organic-rich sediments to understand how these factors influence the mobility of uranium in contaminated aquifers.

Whereas a relatively large body of literature has examined sorption of U(VI) on aquifer materials, relatively little attention has focused on U(IV) sorption. U(IV) exhibiting local molecular structure consistent with sorbed complexes has been observed in natural sediments, suggesting that such complexes are important. It is unknown which materials will adsorb U(IV) in complex aquifer solids, or under what geochemical conditions adsorption will outcompete UO₂ precipitation to dominate U(IV) speciation. We will show examples to illustrate the importance of U(IV) adsorption to uranium mobility in contaminated sediments in the upper Colorado River Basin, USA. Together, these results highlight the tightly intertwined roles of interfacial and redox chemistry in controlling contaminant mobilization in complex natural subsurface systems.

Uraninite (UO₂) is a desirable product of bioreduction and a major component of US spent nuclear fuel. In sediments containing UO₂, long-term uranium release is controlled by surface-mediated oxidative dissolution. Dissolution rates are profoundly influenced by the concentrations of dissolved oxygen (DO), carbonate, and solutes such as Ca²⁺, which retards UO₂ oxidation. We show that Ca²⁺ reacts strongly with UO₂ in the aquifer at Rifle, CO, a result of surface binding at uranium structural sites. Overall oxidative uranium loss rates in the aquifer were highly sensitive to DO concentrations, with relatively rapid loss when DO was > 0.6 mg/L, but no measureable loss at lower concentrations. We conclude that the spatial and temporal dynamics of DO in many shallow aquifers will drive periodic oxidative release of uranium from UO₂ and other forms of U(IV).

Sulfur XANES analysis of Atlantic Oysters and Mediterranean Mussels

Carlo MARINI^{a)}, Marta AVILA^{a)}, M. Angels SUBIRANA^{b)}, Wojciech OLSZEWSKI^{a)}, Montserrat LÓPEZ-MESAS^{b)}, Manuel VALIENTE^{b)}, Laura SIMONELLI^{a)}

^{a)} ALBA Synchrotron Light Facility, Carrer de la Llum 2-26, 08290 Cerdanyola del Vallés, Barcelona, Spain; ^{b)} Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona. Departament de Química;
cmarini@cells.es

Marine pollution has become one of the major environmental problems all over the world and extensive research is being undertaken to understand the effect of marine pollution on the global environment and in particular on life forms. Heavy metals present in high concentrations in aquatic habitats are found to be bio-accumulated within the tissue of several organisms. Functional organic groups (such as amide, amine, hydroxyl, carboxylic, imidazole, sulfate, phosphate, and thiol or sulfhydryl) present inside the cell provide indeed the chemical basis to bind these metals. The sulfur electronic properties, contributing the sulfur atom to the structure of amino acids such as cysteine and cystine, are then affecting the protein functionality.

There are very few tools to study the role of sulfur in biological systems, and among them X-ray absorption near edge structure (XANES) spectroscopy offers a unique non-destructing possibility to determine the oxidation state of the element characterizing its chemical speciation [1, 2].

In the present study, we report about sulfur speciation of well characterized Atlantic oysters and Mediterranean mussels samples, by means of X ray absorption near edge structure (XANES) spectroscopy. This noninvasive method provides direct information and evidences about a large variety of organic and inorganic forms, thus allowing for their different functionality identification of the sulfur complexes.

The obtained spectra have been analysed and compared with synthesized Zinc methalotianins (Zn-MTs) and other sulfur references found in literature [3]. Gaussian combination (GC)[4] as well as linear combination (LC)[5] methods have been employed to quantify the species content, decomposing the observed spectral features as results of the different oxidation states of sulfur.

A rough estimation of a maximum Zn-MTs content has been provided, as well as a residual quantification of both organic and inorganic forms of sulfur in the analysed samples.

The obtained results have been compared with the amount of impurities detected in the analysed samples, revealing the high biomarkers efficiency of oysters or mussels in revealing the pollution of heavy metals.

References:

- [1] Vairavamurthy, A., Using X-ray absorption to probe sulfur oxidation states in complex molecules. *Spectrochim. Acta A* **1998**, 54(12), 2009-2017.
- [2] I.J. Pickering, I.J.; Prince, R.C.; Divers, T.; George G.N., Sulfur K-edge X-ray absorption spectroscopy for determining the chemical speciation of sulfur in biological systems. *Federation European Biochemical Societies Lett.* **1998**, 441, 11
- [3] Dyrek, K.; Adamski, A.; Sojka, Z., *Spectrochim. Acta A* **1998**, 54 (12), 2009
- [4] Manceau, A.; Nagy, K.L., Quantitative analysis of sulfur functional groups in natural organic matter by XANES spectroscopy. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta* **2012**, 99, 206-223.
- [5] Prietzel, J.; Botzaki, A.; Tyufekchieva, N.; Brettholle, M.; Thieme, J.; Klysubun, W., Sulfur Speciation in Soil by S K-Edge XANES Spectroscopy: Comparison of Spectral Deconvolution and Linear Combination Fitting. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2011**, 45 (7), 2878–2886.

Selenium enrichment of wheat plants: characterization by synchrotron techniques

Maria Àngels SUBIRANA MANZANARES^{a)}, Mercè LLUGANY^{b)}, Manuel VALIENTE^{a)}

^{a)} Departament de Química, Facultat de Ciències, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 08193, Cerdanyola del Vallés, Barcelona ^{b)} Departament de Biologia Animal, de Biologia Vegetal i d'Ecologia, Facultat de Ciències, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 08193, Cerdanyola del Vallés, Barcelona

mariaangels.subirana@uab.cat

Selenium is an essential micronutrient for humans and it has been shown to be antioxidant, anti-tumoral, anti-viral and to contribute in the treatment of cardiovascular diseases. Therefore, appropriate selenium intake can benefit human health, but millions of people worldwide consume it at levels below the body's need for the correct expression of proteins, where Se is found as selenoamino acids.

Selenium enters the food-chain through plants but Se-poor soils around the world produce Se-deficient crops, resulting in deficient food for humans,. Soil Se enrichment in edible plants has been proposed as a solution for this problem, and wheat has been chosen as an ideal candidate to contribute to human welfare in the form of functional foods. The chemical speciation of Selenium in the system is crucial, since the properties of Se in wheat (bioavailability, toxicity, etc.) are strongly dependent on the form in which it is found. Consequently, characterization of the different species present is required in order to assess the potential health benefits as well as its safety. In this context, it is important to gain an understanding of the plant's physiology, and how it affects the mechanism of bioassimilation of Se, and its metabolism, where inorganic species are transformed to selenoaminoacids. It is also critical to determine the distribution of the species in the different plant tissues (roots, stems, leaves, and grain).

The novel element in the proposed research includes a chemical tuning. By controlling the Se species added to the soil by the related redox potential, it is feasible to obtain the desired ratio of selenoamino acids in wheat grain. This enables the possibility to ensure specific selenium bioavailability and to target determined health benefits for the applications of the obtained functional food. At the same time, it is possible to avoid seasonal variability of the mentioned selenoamino acids ratio.

Proper characterization is essential. Conventional techniques to analyze chemical speciation, (such as HPLC-ICP-MS) require a pretreatment that may alter the selenium species. On the contrary, Synchrotron-based techniques are non-destructive methods that can provide real insight on speciation and also perform distribution studies in small samples. Synchrotron results serve as a reliable validation technique for HPLC-ICP-MS data.

Accordingly, the Se content and speciation in wheat tissues has been measured by direct X-Ray Absorption Spectroscopy (XAS) with Synchrotron Radiation. Furthermore, the location and distribution of several elements through the plant and the grain, including Se and essential nutrients, has been determined by X-Ray Fluorescence mapping (XRF), providing novel significant results on wheat physiology and selenium enrichment.

Acknowledgement:

This work has been financially supported by the project CHEMNEXUS (Ref: CTM2015-65414-C2-1 R) from the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (MINECO) and the European Regional Development Fund (FEDER).

M Angels Subirana Manzanares is grateful to the Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (MINECO) for the predoctoral fellowship: Ayudas para contratos predoctorales para la formación de doctores 2013.

References:

- [1] Rayman, M.P., The importance of selenium to human health. *The Lancet* **2000**, 356, 233-241
- [2] Pyrzynska, K., Selenium speciation in enriched vegetables. *Food Chemistry* **2009**, 114 (4), 1183-1191.
- [3] Pickering, I.J.; Prince, R.C.; Salt, D.E.; George, G.N., Quantitative, chemically specific imaging of selenium transformation in plants. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* **2000**, 97 (20), 10717-10722.
- [4] Guerrero, B.; Llugany, M.; Valiente, M., Method to enrich plant selenoaminoacids by chemical tuning. Patent EP13172305, 2013

KEY NOTE

X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy and its application to biomarkers identification

Laura SIMONELLI^{a)}, Maribel RESTITUYO SILIS^{b)}, Carlo MARINI^{a)}, Marta AVILA^{a)}, Wojciech OLSZEWSKI^{a)}, Ma Angels SUBIRANA^{b)}, Montserrat LOPEZ-MESAS^{b)}, Manuel VAILENTE^{b)}

^{a)} CELLS-ALBA, BP1413, 08290 Cerdanyola del Vallès, Barcelona, Spain ^{b)} Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona. Dept of Chemistry. Center GTS. Campus de la UAB, 08193 Bellaterra (Barcelona), Spain

X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) is a powerful tool to direct access to metal speciation and to the local structural and electronic properties around an absorber. By this technique samples can be analyzed directly or after minimal pretreatment. XAS have been already widely applied in environmental sciences in general, and to the investigation of MTs [1-3] and aquatic organisms in particular [4-8].

Here we will show the powerfulness of this technique and its successful application to biomarkers identification. More in particular by hard X-ray absorption spectroscopy we investigate how Atlantic oysters (*Crassostrea gigas*) and Mediterranean mussels (*Mytilus edulis*) store Zn in their tissues as potential indication of metal pollution. We found that oysters and mussels show very similar Zn storing mechanism and a coexistence of Zn-O and Zn-S bonded-species, which the relative fraction resulting clearly correlated to the amount of MeHg, AsB, and Ni present in the samples. Our findings throw light on the intrinsic heavy metal storing mechanism of these aquatic organisms, and also provide a tool to monitor the sea MeHg, AsB, and Ni aquatic pollution by using oysters and mussels as biomarkers.

References:

- [1] Garner, C. D.; Hasain, S. S.; Bremner, I.; Bordas, J., An EXAFS study of the zinc sites in sheep liver metallothionein. *J. Inorg. Biochem.* **1982**, 16, 253-256;
- [2] Ross, I.; Binstead, N.; Blackburn, N. J.; Bremner, I.; Diakun, G. P.; Hasnain, S. S.; Knowles, P. F.; Vasak, M.; Garner, C. D., EXAFS studies of copper and zinc in metallothionein and bovine superoxide dismutase. *Inorg. Chim. Acta* **1983**, 79, 89-90;
- [3] Charnock, J. M.; Garner, C. D.; Abrahams, I. L.; Arber, J. M.; Hasnain, S. S.; Henehan, C.; Vasak, M., EXAFS studies of metallothionein. *Physica B* **1989**, 158, 93-94.
- [4] Tan, Q-G.; Wang, Y.; Wang, W-X., Speciation of Cu and Zn in Two Colored Oyster Species Determined by X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2015**, 49 (11), 6919–6925.

- [5] Beauchemin, S.; Hesterberg, D.; Nadeau, J.; McGeer, J. C., Speciation of hepatic Zn in trout exposed to elevated waterborne Zn using X-ray absorption spectroscopy. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2004**, *38*, 1288-1295.
- [6] Pokrovsky, O. S.; Pokrovski, G. S.; Gelabert, A.; Schott, J.; Boudou, A., Speciation of Zn associated with diatoms using X-ray absorption spectroscopy. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2005**, *39* (12), 4490–4498.
- [7] Mishra, B.; Boyanov, M. I.; Bunker, B. A.; Kelly, S. D.; Kemner, K. M.; Nerenberg, R.; Read-Daily, B. L.; Fein, J. B., An X-ray absorption spectroscopy study of Cd binding onto bacterial consortia. *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta* **2009**, *73* (15), 4311–4325.
- [8] Pokrovsky, O. S.; Pokrovski, G. S.; Shirokova, L. S.; Gonzalez, A.G.; Emnova, E. E.; Feurtet-Mazel, A., Chemical and structural status of copper associated with oxygenic and anoxygenic phototrophs and heterotrophs: possible evolutionary consequences. *Geobiology* **2012**, *10* (2), 130–149.
- [9] Simonelli, L.; Restituyo Silis, M.; Marini, C.; Avila, M.; Olszewski, W.; Subirana, M.A.; Lopez-Mesas, M.; Vailente, M., Atlantic Oysters and Mediterranean Mussels Characterization by XAS Techniques as Biomarkers for Coastal Metal Pollution, to submit to *Environmental Science and Technology*

Using mass spectrometry to monitor the interaction of metallic compounds with biomolecules

Òscar PALACIOS^{a)}, Mercè CAPDEVILA^{a)}

^{a)} *Department of Chemistry, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, E- 08193 Cerdanyola del Vallès (Barcelona) Spain*
oscar.palacios@uab.cat

Due to the high number of existing metalloproteins and their involvement in several natural processes and diseases, the analysis of the interaction between proteins and metals became crucial for understanding the role of the metal ions in living organisms. Also, the increasing use of metal-based drugs for the treatment of different kind of diseases imposes the need of developing new tools to study these interactions. In recent years, electrospray ionization mass spectrometry (ESI-MS) has emerged as an extremely valuable and powerful method to monitor the interactions between metal ions and different kind of biomolecules. In spite of the relatively common use of nano-ESI sources for these purposes, this special methodology requires very specific conditions to be applied, while showing some limitations in reproducibility.

The optimization of conventional ESI sources to the study of these interactions has become one of the current goals. Hence, we adapted the conditions of a standard ESI source instrument, equipped with a TOF high resolution analyzer, to study the interactions between metallic complexes (Pt(II), Ru(II), Re(I) and Tc(I)) and biomolecules (proteins and DNA) [1], as well as the interaction of several metal ions (Zn(II), Cd(II), Cu(I), Pb(II)) with Cys-rich proteins, namely metallothioneins [2]. When necessary, the MS results have been complemented with spectroscopic data (DC, UV-vis, fluorimetry) to better understand the nature of the metal-biomolecules interactions.

References:

- [1] Samper, K.G.; Vicente, C.; Rodriguez, V.; Atrian, S.; Cutillas, N.; Capdevila, M.; Ruiz, J.; Palacios, O., Studing the interactions of a platinum(II) 9-aminoacridine complex with proteins and oligonucleotides by ESI-TOF MS. *Dalton Trans.* **2012**, 41, 300-306.
- [2] Pérez-Rafael, S.; Atrian, S.; Capdevila, M.; Palacios, O., Differential ESI-MS behavior of highly similar metallothioneins. *Talanta* **2010**, 83, 1057-1061.

Studies on mutants of Colicin E7 metallonuclease - Crystal structures vs. aqueous solution

Eszter NÉMETH^{a*)}, Anikó CZENE^{a)}, Sine LARSEN^{b)}, Ria K. BALOGH^{c)}, Béla GYURCSIK^{c)}

^{a)} MTA-SZTE, Bioinorganic Chemistry Research Group of Hungarian Academy of Sciences, Szeged, Hungary; *Present address: Nagata Special Laboratory, Faculty of Medicine, University of Tsukuba, Tsukuba, Japan ^{b)} Department of Chemistry, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark ^{c)} Department of Inorganic and Analytical Chemistry, University of Szeged, Szeged, Hungary
gyurcsik@chem.u-szeged.hu

Colicin E7 is the nuclease toxin of *Escherichia coli* bacteria, expressed under stress conditions. Its nuclease domain (NColE7) enters the target cell killing it through the non-specific digestion of the nucleic acids. The C-terminus of this enzyme comprises an HNH active centre made up of ~ 40 amino acids. It forms a $\beta\beta\alpha$ -type Zn^{2+} -ion binding structure. The HNH motif binds to the 3' site of the scissile phosphodiester-group in the DNA minor groove, while the central helical regions of NColE7 form strong nonspecific interactions in the major groove [1].

The DNA cleavage mechanism of NColE7 has been widely studied. It was proposed that the H544, H569, H573 side-chains at the C-terminus have essential role of the coordinating the metal ion [1], while the fourth, uncoordinated His (H545) generates an activated water molecule for the nucleophilic attack of the scissile phosphodiester group. It is a striking feature of NColE7 that its N-terminus is also involved in the catalytic reaction. The ~ 40 amino acids long sequence does not show any well-defined secondary structure, but the positively charged Arg at its N-terminus is necessary for effective nuclease activity [2]. Similarly, a positively charged amino acid distant in the sequence, but spatially close to the active centre can be commonly observed in the HNH nucleases. These amino acids may have multiple role in the enzymatic mechanism, such as the binding of the substrate at the cleavage site and thereby contribute to structural distortion and electrostatic activation, stabilization of the transition state intermedier and/or the leaving group. Besides, they also may participate in the proton transfer reaction between H545 and the leaving group.

In addition, the N-terminus was also found to affect the structure of the enzyme, inducing a disorder in the protein folding. This also affected the metal ion binding ability of the enzyme, which is crucial for its nuclease activity. On the other hand the binding of the DNA substrate or the enzyme inhibitor Im7 immunity protein in some cases could induce the folding of the mutants into the native-like structure, similarly to the effect of the protein-protein interactions within the family of the intrinsically disordered proteins.

The above findings may allow for controlling of the conserved metal binding catalytic motif of NColE7 through an intramolecular allosteric activation by a distal part of the protein. Therefore, to get a more detailed insight into the role of the above mentioned residues, we designed eight variants of NColE7 (Scheme 1), including N-terminal truncated mutants, missing 4, 25, 45 or 69 amino acid residues [2], as well as, point mutants substituting the

(T454) threonine and/or (K458) lysine and/or (W464) tryptophan amino acid with alanines [3].

Scheme 1. Schematic drawing of the NCoIE7 variants. TKW symbolizes the TKW, TK, KW or W NCoIE7 point mutants, in which T454A and/or K458A and/or W464A mutations were performed. For the truncated mutants X in the ΔNX notation indicates the number of deleted amino acids at their N-termini out of the total 131 amino acids of NCoIE7.

We have studied the effects of the individual amino acids in this region on the solution structure, metal-ion and DNA binding properties, as well as the catalytic activity of the mutants. Protein crystallization experiments were also carried out for comparison with the results of the solution studies. These experiments clearly showed that mutations within the four N-terminal amino acids, even their deletion did not affect the structure significantly, while having dramatic effect on the catalytic activity. At the same time the structure collapsed upon the exchange of W464 to alanine. These mutants could not be crystallized, while the former variants yielded crystals suitable for X-ray diffractometry (Figure 1)

Figure. 1. An example of the commonly observed shape of protein crystals of the NCoIE7 mutants at N-terminus (left panel), and precipitate with the W464A mutants (right panel).

These results inspired us to investigate the structural consequences of the interaction of mutant NCoIE7 proteins in aqueous solution in more detail. We showed how the folding of NCoIE7 is affected by mutations and by specific protein-protein or protein-substrate interactions using synchrotron radiation circular dichroism spectroscopy. The discrepancies between solution and crystallographic protein structure studies, will also be discussed.

References:

- [1] Doudeva, L.G., Huang, H., Hsia, K.C., Shi, Z., Li, C.L., Shen, Y., Cheng, C.L., Yuan, H.S., *Protein Sci.* 2006, 15, 269–280.
- [2] Czene, A., Tóth, E., Németh, E., Otten, H., Poulsen, J.C.N., Christensen, H.E.M., Rulíšek, L., Nagata, K., Larsen, S., Gyurcsik, B., *Metallomics* 2014, 6, 2090–2099.
- [3] Németh, E., Kožíšek, M., Schilli, G.K., Gyurcsik, B., *J. Inorg. Biochem.* 2015, 151, 143–149.

Targeting G-quadruplex DNA with fluorescent perylene derivatives

**Natalia BUSTO^{a) b) c)}, Patricia CALVO^{a)}, José GARCÍA^{a)}, Aurore GUÉDIN^{b) c)}, José M. LEAL^{a)},
Tomás TORROBA^{a)}, Jean Louis MERGNY^{b) c)}, Begoña GARCÍA^{a)}**

^{a)}Chemistry Department, University of Burgos, Pza. Misael Bañuelos s/n, 09001Burgos (Spain); ^{b)}ARNA Laboratory, University of Bordeaux, F-33000 Bordeaux (France); ^{c)}INSERM U1212, CNRS UMR 5320, IECB, F-33600 Pessac (France);
nataliabyv@msn.com

DNA guanine rich stretches are able to fold in G-quadruplex structures (G4) in which four guanines interact by Hoogsteen hydrogen bonds and form a tetrad square planar structure. Two or more of these G-tetrads are stabilized by stacking and by the presence of a monovalent cation in the central channel. The biological role of G4 structures is not completely understood but evidences suggest that they are involved in a number of regulatory processes such as DNA replication and stability, transcription, translation and telomere maintenance. Therefore, the search of molecules able to interact and stabilize these structures has attracted much attention in the scientific community.

In this work we show the synthesis of some perylene derivatives and their interaction with several G-quadruplexes in order to evaluate structure – reactivity relationships. Firstly, the selectivity of the synthesized probes for a particular conformation and/or sequence was evaluated by a FRET melting assay. [1] Interestingly, the tested perylene derivatives that are able to interact with G-quadruplex display higher stabilization in quadruplexes with only 2 tetrads in their structure than in three-tetrad quadruplexes (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Thermal stabilization of different G-quadruplex sequences with a perylene monoimide derivative at several concentrations.

Then, the interaction of these fluorescent probes with some of the above G4 structures was studied by a range of techniques, namely, absorption, fluorescence and circular dichroism spectroscopy, isothermal titration calorimetry and relaxation T-jump.

In addition, their potential biological effect such as telomerase activity inhibition and cytotoxicity was also evaluated in tumour (HeLa) and healthy (IMR-90) cell lines. Finally, their selectivity towards G4 in comparison to duplex DNA (ctDNA) has been also evaluated.

Acknowledgments

The financial support of Obra Social “la Caixa” (project OSLC-2012-007), MINECO, Spain (CTQ2014-58812-C2-2-R, FEDER Funds) and José Castillejo Program of the Spanish Ministry of Education, Culture and Sports (JC2015-00403) is gratefully acknowledged. J.L.M. acknowledges support from Conseil Regional d'Aquitaine, Fondation ARC and Agence Nationale de la Recherche (ANR Quarpdiem and Oligoswitch).

References:

[1] De Rache, A.; Mergny, J.L., Assessment of selectivity of G-quadruplex ligands via an optimised FRET melting assay. *Biochimie* **2015**, 115, 194-202.

Efficient Fluoride Adsorption by mesoporous Hierarchical Alumina Microspheres

Sara GRACIA LANAS^{a)}, Manuel VALIENTE^{b)}, Marilena TOLAZZI^{a)}, Andrea MELCHIOR^{a)}

*a) Dipartimento Politecnico, Laboratori di Scienze e Tecnologie Chimiche Università di Udine,
Via del Cottonificio 108, 33100 Udine, Italy* *b) Departamento de Química, Centre GTS,
Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Campus Bellaterra Edificio CN, Barcelona, Spain*
gracialanas.saraisabel@spes.uniud.it

Fluoride (F⁻) in drinking water has a harmful effect on health, as an excessive intake of F⁻ for a long period can result in skeletal fluorosis [1]. Therefore, the concentration in water should not exceed 1.5mg L⁻¹ [1]. Minerals containing F⁻ are used in several industries which contribute to F⁻ pollution with concentrations that can reach thousands of mg L⁻¹, much higher than the acceptable level in drinking water.

In order to reduce F⁻ concentration in drinking water, different methods have been developed such as adsorption, precipitation, electro-coagulation or ion-exchange [1]. Among the technologies used for F⁻ removal, adsorption is the most viable method due to its flexibility and simplicity of design, ease of operation and low cost.

The application of nanostructured materials with mesoporous nature for water defluoridation have been widely studied in recent years[2], as, due to their high surface area and high loading capacity, they are ideal adsorbents[3]. Among the various adsorbents available, alumina (Al₂O₃) has been recognized as one of the most effective materials for water defluoridation because of the high surface area and porosity, thermal stability and low solubility in a wide pH range [4]. According to these premises, hierarchically structured alumina microspheres (HAM) seem to be promising candidates for effective F⁻ removal from contaminated waters.

The scope of this work is to prepare new HAM differing for structural/morphological parameters and define the F⁻ adsorption in terms of loading capacity and thermodynamics of the process. HAM have been prepared and characterized by standard methods, while adsorption studies have been performed using a new experimental approach, which combines potentiometry and Isothermal Titration Calorimetry (ITC). While in previous works ΔH_{ads} (enthalpy of adsorption) related to F⁻ adsorption have been calculated by the van't Hoff equation, ITC is applied for the first time in this work for the direct determination of ΔH_{ads} . Different HAM with high efficiency for F⁻ adsorption were synthesized based on the reported methodology [5-7] with some modifications. Two types of HAM have been obtained and characterized by SEM, TEM, BET, porosimetry, Dynamic Light Scattering and XRD, which reveals that the synthesized materials differ mostly for crystallinity. It has been suggested in the literature that crystallinity has an influence for fluoride adsorption capacity [3,8].

The equilibrium data are well described by Langmuir isotherm while a two-step process describes the adsorption kinetics. The adsorption constant obtained for the amorphous HAM (HAM-A) is one order of magnitude higher than the material with a higher degree of crystallinity (HAM-B), showing that a small change in the synthetic protocol has an important effect on this parameter. The highest defluoridation capacity reaches 26 mmol·g⁻¹ after 1 hour of equilibration for HAM-A, revealing that the adsorption is rapid and that the adsorbent has high affinity for F⁻. Contrarily to the data presented in most previous works, the ΔH_{ads} values obtained are clearly negative (Figure 1) for the different samples investigated.

Figure 1. ITC for F⁻ adsorption into HAM-A (blue) and HAM-B (green).

References:

- [1] Bhatnagar, A.; Kumar, E.; Sillanpää, M., Fluoride removal from water by adsorption: A review. *Chem. Eng. J.* **2011**, 171, 811–840.
- [2] Kang, D.; Tong, S.; Yu X.; Ge, M., Template-free synthesis of 3D hierarchical amorphous aluminum oxide microspheres with broccoli-like structure and their application in fluoride removal. *RSC Adv.* **2015**, 5, 19159–19165.
- [3] Cai, W.; Yu, J.; Gu S.; Jaroniec, M., Facile hydrothermal synthesis of hierarchical boehmite: Sulfate-mediated transformation from nanoflakes to hollow microspheres. *Cryst. Growth Des.* **2010**, 10, 3977–3982.
- [4] Kim, Y.; Kim, C.; Choi, I.; Rengaraj S.; Yi, J., Arsenic Removal Using Mesoporous Alumina Prepared via a Templating Method. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2004**, 38, 924–931.
- [5] Cai, W.; Yu J.; Mann, S., Template-free hydrothermal fabrication of hierarchically organized γ -AlOOH hollow microspheres. *Micropor. Mesopor. Mat.* **2009**, 122, 42–47.
- [6] Wu, X.; Zhang B.; Hu, Z., Microwave hydrothermal synthesis of boehmite hollow microspheres. *Mater. Lett.* **2012**, 73, 169–171.
- [7] Wu, X.; Zhang B.; Hu, Z., Microwave hydrothermal synthesis of core-shell structured boehmite. *Mater. Lett.* **2013**, 91, 249–251.
- [8] Du, J.; Sabatini, D. A.; Butler, E. C., Synthesis, characterization, and evaluation of simple aluminum-based adsorbents for fluoride removal from drinking water. *Chemosphere* **2014**, 101, 21–27.

Influence of organic ligands on the sorption and solubility of radionuclides

Mireia GRIVÉ^{a)}, Elisenda COLÀS^{a)}, Jordi BRUNO^{a)}

^{a)} *Amphos 21, Pg. Garcia i Fària, 49-51, Barcelona, Spain*
eli.colas@amphos21.com

Low- and intermediate- level radioactive wastes usually have a very diverse origin and composition. A wide variety of organic materials (such as packaging plastics, clothes, paper, gloves, cement additives, cleaning agents or ion-exchange resins) are generally present among them [1]. In particular,

-Polyaminocarboxylic acids such as EDTA or NTA, which may be used in decontamination procedures.

-Polyhydroxycarboxylic acids such as gluconate (a simple model to account for complex cement additives) and isosaccharinate (the most important degradation product of cellulose in alkaline pore waters) are likely to be present due to the important amount of cement used in the building of the repository and the conditioning of waste.

-Dicarboxylic acids such as oxalate may be formed due to bitumen or ion-exchange resin degradation, and tricarboxylic acids as citrate are also used in decontamination procedures.

Those organic materials are of special interest as they may influence the mobility of radionuclides [2], and may exhibit different behaviour depending on their chemical characteristics.

In this work, we have reviewed the affinity of these ligands with different radionuclides at different oxidation states (Cs(I), Ni(II), Eu(III), Th(IV)) in the alkaline pH range characteristic of cement environments. Using this information, a simple calculation tool has been developed in order to easily handle the influence of organic compounds on the mobility of radionuclides by considering both, the stability of the aqueous species formed and its impact on the radionuclide sorption behaviour. Knowledge gaps relevant for the safety assessment in the radionuclide –organic ligand – calcium system have been identified.

Acknowledgements

This work has been financially supported by SKB.

References:

- [1] Fanger, G.; Skagius, K.; Wiborgh, M., Project SAFE. Complexing agents in SFR, *SKB Technical Report 2001*, R-01-04.
- [2] Hummel, W.; Anderegg, G.; Puigdomenech, I.; Rao, L.; Tochiyama, O., *Chemical Thermodynamics Volume 9: Chemical Thermodynamics of Compounds and Complexes of U, Np, Pu, Am, Tc, Se, Ni and Zr with Selected Organic Ligands* Elsevier: Amsterdam, **2005**; Vol. 9, pp 1088

PLENARY LECTURE

Metal Imaging at Nanometer Level in Biological Cells by Nano Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry (NanoSIMS)

Dirk SCHAUMLÖFFEL^{a)}, Julien MALHERBE^{a)}

*a) Université de Pau et des Pays de l'Adour/CNRS, Institut des Sciences Analytiques et de Physico-Chimie pour l'Environnement et les Matériaux (IPREM) UMR 5254, Pau, France ;
dirk.schaumloeffel@univ-pau.fr*

Nano secondary ion mass spectrometry (NanoSIMS) is an analytical technique which relies on the sputtering of ions from a solid surface by focused positive or negative primary ion beams and the subsequent analysis of the produced secondary ions by a mass spectrometer under high vacuum. Thus, the NanoSIMS can be described as a scanning ion microprobe which can analyse at the sub-micrometre scale and produce elemental and isotopic images in 2D and 3D. State-of-the-art NanoSIMS equipment allows chemical imaging of a sample surface by the detection of almost all elements (including their stable isotopes) of the periodic table with lateral resolution below 50 nm combined with high sensitivity. Detection of seven elements in parallel is possible. Since its introduction in the 1990s, the high spatial resolution and high sensitivity of the NanoSIMS opened numerous new research possibilities. An important increasing application field is element specific bioimaging [1]. NanoSIMS is perfectly suited to localize the distribution of chemical elements with high spatial resolution in a biological sample, e.g. for metal imaging at the cellular and even at the subcellular level. This can be an important contribution to study biochemical functions, biosorption, transport, and bioaccumulation processes of metals in biological cells.

This lecture gives a general introduction to the NanoSIMS technique and highlights its performance and challenges for bioimaging of metals at nanometer level in individual biological cells. This includes sample preparation strategies which is a difficult issue as physiological important metal ions are often highly diffusible. All this will be illustrated by localization of essential metals (e.g. Ca, Mg, Fe, Cu, Zn) together with major elements (C, N, S, and P) in cell cultures of model organisms. In addition, an example for ¹³C stable isotope labelling of metabolites will be presented which enabled the localization of physiological processes inside a cell such as metal stress induced by cadmium. Correlative imaging with other bioimaging techniques allowed the confirmation of results. In outlook will be given to the prospects of bioimaging for trace metal research in health and disease.

References:

- [1] Schaumlöffel, D.; Hutchinson, R.; Malherbe, J.; Le Coustumer, P.; Gontier, E.; Isaure, M.-P., Novel Methods for Bioimaging Including LA-ICP-MS, NanoSIMS, TEM/X-EDS, and SXRF. In: *Metallomics: Analytical Techniques and Speciation Methods*, ed. Michalke, B., John Wiley and Sons **2016**, in press

Alizarine red's immobilized on triacetylcellulose film tapes for metal ions sensing.

Raffaella BIESUZ^{a)}, Anna MARIATIVELLI^{a)}, Giancarla ALBERTI^{a)}

*^{a)}Department of Chemistry University of Pavia via Taramelli 12 Pavia
Italy rbiesuz@unipv.it*

We selected triacetylcellulose as solid phase and Alizarin Red S as metal indicator with the intent to produce a probe for the simultaneous detection of trivalent metal ions in water samples.

The transparent triacetylcellulose membranes were produced from photographic film tapes, previously treated with NaClO to remove coloured gelatinous layers. The ligand was immobilized via ion pair with cetylpyridinium chloride (CPC), under mild conditions [1, 2].

The final material showed good mechanical properties and was characterized to establish the kinetics and thermodynamic properties through the usual experimental sorption profiles. The sorption isotherms confirmed the concentration of ligand on the membrane (independently measured) and the sorption profiles as function of pH were in pretty good agreement with those expected from the formation constants reported in literature for the same metal- ligand systems in solution.

The maximum sorption capacity, slightly dependant on membrane size, was around 0.003 mmol/g, extremely low, if compared other solid materials for metal sorption, but the driving force is here the change in the colour on these thin membrane, so sensing, and not removal capacity.

Sorption studies in function of the pH of the solution were performed in order to explore the pH interval that guarantees the quantitative formation of the complex in the solid phase.

In the second step, the chromatic properties of the derivatized membranes were studied via spectrophotometric measurements of the solid phase (operative condition: pH=4.5, overnight loading of metals, excess of ligand).

At a first stage, Fe(III) , Al(III) and Cu(II) were the metal ions selected for this system.

The entire visible spectrum was employed for the analysis.

Firstly, we selected a proper data set, called training set, with a combination of 16 standard solutions to cover symmetrically the entire experimental domain. We used the Multilevel Partial Factorial Design to choose the combination of metals for the standard solutions. Then we used PLS to find the most suitable model to correlate the spectra of these Aliz-films with metals concentrations.

In figure 1, the regression models for Aluminum and Iron created on the colour developed by Aliz-films after equilibration, are presented. The true values are reported versus the calculated ones. Copper was finally excluded from this modeling.

The regression model was firstly tested with a cross-validated procedure, and then on an external data set, called test set. A series of independent samples of metals was prepared

for this purpose and validates the regression models of each metal ions (prediction for Al and Fe around 10%).

Figure 1: a) PLS model of aluminium of Aliz-films spectra; b) PLS model of iron of Aliz-films spectra (pH4.5, I=0.1M, w=0.022g)

Tests on real samples included the determination of Aluminum in a tea infusion and of Aluminum and Iron in a sample of sewage sludge (via acid digestion with HF and HNO₃ in sealed telfon vessel heated at 130°C overnight).

The true values refer to the ICP OES determination. The results, predicted after equilibration of the same solutions on Aliz-film with the PLS models, are reported in table 1

Table 1 result of real samples with PLS model and ICP-OES

Sample	aluminium			iron		
	PLS model (M)	ICP (M)	Err%	PLS model (M)	ICP (M)	Err%
s.sludge	1.5(4)*10 ⁻⁴	1.39(3)*10 ⁻⁴	+5.8%	4.6(7)*10 ⁻⁵	5.17(9)*10 ⁻⁵	-11.8%
Tea	4.88(6)*10 ⁻⁴	4.40(2)*10 ⁻⁴	+10.9			

An estimate of the detection limit was performed on blank spectra of Alizarin Red S solid film. Since the concentrations given by the regression output refer to the solid phase (mmol/g), employing the smallest Aliz-film with the largest volume of sample, for our experimental setup, the operative LOD estimate, referred to solution phase corresponds to values around 7*10⁻⁸ M of Aluminum end 1*10⁻⁷ M of Iron.

References:

[1] Safavi, A.; Bagheri, M., A novel optical sensor for uranium determination. *Analytica Chimica Acta* **2005**, 530, 55-60.
 [2] Safavi, A.; Bagheri, M., Novel optical pH sensor for high and low pH values. *Sensors and Actuators B* **2003**, 90, 143-150.
 [3] Brereton, R., Multilevel Multifactorial Design for Multivariate Calibration. *Analyst*, **1997**, 122 1521-1522.

The Chemistry of Metal-Organic Non-Trivial Structures

Ali TRABOLSI^{a)}, Rana A. BILBEISI^{a)}, Thirumurugan PRAKASAM^{a)}

^{a)}New York University Abu Dhabi, Abu Dhabi, UAE.

ali.trabolsi@nyu.edu

Where will the chemistry of topologically non-trivial structures lead us? Will there be practical applications for such complex molecules? These two questions have challenged chemists since the field of molecular topology started, particular since its explosive growth over the past 25 years. Fast-paced development of synthetic methods has led to the preparation of a variety of complex molecules; however, landmarks in the field of molecular topology have remained, for the most part, aesthetic achievements rather than practical advances, as the search for applications continues. The complexity of these structures makes it hard to scale them up, which is critical for their assessment, in addition to the challenge of post-synthetic modifications, which limit their use as building blocks for advanced materials.

To address these challenges, recent research by the Trabolsi group has focused on the synthesis of complex non-trivial structures from simple chelating ligands and metal ions. The strategy involves the use of metal templates and the dynamic covalent chemistry of imine-bond formation. Initial experiments produced mixtures of three zinc-based non-trivial structures, a [2]catenane, a trefoil knot, and a Solomon link. The [2]catenane and the trefoil knot were then isolated and characterized by means of NMR spectroscopy, mass spectrometry, and X-ray crystallography. Through reaction optimization, the [2]catenane or the trefoil knot could be selectively formed and scaled up in solution (one pot, 5g scale, 80-100 % yield). The zinc-based trefoil knot can host a variety of mono-charged anions in its cavity, in solution and the solid state. Such host-guest associations enhance the thermal stability of the trefoil knot in solution.

Two main aims will be outlined in my presentation. (1) Advancing understanding at the molecular level of metal-directed synthesis of metal-organic links, and the potential of their post-synthetic modification, and (2) Exploring the anion-binding properties of trefoil knots and establish a triple structure-property-reactivity relationship by using a library of different anions and metal-based links.

Figure 1: a) Controlling the outcome of the reaction leading to a library of metal-templated knots and links either by adjusting the reaction temperature or via the use of different sizes anions as templates. b) post synthetic modification of Cd-based molecular links and knots.

References:

- [1] Bilbeisi, R.A.; Prakasam T.; Lusi, M.; El-Khoury, C.; Platas-Iglesias, L.J.; Charbonnière, J.; Olsen, J.-C.; Elhabiri, M.; Trabolsi, A., [C–H⋯Anion] Interactions Mediate the Templatation and Anion Binding Properties of Topologically Non-Trivial Metal-Organic Structures in Aqueous Solutions. *Chem. Sci.* **2016**, Advanced Article.
- [2] Prakasam, T.; Lusi, M.; Elhabiri, M.; Platas-Iglesias, C.; Olsen, J.-C.; Asfari, Z.; Cianférani-Sangler, S.; Debaene, F.; Charbonnière L.J.; Trabolsi, A., Simultaneous Self-Assembly of a [2]Catenane, a Trefoil Knot, and a Solomon Link from a Simple Pair of Ligands. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2013**, 52, 1-6.

Kinetics of the Formation of a Rotaxane from the End-Capping Process of a Pseudorotaxane.

Eva BERNAL^{a)}, Victoria I. MARTÍN^{a)}, Pilar LOPEZ^{a)}, Manuel LÓPEZ^{b)}, Maria Luisa MOYÁ^{a)}

^{a)} University of Seville, Dept. Physical Chemistry, C/Profesor García González 1 41012 Seville Spain; ^{b)} University of Huelva, Dept. of Chemical Engineering, Physical Chemistry and Material Science. Avda. Tres de Marzo s/n. Campus El Carmen. 21071 Huelva.
evabernal@us.es

A rotaxane is a supramolecular assembly formed by a linear axle which penetrates into the cavity of a cyclic molecule and is capped with bulky end groups to prevent the exit of the axle from the inner cavity of the macrocycle. Different systems have been used as axle (surfactants, polymers, linear ligands, etc) [1] and as wheel (cyclodextrins, crown ether, calixarene, etc) [2].

In this work the formation of a rotaxane by an end-capping process between a pseudorotaxane, formed by the surfactant triethyl(1-(isonicotinoiloxi)undecyl)ammonium bromide and β -cyclodextrin, and the complex $\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{CN})_5\text{H}_2\text{O}^{3-}$ was investigated (see Figure 1). This rotaxane was subsequently opened, through a ligand substitution reaction, by adding cyanide ions. The two processes were also investigated in the absence of β -cyclodextrin for the sake of comparison.

Figure 1: Formation of the rotaxane

Conventional and two-dimensional, 2D, rotating frame nuclear Overhauser effect ^1H NMR experiments show the formation and subsequent opening of the rotaxane.

Acknowledgements

This work was financed by Consejería de Innovación, Ciencia y Empresa de la Junta de Andalucía (FQM-274 and P12-FQM-1105) and FEDER funds.

References:

- [1] Liu, Y.; Zhao, Y-L.; Zhang, H-Y.; Song, H-B., Polymeric Rotaxane Constructed from the Inclusion Complex of β -Cyclodextrin and 4,4'-Dipyridine by Coordination with Nickel(II) Ions. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2003**, 42, 3260.
- [2] Jiménez-Molero, M. C.; Dietrich-Buchecker, C.; Sauvage, Chemically Induced Contraction and Stretching of a Linear Rotaxane Dimer. *J.- P. Chem. Eur. J.* **2002**, 8, 1456.

Nanoparticle systems for future sensing and (bio)targeting applications

Jingjing ZHAO^{a)}, Julio BASTOS^{b)}, Montserrat RESINA-GALLEGO^{a)}, Raquel MONTES^{c)}, Mireia BAEZA^{c)}, Cristina PALET^{a)}

^{a)}Centre Grup de Tècniques de Separació en Química, Unitat de Q.Analítica, Departament de Química, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 08193 Bellaterra, Catalunya, Spain; ^{b)} Departament d'Enginyeria Química, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC), Av. Diagonal 647, 08028 Barcelona, Spain; ^{c)}Grup de Sensors i Bioensors, Unitat de Q.Analítica, Departament de Química, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 08193 Bellaterra, Catalunya, Spain.

jingjing.zhao@uab.cat

Everyday humans interact with a great amount of different materials and with the imminent need to control matter. Since the very beginning of their existence, humans have design materials to change and take advantage of the surrounding elements to improve their life quality.

The main aim of material scientist is to overcome with new efficient and low cost methodologies for the preparation of novel materials. Taking that into account, the incorporation of Nanomaterials (NMs) into bulk components has become a priority.^{1,2}

The design of materials depends on the current necessities of the society, the availability of resources and the investment required for an appropriate scale up production.

Metal nanoparticles of Ag and Au (AgNPs and AuNPs, respectively) are here prepared and used for electrode composite materials. We present the electrochemical characterization of recently prepared electrode composite nanomaterials.

Further research of these materials, includes the design and development of biosensing technologies, together with their use as modifiers of nanodiamond systems (NDs), which are a novel class of nanomaterials interesting for their application in biomedical field, as they are biocompatible (possibility of being produced on large scale and with relatively inexpensive synthetic methodologies).³

Acknowledgments:

This work has been financially supported by the project CHEMNEXUS (Ref: CTM2015-65414-C2-1-R) from the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (MINECO) and the European Regional Development Fund (FEDER). Jingjing Zhao thanks to the China Scholarship Council for her grant.

References:

- [1] Campelo, J.M.; Luna, D.; Luque, R.; Marinas, J. M.; Romero, A., Sustainable Preparation of Supported Metal Nanoparticle and Their Applications in Catalysis. *ChemSusChem* **2009**, 2(1), 18–45.
- [2] Polshettiwar, V.; Luque, R.; Fihri, A.; Zhu, H.; Bouhrara, M.; Basset, J.-M., Magnetically Recoverable Nanocatalysis. *Chem. Rev.* **2011**, 111(5), 3036-3075.
- [3] Mochalin, V. N.; Shenderova, O.; Ho, D.; Gogotsi, Y., The properties and applications of nanodiamonds. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **2012**, 7, 11–23.

Perylene-bisimide (PBI) metal complexes as stabilizers of carbon nanotubes mixtures for temperature sensing

Romualdo BIANCO^{a)}, Tarita BIVER^{a)}, Francesco CRISCITIELLO^{a)}, Andrea PUCCI^{a)}, Anita SCIGLIANO^{a)}, Fernando SECCO^{a)}

^{a)} Department of Chemistry and Industrial Chemistry – University of Pisa – Via Moruzzi 13, 56124 Pisa - Italy

It has been observed that perylene-bisimide (PBI) derivatives can show interesting properties concerning biosubstrates binding and non-canonical nucleic acids forms stabilization [1]. Moreover, they find use in new materials as stabilizers for carbon nanotubes and temperature sensors [2].

Therefore, it seemed to be of some interest, to perform a study of the metal complexation ability of a newly synthesised ligand, where the central perylene core (chromophore) is connected to two crown-ether residues (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The perylene-bisimide ligand used in this study

Absorbance titrations were analysed, also by means of the HypSpec2014[®] software, to shed light on the ligand affinity toward Ca^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Pb^{2+} metal ions and on the stoichiometry of complexes eventually formed. Nickel and cobalt do form the 1:1 complex and not quantitatively. In the case of Ca^{2+} , Fe^{3+} and Pb^{2+} the 1:1 ML complex can be quantitatively formed, even if other stoichiometries are possible.

The 1:1 Pery-Crown5/Ca, Pery-Crown5/Fe, Pery-Crown5/Pb complexes (together with Pery-Crown5 alone for comparison purposes) were then added to multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) mixtures. The stabilizing ability of the metal complexes towards MWCNTs was quantitatively measured by means of thermal analysis (TGA).

The deposition of MWCNT/Pery-Crown5 dispersions on plastic film supporting gold electrodes allowed the fabrication of temperature sensors, whose response was checked. The results obtained are promising and give interesting information on possible modulation and optimisation of the use of metal complexes in MWCNTs-based sensors.

References:

- [1] Biver, T., Stabilisation of non-canonical structures of nucleic acids by metal ions and small molecules. *Coordination Chemistry Reviews*, **2013**, 257, 2765– 2783.
- [2] Biver, T.; Criscitiello, F.; Di Francesco, F.; Minichino, M.; Swager, T.; Pucci, A., MWCNT/perylene bisimide water dispersions for miniaturized temperature sensors. *RSC Advances*, **2015**, 5, 65023–65029.

An(III) and Ln(III) complexation with TPAEN: selectivity quantification for an americium(III) separation process

N. BOUBALS^{a)}, L. CHANÉACA^{a)}, T. DUMASA^{a)}, G. MANIEA^{a)}, P. GUILBAUDA^{a)}

CEA, Nuclear Energy Division, Marcoule, RadioChemistry & Processes Department, F-30207 Bagnols sur Cèze, France; nathalie.boubals@cea.fr

Among the different options studied in Europe for the advanced reprocessing of nuclear fuels, and especially the recycling of minor actinides, one of them consist in separating the americium from the other fission products in order to reintroduce this element in the fuel cycle. The main challenge for the separation of americium is to find selective processes toward the lanthanide cation series and the curium cation that have close chemical behaviour at the III oxidation state.

One solvent extraction process aiming at the Am(III) separation has been studied in the framework of the SACSESS European project (FP7, Euratom Nuclear Fission and Radiation Protection Theme). This process uses the TODGA diglycolamide extractant in the organic phase, and the TPAEN (N,N,N,N'-tetrakis-tetrakis[-(6-carboxypyridine-2-yl)methyl]-ethylenediamine) complexant in the aqueous phase in order to take advantage of both ligand selectivities in the lanthanide(III) and actinide(III) cation series.

The TPAEN ligand was indeed identified as a selective ligand for the complexation of the americium(III) cation versus curium(III) and the lanthanide(III) cations [2]. In order to better understand this selectivity, the study presented here aims at characterizing the complexes formed between these cations and the TPAEN complexant in the aqueous phase.

Figure 1: TPAEN (N, N, N, N'-tetrakis-tetrakis [- (6-carboxypyridine 2-yl) methyl]-ethylenediamine

The stoichiometry of the americium complex was determined by X-ray absorption spectroscopy (EXAFS) showing that the complex is 1:1 and that the cation is bonded to 6 nitrogen atoms and 4 oxygen atoms coming from the carbonyl functions. Speciation studies using time-resolved laser induced fluorescence spectroscopy (TRLIFS) with Eu(III) and Cm(III) confirmed this stoichiometry and enabled the determination of the stability constants with these cations. The thermodynamic data associated with the complexation constants were also determined for La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Eu(III) and Dy(III) using micro-

calorimetry. At last, the TPAEN/Am(III) complexation constant was determined using UV/Vis spectrometry.

Figure 2: TPAEN / Am complex structure deduced from EXAFS

The comparison of all the data acquired during this study enabled us to quantify the selectivity of the TPAEN ligand for Am(III) over Cm(III). In the lanthanide(III) series, the maximum value met for Nd(III) and the relatively adjacent values for La(III) and Pr(III) are in agreement with the extraction experiments: the selectivity of the TPAEN ligand for Am(III), with some difficulties to separate from the light lanthanide(III) cations[1].

References:

- [1] Marie, C.; Duchesne, M.-T.; Russello, E.; Kaufholz, P.; Wilden, A.; Modolo, G.; Casnati, A.; Miguirditchian, M., Development of a selective americium separation process using TPAEN as a water-soluble stripping agent. *Proceedings of Global 2015*, Paris, France.
- [2] Heres, X.; Burdet, F.; Borrini, J.; Duchesne, M.-T.; Mazzanti, M.; Bernier, G.; Pellet-Rostaing, S.; Favre-Reguillon, A.; Lemaire, M., Process for separating americium from other metallic elements present in an acidic aqueous or organic phase and applications thereof. *Patent 2011*, WO2012069573.

Halogenide Anion Complexes with a Tetrazine-based Ligand

Matteo SAVASTANO^{a)}, Carla BAZZICALUPI^{a)}, Antonio BIANCHI^{a)}, Celeste GARCÍA^{b)}, Maria Dolores LÓPEZ de la TORRE^{b)}, Manuel MELGUIZO GUIJARRO^{b)}, Fabio PICHIERRI^{c)}

^{a)} Department of Chemistry “Ugo Schiff”, University of Florence, Via della Lastruccia 3, 50019, Sesto Fiorentino, Italy. ^{b)} Department of Inorganic and Organic Chemistry, University of Jaén 23071, Jaén, Spain. ^{c)} Department of Applied Chemistry, Graduate School of Engineering, Tohoku University, Sendai 980-8579, Japan.

matteo.savastano@unifi.it

Anion coordination chemistry has sparked considerable interest in recent years due to the ubiquitous presence of anions in biological and environmental systems, the roles they play in various biochemical processes, and their involvement in many technological areas. The design of receptors for the binding of anions in solution, in particular in water, can be very challenging as the non-covalent interactions employed to anchor anions to the receptor are weak, they must prevail over the competing anion-solvent interactions, and structural features that provide them are often difficult to build into the receptor framework. Fortunately, while individual non-covalent interactions are weak, collectively they could be made sufficiently powerful to afford polyfunctional receptors capable of strong and selective anion binding [1].

Anion- π interactions are among the most recently recognized non-covalent forces [2]. Their importance has long been underappreciated by the scientific community as it is counterintuitive to expect that an attraction may arise between a negatively charged species and common aromatic rings characterised by negative quadrupole moments. However, upon insertion of strongly electron-withdrawing substituents, these quadrupole moments can be inverted, turning parent aromatic systems into π -acids able to attract anions.

We present here preliminary thermodynamic and crystallographic results on the interaction of the tetrazine-based ligand L and halogenide anions. Tetrazines are strong π -acids and, thus, amenable to anion π interactions, but usually they have low water solubility. Functionalization with two morpholine groups makes them sufficiently soluble in water to be studied by means of pH-metric methods.

Potentiometric (pH-metric) titrations performed in aqueous solution showed that both mono- and diprotonated forms of L bind F^- , Cl^- , Br^- and I^- anions forming rather stable

complexes. The stability of these complexes is poorly affected by the ligand charge and by the anion ability to form hydrogen bonds, suggesting that other forces must furnish a significant contribution. The crystal structures of $(H_2L)F_2 \cdot 3H_2O \cdot MeOH$, $(H_2L)Cl_2$, $(H_2L)Br_2$ and $(H_2L)I_2 \cdot H_2O$ (Figure 1) showed that, in the solid state, all complexes are stabilized by an interplay of different weak forces, among which, anion- π interactions are invariably present and prominent. Reasonably, such anion- π interactions are also operative in solution and characterize the particular behaviour of these anion binding equilibria.

Density functional theory (DFT) calculations are in progress to further analyse these binding processes.

Figure 1. Crystal structures of $(H_2L)F_2 \cdot 3H_2O \cdot MeOH$, $(H_2L)Cl_2$, $(H_2L)Br_2$ and $(H_2L)I_2 \cdot H_2O$

References:

- [1] Bowman-James, K.; Bianchi, A.; Garcia-España, E., *Anion Coordination Chemistry*; Eds. Wiley-VCH: New York, **2012**.
- [2] Quiñero, D.; Garau, C.; Rotger, C.; Frontera, A.; Ballester, P.; Costa, A.; Deyà, P. M., Anion- π Interactions: Do They Exist?. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2002**, 41, 3389–3392

Novel bridging μ_2 -N7,O6-acyclovir mode in a tetranuclear complex having a cubane-like core $[\text{Ni}^{II}_4(\mu_3\text{-methanolato})_4]^{4+}$

Esther VÍLCHEZ-RODRÍGUEZ^{a)}, Duane CHOQUESILLO-LAZARTE^{b)}, Alicia DOMÍNGUEZ-MARTÍN^{a,c)}, Inmaculada PÉREZ-TORO^{a)}, Josefa María GONZÁLEZ-PÉREZ^{a)}, Alfonso CASTIÑEIRAS^{d)}, Juan NICLÓS-GUTIÉRREZ^{a)}

^{a)}Department of Inorganic Chemistry, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Granada, Granada, Spain, ^{b)} Laboratorio de Estudios Cristalográficos, IACT, CSIC-UGR, Av. de las Palmeras 4, 18100 Armilla, Granada, Spain, ^{c)} Department of Chemistry, University of Zurich, Winterthurerstrasse 190, 8057 Zurich, Switzerland, ^{d)} Department of Inorganic Chemistry, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Santiago de Compostela, Santiago de Compostela, Spain
iniclos@uqr.esa

Recent advances on the metal binding pattern (MBP) of acyclovir (acv, also called acyclo-guanosine) revealed that its N7-guanine donor atom is always involved in coordination. The formation of the M-N7(acv) bond alone or in cooperation of a X-H...O6(acv) intra-molecular interligand interaction represents the most frequent MBP of this synthetic purine nucleoside analogue (SPNA) [1]. Examples are known with less common MBP: chelating Cu^{II} -N7,O6-acv, bridging μ_2 -N7,O(ol) chain or a chelating+bridging tetradentate mode Cu^{II} - μ_4 -N7,O6,O(e),O(ol)-acv (where O(e) and O(ol) are the O-ether and O-alcohol atoms of the N9-acyclic side chain respectively).

Attempts to react nickel(II) nitrate or chloride with 2-(2-aminoethoxy)ethanol (2aee) and acv in methanol affords many single crystals (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Crystals of the novel tetranuclear Ni(II) complex with a $[\text{Ni}_4\text{O}_4]$ -cubane-like core.

But crystallographic studies lead to poor results, probably related to disorder in the N9-side chain of acv ligands and/or solvent molecules. The complex seems to be 2aee-free

and the same crystals have been obtained from nickel(II) chloride or nitrate salts. Best structural results only enables a modelling-cif file of the complex (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Structural modelling of the novel tetranuclear Ni-acv complex.

The $[\text{Ni}_4\text{O}_4]$ -cubane-like cage consists of four Ni(II) centres and four O-methanolate donor atoms. The stability of the cage is reinforced by four μ_2 -N7,O6-acv bridging ligands, a novel MBP for this SPNA [1,2]. The estimated bond distances Ni-N7 (2.083) and Ni-O6 (2.046) have usual values. In the compound each metal atom exhibits an octahedral coordination, fulfilled by an N7 and O6 donors from two distinct acv ligands, there O donors from three μ_3 -methanolate ligands and an O-hydroxo donor atom, ensuring the neutrality of the compound. Close similar $[\text{Ni}_4\text{O}_4]$ -cubane-like cages have been previously reported for this and other second-half first-row transition M(II) ions [3].

References:

- [1] Choquesillo-Lazarte, D.; Domínguez-Martín, A.; Vílchez-Rodríguez, E.; Pérez-Toro, I.; García-Rubiño, M.E.; Nurchi, V.M.; Matilla-Hernández, A.; González-Pérez, J.M.; Castiñeiras, A.; Niclós-Gutiérrez, J.; *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, **2016**, submitted.
- [2] García-Raso, A.; Fiol, J.J.; Badenas, F.; Cons, R.; Terrón, A.; Quirós, M., Synthesis and structural characteristics of metal–acyclovir (ACV) complexes: $[\text{Ni}(\text{or Co})(\text{ACV})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{ACV}$, $[\text{Zn}(\text{ACV})\text{Cl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$, $[\text{Cd}(\text{ACV})\text{Cl}_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\{\text{Hg}(\text{ACV})\text{Cl}_2\}_x]$. Recognition of acyclovir by Ni–ACV. *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.* **1999**, 2, 167-174.
- [3] Gao, Y.-Z.; Zhang, Y.-A.; Zhang, J., *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, **2015**, 54, 85-88, and references therein.

New polytopic ligands from pyridine-based -macrocycles and open chain bipodal chelator moieties.

Lluís GUIJARRO^{a)}, Begoña VERDEJO^{a)}, Mario INCLAN^{a)}, Enrique GARCÍA-ESPAÑA^{a)}

^{a)} Molecular Science Institute (ICMol), Department of Inorganic Chemistry, University of Valencia, Catedrático José Beltrán 2, 46980, Paterna, Valencia, Spain
lluis.guijarro@uv.es

The combination of distinctly different metal ion binding sites within one ligand can lead to new metal-complexes with interesting new properties in fields such as molecular recognition, molecular devices, enzyme mimicking and pharmaceutical chemistry.[1]

With this aim, great efforts have been made in the Supramolecular Chemistry Group of the University of Valencia to combine the well-known pyridine-based ligand, PYTREN, with open chain chelators offering structural flexibility that can presents new properties. The coordination chemistry and SOD mimicking activity of PYTREN have been fully described.[2]

Here we report a new family of ligands that combine the macrocyclic moiety py22 with a tripodal open-chain chelating unit having quinolines, pyridines or anthracenes as terminal units (red in scheme). These ligands are expected to coordinate not only one metal ion but

also two metal ions with different coordination environment.

Scheme. Drawing of the new ligands with the tripodal open-chain chelating units with: 2-Pyridine, Anthracene and 4-Quinoline.

The metal ion coordination capability of the new ligands has been studied by means of potentiometric titrations, UV-Vis and fluorescence techniques.

References:

- [1] Zanello, P.; Tamburirni, S.; Vigato, P. A.; Mazzochin, G. A, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, Syntheses, structure and electrochemical characterization of homo- and heterodinuclear copper complexes with compartmental ligands. **1987**, *77*, 165-273. Serrano-Plana, J.; Costas, M.; Compañ, A., Building Complexity in O₂-Binding Copper Complexes. Site-Selective Metalation and Intermolecular O₂-Binding at Dicopper and Heterometallic Complexes Derived from an Unsymmetric Ligand. *Inorg. Chem*, **2014**, *53* (24), 12929-12938.
- [2] Clares, M.P.; Serena, C.; Blasco, S.; Nebot, A.; Del Castillo, A.; Soriano, C.; Domènech, A.; Sánchez-Sánchez, A.V.; Soler-Calero, L.; Mullor, J.L.; García-España, A.; García-España, E., Mn(II) complexes of scorpionand-like ligands. A model for the MnSOD active centre with high in vitro and in vivo activity. *Journal of Inorganic Biochemistry*, **2015**, *143*, 1-8.

Modelling the dependence on medium and ionic strength of molybdate acid-base properties, and its interactions with phytate

Francesco CREA^{a)}, Concetta DE STEFANO^{a)}, Claudia FOTI^{a)}, Anna IRTO^{a)}, Demetrio MILEA^{a)},
Alberto PETTIGNANO^{b)}, Silvio SAMMARTANO^{a)}

^{a)} *Dipartimento di Scienze Chimiche, Biologiche, Farmaceutiche ed Ambientali,
Università degli Studi di Messina, V.le F. Stagno d'Alcontres, 31, I-98166 Messina, ITALY*

^{b)} *Dipartimento di Fisica e Chimica, Università degli Studi di Palermo, Viale delle Scienze,
I-90128 Palermo, ITALY*

dmilea@unime.it

The importance of molybdenum from a biological, environmental and technological point of view is very well known since many decades [1-5]. In particular, it is mainly present in aqueous solutions as molybdate (MoO_4^{2-}), which is the biologically active form, entering in the cells by active transport systems. Though molybdate is the major species in neutral to basic pH conditions, at lower pH it undergoes protonation and, chiefly, polymerization, even at millimolar concentration levels [2]. Consequently, the modelling of its speciation and acid-base properties is not very simple, as demonstrated by the non-homogeneity of available literature data. In this light, our group has started a systematic study aimed at the evaluating the dependence on medium and ionic strength of the acid-base properties of molybdate. This contribution reports some results relative to the protonation constants of molybdate at $T = 298.15 \text{ K}$, in NaCl_{aq} and $\text{NaNO}_{3\text{aq}}$ at different ionic strengths ($0 < I / \text{mol dm}^{-3} \leq 5.0$ in NaCl_{aq} , $0 < I / \text{mol dm}^{-3} \leq 3.0$ in $\text{NaNO}_{3\text{aq}}$), by potentiometric and spectrophotometric titrations. The two techniques allowed the investigation of different ligand concentration ranges, in order to define the acid-base behaviour of molybdate below and above the concentration limits for the formation of the polynuclear species. The dependence of the protonation constants on ionic strength has then been modelled by means of classical approaches (Extended Debye-Hückel, Specific ion Interaction Theory, Pitzer).

Moreover, it is well known that molybdate, other than as a classical anion, behaves as Lewis acid too, leading to relevant interactions with both cations and ligands in aqueous solution [4]. As a consequence, a better insight on the coordination behaviour and the speciation of molybdate in aqueous systems containing various cations and ligands is of great concern from many different point of view. For this reason, its interactions with phytate [Phy, 1,2,3,4,5,6-hexakis(dihydrogen phosphate) *myo*-inositol] have also been investigated at $T = 298.15 \text{ K}$ in NaCl_{aq} at different ionic strengths, with the aim of defining the speciation of these systems and evaluating the sequestering ability of this ligand toward molybdate. In fact, analogously to MoO_4^{2-} , also phytate is a very important molecule from the biological, environmental and technological point of view, due to its ability to form quite stable complex species with several metal and organometal cations, as well as other ligands [6,7].

References:

- [1] Schwarz, G., Molybdenum cofactor and human disease. *Curr Opin Chem Biol* **2016**, 31, 179-187.
- [2] Ning, P.; Xu, W.; Cao, H.; Lin, X.; Xu, H., Determination and modeling for the solubility of Na₂MoO₄·2H₂O in the (Na⁺+MoO₄²⁻+SO₄²⁻) system. *J. Chem. Thermodyn.* **2016**, 94, 67-73.
- [3] Leimkuhler, S.; Iobbi-Nivol, C., Bacterial molybdoenzymes: old enzymes for new purposes. *FEMS Microbiol Rev* **2016**, 40, 1-18.
- [4] Yoder, C. H.; Christie, E. L.; Morford, J. L., ⁹⁵Mo NMR study of the effect of structure on complexation of molybdate with alpha and beta hydroxy carboxylic acid ligands. *Polyhedron* **2015**, Ahead of Print.
- [5] Biancalana, L.; Bortoluzzi, M.; Forte, C.; Marchetti, F.; Pampaloni, G., Structural characterization of α-amino acid complexes of molybdates: a spectroscopic and DFT study. *RSC Adv.* **2015**, 5, 9010-9018.
- [6] Bretti, C.; Cigala, R. M.; De Stefano, C.; Lando, G.; Milea, D.; Sammartano, S., On the interaction of phytate with proton and monocharged inorganic cations in different ionic media, and modeling of acid-base properties at low ionic strength. *J. Chem. Thermodyn.* **2015**, 90, 51-58 and refs therein.
- [7] Crea, F.; De Stefano, C.; Milea, D.; Sammartano, S., Formation and stability of phytate complexes in solution. *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **2008**, 252, 1108-1120

POSTER PRESENTATIONS

Platinum complexes with antiproliferative activity

**Tiziana Pivetta^{a)}, Elisa Valletta^{a)}, Enzo Cadoni^{a)}, Sarah Vascellari^{b)}, Francesco Isaia^{a)},
Alessandra Pani^{b)}**

*a) Dipartimento di Scienze Chimiche e Geologiche, b) Dipartimento di Scienze Biomediche,
University of Cagliari, Cittadella Universitaria, 09042 Monserrato – CA ITALY;*

tpivetta@unica.it

Cancer is a group of malignancy characterized by unregulated cell growth. The use of platinum complexes in cancer therapy started with the introduction of cisplatin (cis-diamino-dichloroplatinum(II)) in clinical practice. Cisplatin, by binding DNA, causes a distortion of the helix and leads to cellular apoptosis.[1] It is able to interact with different plasmatic proteins containing thiolic groups, thanks to the great affinity of platinum for the sulfur atom.[2-4]

Nitrogen-containing ligands with delocalized electrons react with DNA, intercalating between base pairs by aromatic pi-pi stacking. For example, 1,10-phenanthroline (**phen**) and phenanthroline-5,6-dione (**phendione**) show anticancer activity against several cancer cell lines, both alone [5, 6] and metal-bound.[7-10]

We synthesized and characterized a new family of mixed platinum(II) complexes with phen, phendione and 5,6-dihydroxy-phenanthroline (**phendiol**) and with imidazolidine-2-thione ligands.

The cytotoxic activity of ligands and platinum complexes has been tested against several tumour derived human cell lines.

The interaction of platinum complexes with albumin was studied by UV-vis spectroscopy and Electrospray Ionization at Atmospheric-Pressure Mass Spectrometry (ESI-MS) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. ESI-MS (+) spectra of a platinum complex with albumin.

References:

- [1] Alderden, R. A.; Hall, M. D.; Hambley, T. W., The discovery and development of Cisplatin. *Journal of Chemical Education* **2006**, 83 (5), 728-734.
- [2] Rudnev, A. V.; Aleksenko, S. S.; Semenova, O.; Hartinger, C. G.; Timerbaev, A. R.; Keppler, B. K., Determination of binding constants and stoichiometries for platinum anticancer drugs and serum transport proteins by capillary electrophoresis using the Hummel-Dreyer method. *J. Sep. Sci.* **2005**, 28, 121–127.
- [3] Sooriyaarachchi, M.; Narendran, A.; Gailer, J., Comparative hydrolysis and plasma protein binding of cis-platin and carboplatin in human plasma in vitro. *Metallomics* **2011**, 3, 49–55.
- [4] Ivanov, A. I.; Christodoulou, J.; Parkinson, J. A.; Barnham, K. J.; Tucker, A.; Woodrow, J.; Sadler, P. J., Cisplatin binding sites on human albumin. *J. Biol. Chem.* **1998**, 273, 14721–14730.
- [5] Falchuk, K.H.; Krishan, A., 1,10 Phenanthroline inhibition of lymphoblast cell cycle. *Cancer Research* **1977**, 37, 2051-2056.
- [6] Berger, N.A.; Johnson, E.S.; Skinner, A.M., Ortho phenanthroline inhibition of DNA synthesis in mammalian cells. *Experimental Cell Research* **1975**, 96, 145-155.
- [7] Marzano, C.; Pellei, M.; Tisato, F.; Santini, C., Copper complexes as anticancer agents. *Anti-Cancer Agents in Medicinal Chemistry* **2009**, 9, 186-211.
- [8] Pivetta, T.; Isaia, F.; Verani, G.; Cannas, C.; Serra, L.; Castellano, C.; Demartin, F.; Pilla, F.; Manca, M.; Pani, A. Mixed-1,10-phenanthroline-Cu(II) complexes: synthesis, cytotoxic activity versus hematological and solid tumor cells and complex formation equilibria with glutathione. *Journal of Inorganic Biochemistry* **2012**, 104, 28-37.
- [9] Pivetta, T.; Trudu, F.; Valletta, E.; Isaia, F.; Castellano, C.; Demartin, F.; Tuveri, R.; Vascellari, S.; Pani, A., Novel copper(II) complexes as new promising antitumour agents. A crystal structure of [Cu(1,10-phenanthroline-5,6-dione)₂(OH₂)(OCIO₃)](ClO₄). *J. Inorg. Biochem.* **2014**, 141, 103–113.
- [10] Deegan, C.; Coyle, B.; McCann, M.; Devereux, M.; Egan, D. A., In vitro anti-tumour effect of 1,10-phenanthroline-5,6-dione (phendione), [Cu(phendione)₃](ClO₄)₂·4H₂O and [Ag(phendione)₂]ClO₄ using human epithelial cell lines. *Chemico-Biological Interactions* **2006**, 164, 115-125.

Thermodynamic and structural characterization of transition metal complexes of peptides with thiolate and other binding sites

Norbert LIHI^{a)}, Mária RAICS^{a)}, Csilla KÁLLAY^{b)}, Katalin VÁRNAGY^{a)}, Imre SÓVÁGÓ^{a)}

^{a)} *Department of Inorganic and Analytical Chemistry, University of Debrecen, H-4010, Debrecen, Hungary* ^{b)} *Research Group of Homogeneous Catalysis and Reaction Mechanism, Hungarian Academy of Sciences, H-4010, Debrecen, Hungary;*

lihi.norbert@science.unideb.hu

The role of cysteine and histidine is outstanding in the biological systems. Imidazole-N of histidine and thiolate-S of cysteine are the most common binding sites in metalloproteins and metalloenzymes. As a consequence, huge number of papers has already been published in this field focused on the characterization of metal binding[1-3]. Most of them are dealing with the multihistidine peptides because the proteins containing multihistidine sequences have abnormal behaviour in the neurodegenerative disorders[4]. The studies on the cysteine containing peptides are much less available, most common examples are related to the nickel(II) homeostasis of *Helicobacter pylori* and to the zinc(II) transporter proteins[3,5]. The cysteine residue, however, could serve as a main binding site for toxic heavy metal ions such as cadmium(II), which able to substitute the essential metal ions. This irreversible connection may change or hinder the participation of metalloenzymes and metalloproteins in biochemical processes. Systematic studies of peptides containing thiolate and other donor group in the side chains (imidazole or carboxylate) can contribute to the understanding of the metal binding selectivity of oligopeptides.

The above mentioned facts inspired us to launch systematic studies[6,7] with the synthesis of N-terminally free but C-terminally amidated peptides containing only cysteine (AAASSC-NH₂) and cysteine with other binding sites (AAHAAC-NH₂, AHAAAC-NH₂, AADAAC-NH₂ and ADAAAC-NH₂). The complex formation processes with transition metal ions (nickel(II), zinc(II) and cadmium(II)) have been studied by equilibrium (pH-potentiometric, UV/Visible spectroscopy) and spectroscopic methods (NMR, UV/Vis and CD). In some cases, DFT calculations were used to optimize the complex structure and to calculate the spectroscopic properties.

Our results indicate that the binding of thiolate group on the C-termini largely depends on the place of another donor group in the peptide chain. In the case of the nickel(II) complexes with AADAAC-NH₂ and AAHAAC-NH₂ the formation of (NH₂, N⁻, N⁻, β-COO⁻ or N_{im}) complex is favourable (Fig. 1. A) and the coordination of the thiolate group could be supposed only in the case of dinuclear complexes. The nickel(II) complexes of the peptides, ADAAAC-NH₂ and AHAAAC-NH₂, are (NH₂, N⁻, β-COO⁻ or N_{im})-coordinated species at slightly acidic pH. This coordination environment, however, results in an unsaturated coordination sphere of nickel(II) that can be completed via the coordination of the thiolate group resulting in macrochelate supported species (Fig. 1. B). In the presence of zinc(II) and

cadmium(II), the ligands are usually bounded with tridentate coordination mode via terminal amino group, thiolate group and imidazole or carboxylate group. Nevertheless, in the zinc(II)-AHAAC-NH₂ system the complex formation processes are similar to that of nickel(II).

Figure 1. Optimized structure of the nickel complexes formed with AAHAAC-NH₂ (A) and AHAAC-NH₂ (B) at physiological pH.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by the Hungarian Scientific Research Fund (OTKA K 115480) and Richter Gedeon Talentum Foundation.

References:

- [1] Kozłowski, H.; Bal, W.; Dyba, M.; Kowalik-Jankowska, T., Specific structure–stability relations in metallopeptides *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **1999**, 184, 319-346.
- [2] Sóvágó, I.; Kállay, C.; Várnagy, K., Peptides as complexing agents: Factors influencing the structure and thermodynamic stability of peptide complexes. *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **2012**, 256 (19-20), 2225-2223.
- [3] Witkowska, D.; Rowinska-Zyrek, M.; Valensin, G.; Kozłowski, H., Specific poly-histidyl and poly-cysteil protein sites involved in Ni²⁺ homeostasis in *Helicobacter pylori*. Impact of Bi³⁺ ions on Ni²⁺ binding to proteins. Structural and thermodynamic aspects. *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, **2012**, 256, 133-148.
- [4] Arena, G.; La Mendola, D.; Pappalardo, G.; Sóvágó, I.; Rizzarelli, E., Copper(II) interaction with amyloid- β : Affinity and speciation. *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **2012**, 256, 3-12.
- [5] Kozłowski, H.; Potocki, S.; Remelli, M.; Rowinska-Zyrek, M.; Valensin, D., Specific metal ion binding sites in unstructured regions of proteins *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **2013**, 257 (19-20), 2625-2638.
- [6] Lihi, N.; Grenács, Á.; Timári, S.; Turi, I.; Bányai, I.; Sóvágó, I.; Várnagy, K., Zinc(II) and cadmium(II) complexes of N-terminally free peptides containing two separate cysteinyl binding sites *New J. Chem.* **2015**, 39, 8364-8372.
- [7] Raics, M.; Laskai, A.; Lihi, N.; Várnagy, K.; Kállay, C.; Sóvágó, I., Nickel(II), zinc(II) and cadmium(II) complexes of hexapeptides containing separate histidyl and cysteinyl binding sites *New J. Chem.* **2016**, submitted.

Photocleavage and Chemical Properties of Arene-Organometallic Complexes depend of the Metal Center

Begoña GARCIA^{a)}, Natalia BUSTO^{a)}, Matteo LARI^{a)}, Ana R. RUBIO^{a)}, Cristina PÉREZ^{a)}, Héctor J. LOZANO^{a)}, José M. LEAL^{a)}, Marta MARTINEZ^{a)}, Gustavo ESPINO^{a)}.

^{a)}Chemistry Department, University of Burgos, Plaza Misael Bañuelos s/n, 09001 Burgos
begar@ubu.es

Iridium, rhodium and ruthenium complexes have attracted recently growing attention because of their promising potential as anticancer drugs. [1,2] Three analogous phenylbenzimidazole organometallic complexes with different metallic centres have been synthesized: [Ir(Cp*)(phbzIm)Cl], [Rh(Cp*)(phbzim)Cl] and [Ru(p-cim)(phbzIm)Cl] (Figure 1).

Photoirradiation of a drug at a particular wavelength may cause excitation and subsequent transfer of the energy in excess to the Oxygen molecules present in solution, giving rise to Oxygen radicals. The latter can, in turn, interact with plasmid DNA, bringing about the photorupture of DNA. This behaviour may be of particular importance in photodynamic therapy. The results have shown that direct irradiation of the sample containing the metal complex and the plasmid, at different irradiation time to 315nm, Ru complex exhibits good photocleavage activity, whereas Ir and Rh complexes cause only little cleavage, increasing only for high irradiation times.

Figure 1. Arenephenylbenzimidazole complexes of: (left) Ru (II); (right) Rh(III) or Ir(III).

In the absence of irradiation, the cytotoxic activity of the complexes has been tested on A549 (human lung carcinoma), MCF-7 (human breast adenocarcinoma) and HT-116 (human colon carcinoma) cell lines. Due to the different cytotoxic activity displayed by the complexes (all of them with IC₅₀ values in the micromolar range) we have studied the interaction of the three complexes with DNA, NADH (nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate) and GSH (reduced glutathione) to elucidate the possible biological target. The NAD⁺ (oxidized form) is used in redox reactions in the cell and acts as a reducing agent. NADH (reduced form) contributes to oxidation in cell processes, such as glycolysis, to help with the oxidation of glucose. The energy stored in this reduced NADH coenzyme is supplied by the TCA

(tricarboxylic acid) cycle in the process of aerobic cellular respiration and powers the electron transport process in the membranes of mitochondria. Glutathione can exist in both reduced (GSH) and oxidized (GSSG) states. In the reduced state, the thiol group of cysteine is able to transfer a reducing equivalent ($H^+ + e^-$) to other unstable molecules, such as reactive oxygen species.

Figure 2: (left) The NAD⁺ structure; (right) The GSH structure

In absence of irradiation only the Rh complex can interact with both DNA and NADH and only the Ir and Rh complexes can interact with GSH. The set of results obtained can explain the different mechanisms of biological action.

References:

- [1] Geldmacher, Y.; Oleszak, M.; Sheldrick W. S., Rhodium(III) and iridium(III) complexes as anticancer agents. *Inorg. Chim. Acta* **2012**, 393, 84-102.
- [2] Han Ang, W.; Dyson, P. J., Classical and Non-Classical Ruthenium-Based Anticancer Drugs: Towards Targeted Chemotherapy. *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.* **2006**, 20, 4003.

Magnetic Metal Organic Frameworks - from synthesis to applications

R. M. MAWALE^{a)c)}, J.E. CONDE-GONZÁLEZ^{a)}, E.M. PEÑA-MÉNDEZ^{a)}, J. HAVEL^{c)}, C. RUIZ-PÉREZ^{b)}

^{a)} Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, University of La Laguna, Campus de Anchieta, 38071 La Laguna, Tenerife, Spain ^{b)} Department of Physics, Faculty of Science, University of La Laguna, Campus de Anchieta, 38071 La Laguna, Tenerife, Spain ^{c)} Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Kamenice 5/A14, 625 00 Brno

Metal–organic frameworks (MOFs) in combination with nanoparticles is the field which exhibited tremendous growth over the last five years. Magnetic MOFs (MMOFs) represent novel materials, where the nano-composite {MOF, magnetic nanoparticles} joins the relevant properties of both materials and furthermore offers the possibility of easy removal of {MMOFs-analyte} from a solution using a magnet [1,2].

In this work, the MIL-101 (Fe) (iron (III)- benzene 1,3,5-tricarboxylate; Fe-BTC) MMOFs was selected because combination of Brunauer, Emmett and Teller (BET) surface area and pore dimension, high chemical stability and stability in aqueous solution of this material offers wide use e.g. in catalysis and medicine. All this makes MMOFs promising candidate as suitable sorbent in aqueous media. Different combinations of Fe-BTC with magnetic nanoparticles (MMOFs, eg. hybrids, core-shell) were synthesized and used as sorbent for small organic molecules in different media. The synthesized compounds were characterized by UV-Vis spectrophotometry, magnetic properties, electronic microscopy (SEM, TEM), infrared spectroscopy, and thermo-gravimetry. The adsorption properties of synthesized materials for different compounds were studied. Analysis of the different analytes was made by Liquid Chromatography equipped with either uv-vis or fluorescence detectors. Results show that MMOFs in comparison to MOFs demonstrate excellent properties as adsorbent in aqueous solution.

Acknowledgements

Grant MAT2014-57465-R (Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness, Spain) is acknowledged. R. M. Mawale thanks to EU Erasmus Program between Univ. La Laguna and Masaryk University.

References:

- [1] Conde-González, J.E.; Peña-Méndez, E.M.; Rybáková, S.; Pasán, J.; Ruiz-Pérez, C.; Havel, J., Adsorption of silver nanoparticles from aqueous solution on copper-based metal organic frameworks (HKUST-1). *Chemosphere* **2016**, 150, 659-66.
- [2] Huang, Y.; Keller, A.A., Magnetic Nanoparticle Adsorbents for Emerging Organic Contaminants. *ACS Sustainable Chem. Eng.* **2013**, 1 (7), 731–736.

Coordination, redox properties and SOD activity of Cu(II) complexes of multihistidine peptides

Gizella CSIRE^{a)}, Sarolta TIMÁRI^{a)}, Katalin VÁRNAGY^{a)}

*Department of Inorganic and Analytical Chemistry, University of Debrecen, H-4032 Debrecen, Egyetem tér 1., Hungary
csire.gizella@science.unideb.hu*

It is well-known that essential metal ions play important roles in the synthesis and transport of organic molecules and in the catalysis of acid-base and redox processes in biological systems. It is also obvious that among the organic compounds proteins serve the most frequent binding sites for metal ions. Such interactions are present in the metalloenzymes too.

One of the most important redox metalloenzymes is the Cu,Zn superoxide dismutase enzyme (Figure 1), in the active site of which one Cu(II) ion is bound through four imidazole nitrogens while one zinc(II) ion is coordinated through three imidazole nitrogens and the carboxylate group of an aspartic acid. Cu(II) complexes of various protected multihistidine peptides can mimic the Cu(II) binding site of this enzyme [1].

Figure 1: The active sites of the Cu,Zn SOD enzyme

Our aim was

- the synthesis of protected peptides containing histidyl residues in different number and positions: Ac-HGGH-NH₂, Ac-HAAH-NH₂, Ac-HVVH-NH₂, Ac-HGGHGH-NH₂, Ac-HAAHGH-NH₂, Ac-HAAHVH-NH₂, Ac-HGGHGHGH-NH₂
- the solution equilibrium studies of their Cu(II) complexes by potentiometric titration, UV-Vis and CD spectroscopy
- the determination of the redox properties and SOD activity of the Cu(II) complexes of these ligands

In the presence of copper(II) ions all studied peptides form CuL complexes in the physiological pH range with the coordination of 2-4 imidazole nitrogens depending on the number of histidines. The increasing number of histidines increases the stability of imidazole coordinated species. An additional stabilizing effect is the presence of HXH sequence on the C-termini of peptides. The stability of the CuL complexes are high, but they cannot prevent the deprotonation of amide nitrogens in slightly basic solution, so complexes with CuLH₋₁, CuLH₋₂ and CuLH₋₃ stoichiometries are formed. In the case of the penta-, hexa- and heptapeptides isomeric structures of mononuclear complexes are present in the solution. On the other hand these oligopeptides are able to bind more than one Cu(II) ion. In the presence of excess metal ion Cu₂LH₋₄ and Cu₂LH₋₅ complexes are formed at high pH range. Based on the cyclic voltammetric studies we concluded that the more imidazole nitrogens are present in the coordinations sphere, the lower formal reduction potential values belong to the imidazole nitrogen coordinated complexes. This is in agreement with the fact that the greater the stability of the complex is, the less reduction potential can be measured [2]. However, redox parameters of CuLH₋₁ and CuLH₋₂ complexes containing amide nitrogen coordination can be determined as well. All formal potential values of CuL, CuLH₋₁, CuLH₋₂ complexes fall in the middle potential range of the SOD activity. Based on these data the Cu(II) complexes may be good SOD models.

As a continuation of our electrochemical experiments, we measured the SOD activity of the complexes that seemed to be promising SOD models from a redox point of view. SOD activity of Cu(II)-peptide complexes are similar to those previously determined for other Cu(II) complexes of multihistidine peptides (e.g. CuL of Ac-HisSarHisSarHisSarHis-NH₂) but compared to the native enzyme it is still one order of magnitude lower. However, taking into account the species distribution curves of copper(II) complexes, the SOD activity data reveal, that not only the imidazole coordinated CuL, but the CuLH₋₁ and/or CuLH₋₂ species have SOD activity due to their distorted geometry.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the Hungarian Scientific Research Fund (OTKA K 115480).

References:

- [1] Kállay, Cs.; Várnagy, K.; Malandrinos, G.; Hadjiliadis, N.; Sanna, D.; Sóvágó, I., Copper(II) complexes of terminally protected pentapeptides containing three histidyl residues in alternating positions, Ac-His-Xaa-His-Yaa-His-NH₂. *Dalton Trans.* **2006**, 4545-4552.
- [2] Timári, S.; Cerea, R.; Várnagy, K., Characterization of CuZnSOD model complexes from a redox point of view: redox properties of copper(II) complexes of imidazole containing ligands. *J. Inorg. Biochem.* **2011**, 105, 1009-1017.

Luminescent Eu³⁺ complexes in acetonitrile solution: effect of water on speciation and anions sensing

Andrea Melchior^{a)}, Fabio Piccinelli^{b)}, Marco Leonzio^{b)}, Marco Bettinelli^{b)}, Georgina Faura Muñoz^{a)}, Marilena Tolazzi^{a)}

^{a)} Dipartimento Politecnico, Laboratori di Scienze e Tecnologie Chimiche, Università di Udine, Via del Cotonificio 108, 33100 Udine, Italy ^{b)} Luminescent Materials Laboratory, DB, Università di Verona, and INSTM, UdR Verona, Strada Le Grazie 15, 37134 Verona, Italy
andrea.melchior@uniud.it

Lanthanide complexes (Ln³⁺ = Sm³⁺, Eu³⁺, Tb³⁺, Dy³⁺, Yb³⁺) have been extensively studied as luminescent sensors[1,2] and optical sensors for cell imaging[3].

The long emission lifetimes of Ln³⁺ ions are favourable for reducing interference from light scattering or autofluorescence in complex microenvironments such as cells, tissue or living animals[4] *via* time-gated detection. Complexes of Ln³⁺ ions present an efficient intramolecular energy transfer from a donor state (usually triplet) of the coordinated organic ligand (*antenna*) to the acceptor excited states of Ln³⁺ ion giving rise to an efficient Ln³⁺ excitation, bypassing the Laporte-forbidden nature of the f-f transitions[5]. The large energy shift between absorbed and emitted radiations and very narrow emission bands allow the discrimination between Ln³⁺ luminescence and short-lived background fluorescence[4].

In previous works,[6-8] Eu³⁺ complexes with a new family of imine- and amine-based ligands containing an heteroaromatic (pyridine or furan) ring (Figure 1) have been studied in anhydrous acetonitrile. These ligands have been synthesized by an easy synthetic protocol which allows to systematically tune the nature (σ -donor ability) of the heteroaromatic ring which demonstrated to have a strong effect both on the species formed in solution and on the optical sensing response towards the nitrate anion. Furthermore, the ligand stereochemistry can be easily defined.

However, in most applications, the solvent used is not rigorously anhydrous, thus it is useful to investigate the effect of water (from the ambient moisture) present in acetonitrile. Indeed, it is expected that water dissolved in an organic solvent in significant amounts can affect the nature of the Eu³⁺ complexes, due to the oxophilicity of lanthanide(III) ions[9], and consequently the nature of the sensing species. In addition, anions are known to be much less solvated in aprotic solvents than in water, thus, also the anion solvation by dissolved water could modify the sensing process by inhibiting the coordination of the anion to the Eu³⁺ complex. Finally, the presence of water in the first coordination sphere quenches the excited state by non-radiative decay.

In this contribution, the results of the study on the complexes formation of Eu³⁺ with **L1-3** (Figure 1) in non-anhydrous acetonitrile containing a known amount of water are

reported. Also, the impact of the nature of the heteroaromatic fragment of the ligand and of the stereochemistry on the luminescence sensitivity and selectivity towards several anions is presented.

Figure 1. Structures of the ligands studied.

References:

- [1] Tsukube, H.; Shinoda, S., Lanthanide complexes in molecular recognition and chirality sensing of biological substrates. *Chem. Rev.* **2002**, 102(6), 2389–2404.
- [2] Liu, Z.; He, W.; Guo, Z., Metal coordination in photoluminescent sensing, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2013**, 42, 1568–600.
- [3] New, E. J.; Parker, D.; Smith, D. G.; Walton, J. W., Development of responsive lanthanide probes for cellular applications. *Curr. Opin. Chem. Biol.* **2010**, 14(2), 238–246
- [4] Bünzli, J.-C. G., Lanthanide luminescence for biomedical analyses and imaging. *Chem. Rev.* **2010**, 110(5), 2729–2755.
- [5] Sabbatini, N.; Guardigli, M.; Lehn, J.-M., Luminescent lanthanide complexes as photochemical supramolecular devices. *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **1993**, 123(1-2), 201–228.
- [6] Piccinelli, F.; Bettinelli, M.; Melchior, A.; Grazioli, C.; Tolazzi, M., Structural, optical and sensing properties of novel Eu(III) complexes with furan- and pyridine-based ligands. *Dalton Trans.* **2015**, 44, 182–192.
- [7] Piccinelli, F.; Leonzio, M.; Bettinelli, M.; Monari, M.; Grazioli, C.; Melchior, A.; Tolazzi, M., Tuning of the sensing properties of luminescent Eu³⁺ complexes towards the nitrate anion. *Dalton Trans.* **2016**, 45, 3310–3318
- [8] Piccinelli, F.; Melchior, A.; Speghini, A.; Monari, M.; Tolazzi, M.; Bettinelli, M., Europium (III) complexes with new N-donor ligand: A comparative study in solid state and solution. *Polyhedron* **2013**, 57, 30–38.
- [9] Di Bernardo, P.; Melchior, A.; Tolazzi, M.; Zanonato, P. L., Thermodynamics of lanthanide(III) complexation in non-aqueous solvents. *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **2012**, 256(1–2), 328–351

A Novel Octasubstituted Zinc Phthalocyanine Containing 4-(trifluoromethoxy)-thiophenol Groups

Hande R. PEKBELGIN KARAOGLU^{a)}, Ozgul SAGLAM^{a)}, Makbule BURKUT KOÇAK^{a)}

*^{a)} Department of Chemistry, Istanbul Technical University, 34469, Istanbul, Turkey. Fax: +902122856386; Tel: +902122853226
pekbelgin@itu.edu.tr*

Phthalocyanines are tetrapyrrolic macrocycles having C=N linkages between pyrrole groups. Unlike porphyrins, synthesis of phthalocyanines gives higher reaction yields. Modern synthesis of phthalocyanines involves 4-nitrophthalonitrile for peripherally tetrasubstituted phthalocyanines (as a mixture of constitutional isomers) and 4,5-dichlorophthalonitrile for peripherally octasubstituted phthalocyanines. The reaction medium is fairly basic –potassium or sodium or even cesium carbonate in DMF or DMSO is used as the base. Substrates commonly have acidic OH or SH groups and get deprotonated with the action of the base.

In the past few decades, much effort has been devoted to the field of nonlinear optics (NLO) for its potential applications in optoelectronics. Devices based on NLO effects might be used to manipulate or process optical signals in telecommunication systems. In addition, phthalocyanines play a vital role in chemical sensors, catalysts, optical data storage materials, semiconductors, liquid crystals, electrochromic displays, and photovoltaic cells due to their physically and chemically outstanding properties including thermal and chemical stability.

In this study, we have described the synthesis of a new phthalonitrile derivative and its metallated phthalocyanine carrying eight 4-(trifluoromethoxy)-thiophenol groups at peripheral positions. The structures of all these original compounds were identified by using FTIR, UV-Vis, ¹H-NMR, ¹³C-NMR, and ¹⁹F-NMR spectroscopic data.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by TUBITAK (Project Number: 115R030) and Scientific Research Projects Unit (BAP) of Istanbul Technical University.

References:

- [1] Leznoff, C. C.; Lever, A. B. P., Phthalocyanines properties and applications, Vol. 1, VCH Publisher, Weinheim, **1989**.
- [2] Mc Keown, N. B., Phthalocyanine Materials: Synthesis, Structure and Function, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, **1998**.
- [3] Dinçer, H. A.; Gül, A.; Koçak, M. B; *J. Porphyrins Phthalocyanines*, **2004**, *8*, 1204.

Non-peripherally Pyrrole-substituted Phthalocyanines

Merve PAMUKÇU^{a)}, H. Yasemin YENILMEZ^{a)}, Zehra Altuntaş BAYIR^{a)}

^{a)} *Istanbul Technical University, Department of Chemistry, 34469, Istanbul, Turkey;*
pamukcum@itu.edu.tr

Phthalocyanine derivatives (Pcs) are planar aromatic macrocycles consisting of four isoindole units linked by aza bridge [1, 2]. They are analogues of naturally occurring porphyrins and chlorins, like heme and chlorophyll. Pyrroles are important heterocycles that contain nitrogen atom within a five-membered ring. Common naturally produced molecules containing pyrroles include vitamin B₁₂, bile pigments and chlorophyll. Pyrroles are also found in several drugs, including atorvastatin, ketorolac, and sunitinib. To the best of our knowledge, there are very few articles in the literature on pyrrole-substituted phthalocyanines [3]. The Q band of phthalocyanines appear around 650 nm.

Our purpose in synthesizing these compounds is that the Q bands of the pcs are shifted to the near infrared region. This can be done by two methods. The ring of pc is added to substituent having π -electron system. As another approach to moving the Q-band to longer wavelengths, one possibility is to introduce an electron donating substituent at a non-peripheral position of the phthalocyanine. When we consider all these, a new phthalonitrile derivative bearing a 4-(pyrrol-1-yl)phenoxy substituent at non-peripheral positions has been synthesized. Novel non-peripheral cobalt, zinc and manganese phthalocyanines were synthesized and characterized for the first time. Further, the wavelength of the absorption of the Q band and the aggregation properties of the compounds were investigated.

M: Co, Zn, Mn(Cl)

This work was supported by TÜBİTAK (Project No:214Z104).

References:

- [1] Leznoff, C. C.; Lever, A. B. P., Phthalocyanines properties and applications, Vol. 1, VCH Publisher, Weinheim, **1989**.
- [2] Mc Keown, N. B., Phthalocyanine Materials: Synthesis, Structure and Function, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, **1998**.
- [3] Obirai, J.; Rodrigues, N. P.; Bedioui, F.; Nyokong, T., Synthesis, spectral and electrochemical properties of a new family of pyrrole substituted cobalt, iron, manganese, nickel and zinc phthalocyanine complexes. *Journal of Porphyrins and Phthalocyanines* **2003**, 7, 508-520.

Synthesis, Characterization, and Spectral Properties of a Novel Tetrasubstituted Zinc Phthalocyanine

Nazli FARAJZADEH^{a)}, Hande R. PEKBELGİN KARAOĞLU^{a)}, Makbule BURKUT KOÇAK^{a)}

^{a)} Department of Chemistry, Istanbul Technical University, 34469, Istanbul, Turkey. Fax: +902122856386; Tel: +902122853226; farajzadeh.nazli@gmail.com

Due to metallophthalocyanines' (MPcs) extraordinary versatility resulting in tremendous chemical and physical properties such as intense color, redox activity, high thermal stability and non-toxicity, they are widely applied in medicine, military, informatics, manufacture, and other fields [1,2].

In addition to their well-known chemical stability, phthalocyanines possess characteristic absorption spectra, with a Soret band at approximately 350 nm and a usually narrow but very strong Q-band around 675 nm. The Q-band bathochromic shift in the visible spectrum into the near-IR region gives a wider transparent window in the spectrum. This is required for possible material applications of Pcs, which make them potentially suitable for PDT as photosensitizers and in nonlinear optics (*e.g.*, human eye protector).

In this study, a new phthalonitrile with a 4-(trifluoromethoxy)-phenol group was synthesized and the corresponding tetrasubstituted zinc phthalocyanine was prepared. The structures of all these original compounds were characterized by using FTIR, UV-Vis, ¹³C-NMR, ¹H-NMR and ¹⁹F-NMR spectroscopic data.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by TUBITAK (Project Number: 115R030) and Scientific Research Projects Unit (BAP) of Istanbul Technical University.

References:

- [1] Leznoff, C. C.; Lever, A. B. P., *Phthalocyanines properties and applications*, Vol. 1, VCH Publisher, Weinheim, 1989.
- [2] Mc Keown, N. B., *Phthalocyanine Materials: Synthesis, Structure and Function*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1998.
- [3] Pekbelgin Karaoglu H.R., Gül A., Burkut Koçak, M., Synthesis and characterization of a new tetracationic phthalocyanine. *Dyes and Pigments* **2008**, 76, 231-235.

Tetra Substituted Phthalocyanines with Morpholinoethanol Moieties

Halit KOÇAN^{a)}, Ayfer KALKAN BURAT^{a)}

^{a)} *Istanbul Technical University, Department of Chemistry, 34469, Istanbul, Turkey;*
kalkanayf@itu.edu.tr

Since the accidental discovery of phthalocyanines (Pcs), much effort has been done to modulate the properties of their derivatives to achieve ideal molecules for a variety of applications, such as biology, catalysis, chemical sensing, liquid crystals, dye sensitized solar cells and non-linear optics [1, 2]. Nitrogen-containing heterocyclic compounds such as piperazine and morpholine derivatives have been extensively investigated by organic chemist due to their close association with various types of biological activities and clinical applications in the therapy of functional diseases [3]. An insertion of nitrogen-containing moieties into the structure of phthalocyanines, has been shown as an important factor modulating their physicochemical properties, thus facilitating their potential applications in medicine [4]. Thus, in continuation of our search for potential application of Pcs, we decided to synthesize phthalocyanines with morpholinoethanol groups as peripheral substituent's. We report herein the synthesis and characterization of tetra substituted cobalt and manganese phthalocyanines. The electronic absorptions, and the biological properties of the novel phthalocyanines will be investigated.

This work was supported by TÜBİTAK (Project No:115Z063).

References:

- [1] Leznoff, C. C.; Lever, A. B. P., Phthalocyanines properties and applications, Vol. 1, VCH Publisher, Weinheim, **1989**.
- [2] Mc Keown N. B., Phthalocyanine Materials: Synthesis, Structure and Function, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, **1998**.
- [3] Ramesh, B.; Sumana, T., *J. Chem.* **2010**, 7, 514-516.
- [4] Zhu, Y. J.; Huang, J. D.; Jiang, X. J.; Sun, J. C., Novel silicon phthalocyanines axially modified by morpholine: Synthesis, complexation with serum protein and in vitro photodynamic activity. *Inorg. Chem. Commun.* **2006**, 9(5), 473–477.

Complex-Formation Ability of Thiosemicarbazones towards Cu(II) Ions

Malgorzata OSTROWSKA^{a)}, Julia TOPORIVSKA^{a)}, Monika PYRKOSZ-BULSKA^{b)}, Marta REJMUND^{b)}, Jaroslaw POLAŃSKI^{b)}, Elzbieta GUMIENNA-KONTECKA^{a)}

^{a)} Faculty of Chemistry, University of Wrocław, F. Joliot-Curie 14, 50383 Wrocław, Poland,

^{b)} Department of Organic Chemistry, Institute of Chemistry, University of Silesia, Szkolna Street 9, 40-006 Katowice, Poland;

malgorzata.ostrowska@chem.uni.wroc.pl

Thiosemicarbazones (TSCs) are a class of compounds with a very wide range of applications, e.g., spectrophotometric and spectrofluorimetric detection of various metal ions. The ability of TSCs to form stable complexes with important biological metal ions makes them also versatile pharmacophores. They possess a broad range of pharmaceutical properties such as antimalarial, antimicrobial and antitumor activity [1, 2].

Taking into account the fact that cancer is one of the main health concerns confronting humanity and one of the primary targets in therapeutic chemistry, studies of new compounds which may possess antitumor properties are very important [3]. Triapine (Figure 1) is the best known example of TSCs family and has been extensively studied as a single agent, and in combination with established drugs, in phase I and phase II clinical trials [4].

Figures 1: Structure of Triapine.

In connection with the anticancer applications of TSCs there have been proposed several mechanisms of action, but many questions still remain unanswered. Information on the speciation of metal complexes, particularly at physiological pH, can be the first step towards elucidation of the cytotoxic mechanism of TSCs. In this work, we characterize novel thiosemicarbazone ligands, in terms of complex formation with Cu(II) ions and their stability constants.

Acknowledgements MNiSW (1507/M/WCH/15)

References:

- [1] Enyedy, E. A.; Nagy, N. V.; Zsigo, E.; Kowol, Ch. R., Arion, V. B.; Keppler, B. K.; Kiss, T., Comparative Solution Equilibrium Study of the Interactions of Copper(II), Iron(II) and Zinc(II) with Triapine(3-Aminopyridine-2-carbaldehyde Thiosemicarbazone) and Related Ligands. *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.* **2010**, 11, 1717-1728.
- [2] Mrozek-Wilczkiewicz, A.; Serda, M.; Musiol, R.; Malecki, G.; Szurko, A.; Muchowicz, A.; Golab, J.; Ratuszna, A.; Polanski, J., Iron Chelators in Photodynamic Therapy Revisited: Synergistic Effect by Novel Highly Active Thiosemicarbazones. *ACS Med.Chem.Lett.* **2014**, 5, 336-339.
- [3] Raja, D. S; Bhuvanesh, N. S. P.; Natarajan, K., Effect of N(4)-Phenyl Substitution in 2-Oxo-1,2-dihydroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde Semicarbazones on the Structure, DNA/Protein Interaction, and Antioxidative and Cytotoxic Activity of Cu(II) Complexes. *Inorg. Chem.* **2011**, 50 (24), 12852-12866.
- [4] Milunovic, M. N.; Enyedy, E. A.; Nagy, N. V.; Kiss, T.; Trondl, R.; Jakupec, M. A.; Keppler, B. K.; Krachler, R.; Novitchi, G.; Arion, V. B., L- and D-Proline Thiosemicarbazone Conjugates: Coordination Behavior in Solution and the Effect of Copper(II) Coordination on Their Antiproliferative Activity. *Inorg. Chem.* **2012**, 51 (17), 9309-9321

Sequestration of Different Mⁿ⁺ Cations by MGDA in Natural Fluids

Clemente BRETTI^{a)}, Rosalia Maria CIGALA^{a)}, Fausta GIACOBELLO^{a)}, Ottavia GIUFFRÈ^{a)},
Gabriele LANDO^{a)}, Demetrio MILEA^{a)}, Silvio SAMMARTANO^{a)}

^{a)}*Dipartimento di Scienze Chimiche, Università degli Studi di Messina, Viale Ferdinando
Stagno d'Alcontres, 31, I-98166 Messina (Vill. S. Agata), Italy.*

dmilea@unime.it

In the last decade, the use of common chelating agents, as EDTA and NTA, is under investigation, due to their persistence in the environment and other problems related to their poor selectivity [1]. For this reason, research in this field is orientated to the synthesis of new chelating agents that may overcome these problems. In general, the new molecules are based on the structure of amino acids with the advantage to retain the biodegradability of the parent molecule and the calibration of the stability of metal complexes. For example, EDDS is a biodegradable isomer of EDTA and is synthesized starting from the structure of aspartic acid, whilst MGDA is an alternative to NTA, based on the structure of glycine. The use of these molecules is growing quickly and their possible use for the chelation of environmental pollutant, metal and organometal cations, has been tested intensively. Recently it was found that EDDS is a good alternative to EDTA for the chelation of Sn²⁺, Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺ and Fe³⁺, without the counter indication of the sequestration of Mg²⁺ and Ca²⁺ [2]. In this contribution the possible use of MGDA for the sequestration of Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Sn²⁺, Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺ and Fe³⁺ is proposed. For this purpose, new experimental data on the binding ability (formation constants and formation enthalpy changes) of this ligand towards these cations were obtained using potentiometry and direct titration calorimetry at different ionic strengths and at T = 298.15 K. This amount of data was carefully analyzed to propose reliable parameters for ionic strength and temperature dependence of formation constants and formation enthalpy change to allow the calculation of these quantities in a wide range of experimental conditions. Some important real multi-component fluids, namely fresh water ($I \sim 0.003 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), urine ($I \sim 0.40 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), sea water ($I \sim 0.75 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), saliva ($I \sim 0.11 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and blood plasma ($I \sim 0.21 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) were chosen as case studies for the evaluation of the sequestering ability of MGDA (compared to NTA) and the possible use of MGDA for the treatment of water for industrial purpose is also tested. The study of the speciation of MGDA in these media was performed drawing speciation diagrams in selected conditions, considering all the network of interaction between the “natural” components of the fluid and those studied in this work, MGDA and NTA (at $c_L = 1 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$) as sequestering agents and the metal cations, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Sn²⁺, Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺, and Fe³⁺ (generally, $c_M = 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$). This means that more than fifteen components and more than a hundred formation constants values are considered in each model. The comparison of the sequestering ability of MGDA and NTA is done using objective tools, namely the pM (residual concentration of free metal cation), and pL_{0.5} (total ligand concentration necessary to bind the 50% of metal in

solution) [3]. In blood plasma, since the fundamental role of proteins cannot be modeled, the above mentioned parameters are useless, and the plasma mobilizing index (PMI) was adopted [4].

References:

- [1] Crisponi, G.; Nurchi, V. M.; Lachowicz, J. I.; Crespo-Alonso, M.; Zoroddu, M. A.; Peana, M., Kill or cure: Misuse of chelation therapy for human diseases. *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **2015**, 284, 278-285.
- [2] Bretti, C.; Cigala, R. M.; De Stefano, C.; Lando, G.; Sammartano, S., Understanding the Bioavailability and Sequestration of Different Metal Cations in the presence of a biodegradable chelant *S,S*-EDDS in Biological Fluids and Natural Waters. *Chemosphere* **2016**, 150, 341-356
- [3] Crea, F.; De Stefano, C.; Foti, C.; Milea, D.; Sammartano, S., Chelating Agents for the Sequestration of Mercury(II) and Monomethyl Mercury(II). *Curr. Med. Chem.* **2014**, 21, 3819-3836.
- [4] May, P. M.; Williams, D. R., Computer Simulation Of Chelation Therapy. *FEBS Letters* **1977**, 78, 134-138.

Some aspects on the evaluation of the adsorption properties of two trihydroxamic acid hybrid materials

Antonio SANTIAGO-MEDINA^{b)}, Paloma ARRANZ-MASCARÓS^{b)}, M^a Luz GODINO-SALIDO^{b)},
Maria Dolores GUTIÉRREZ-VALERO, Manuel MELGUIZO^{b)}, Francisco Javier LÓPEZ-
GARZÓN^{a)}, María DOMINGO-GARCÍA^{a)}

^{a)} University of Granada, Department of Inorganic Chemistry, Granada (Spain) ^{b)} University of Jaen Department of Inorganic and Organic Chemistry; Experimental Sciences Faculty, Campus Las Lagunillas, s/n, 23071, Jaen (Spain)
parranz@ujaen.

Two novel ACs/H₄L hybrid materials were obtained by irreversible adsorption by π - π stacking of the *N*-2-(4-amino-1,6-dihydro-1-methyl-5-nitroso-6-oxopyrimidinyl)-desferrioxamine B molecular receptor (H₄L), on two different activated carbons (ACs).

This work deals with the evaluation of some aspects of the adsorption properties for many divalent and trivalent ions as Cu(II), Fe (III), and Cr(III) in aqueous solution onto the surface of those hybrid materials.

The kinetic adsorption of these metallic ions on ACs/H₄L hybrids were carried out at pH values of 2.0 and 5.5 and at 298.1K. The results show a better agreement between the theoretical and experimental values for the pseudo-second order model. This fact suggests that the overall adsorption rate seems to be controlled by the chemical binding of the metal to the active sites of the hybrid surfaces. The ACs/H₄L hybrid materials have also been characterized by XPS and some relevant details are presented.

On the other hand, as the recovery and reuse of metal ions from the loaded hybrids are very important facts due to the economic interest, the desorption experiments have been carried out in acidic media and in the case of the Cu(II) ions, the obtained results shows that they are desorbed in a large extension. This fact allows the regeneration of the ACs/H₄L materials for possible reuse and also the recovery of Cu(II) ions.

References:

- [1] Godino-Salido, M. L.; Santiago-Medina, A.; Arranz-Mascarós, P.; López-Garzón, R.; Gutiérrez-Valero, M.D.; Melguizo, M.; López-Garzón, F. J., Novel active carbon/crown ether derivative hybrid material for the selective removal of Cu(II) ions: the crucial role of the surface chemical functions, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* **2014**, 114, 94-104.
- [2] Gutierrez-Valero, M.D.; Arranz-Mascarós, P.; Peñas-San Juan, A.; Godino-Salido, M. L.; López-Garzón, R.; Santiago-Medina, A.; Melguizo-Guijarro, M.; Pérez-Mendoza, M.; López-Garzón, F. J.; Domingo-García, M., Transferring the properties of molecular receptors to the carbon surface in hybrid materials: The crucial role of porous texture, *Mat. Chem. Phys.* **2012**, 134, 608-615.

Assessment of different sorbents for metal removal from aqueous samples

Enriqueta ANTICO^{a)}, Claudia FONTAS^{a)}, Ignasi RODRIGUEZ-RODA^{b)}

^{a)}Departament de Química. Universitat de Girona. Girona. Spain ^{b)}Institut Català de recerca de l'Aigua (ICRA). Girona. Spain.

enriqueta.antico@udg.edu

The contamination of water resources in different parts of the world constitutes a problem that requires not only continuous monitoring of water quality, but also efficient water treatment technologies. The increasing number of people on the planet, physical water scarcity, and fresh water degradation due to natural causes and anthropogenic activities makes the situation even worse. Among the different options for water monitoring and treatment, solid sorbents offer an attractive alternative. We have evaluated the use of a new titanium dioxide (Adsorbsia As600) for metal preconcentration and recovery. The titanium dioxide (anatase) has been characterized and a pH_{pzc} of around 6 was measured. To determine the effectivity of the sorbent towards different metals, batch experiments were carried out using a well water sample (St Hilari, Girona, Spain) spiked with copper, zinc, aluminum, cadmium, and nickel at an environmental concentration level (1 mg L^{-1} , except Al $200 \text{ } \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and Cd $50 \text{ } \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$). Moreover, two other resins, Iontosorb Oxin bearing 8-hydroxyquinoline functional groups [1], and Duolite GT-73, with a thiol functionality [2], were also investigated and compared with the results found for Adsorbsia As600. For the sorbents Adsorbsia As600 and Iontosorb Oxin, extraction efficiency was $>90\%$ for all metals except for nickel (200 mg of solid, 40 mL of water sample and 24 h contact time). Duolite GT-73 provided satisfactory results for Cu(II) extraction, in agreement with the hard and soft acids and bases theory. Furthermore, only Iontosorb Oxin allowed the quantitative extraction of nickel.

For the recovery of the loaded metals, different eluents were tested, for example 3M HCl, 0.1M EDTA, 0.1M NaOH, and 0.5M NaSCN + 0.01M HCl. We found that HCl was the most adequate eluent from loaded Iontosorb Oxin resin, and EDTA for Adsorbsia As600. These two sorbents were used for the *in-situ* evaluation of metal contamination in water samples (19 well waters and 13 storage tanks) from the municipality of Torola, Mozarán, El Salvador.

Acknowledgements

The financial support of the Spanish Government (research project CTM2013-48967-C2-2-P) and of the Universitat of Girona (“Ajuts a projectes de cooperació internacional per al desenvolupament 2015”) are acknowledged. R. Sagristà, S. Cot, A. Ribó are knowledged for their participation in the international cooperation project.

References:

- [1] Matúš, P.; Kubavá, J., Complexation efficiency of differently fixed 8-hydroxyquinoline and salicylic acid ligand groups for labile aluminum species determination in soils. *Anal. Chim. Acta* **2006**, 573-574, 474-481.
- [2] Anticó, E.; Iglesias, M.; Salvadó, V., Recovery of Palladium(II) and Gold(III) from diluted liquors using the resin Duolite GT-73. *Anal. Chim. Acta* **1999**, 381, 61-67.

New molecularly imprinted polymer for diclofenac removal from water

**Nurlin ABU SAMAH^{a,c)}, Rosa M^a SEBASTIÁN PÉREZ^{b)}, Manuel VALIENTE MALMAGRO^{a)},
Montserrat LÓPEZ-MESAS^{a)}**

^{a)}Centre Grup de Tècniques de Separació en Química (GTS), Unitat de Química Analítica, Departament de Química, Univ. Autònoma de Barcelona, 08193 Bellaterra, Spain ^{b)}Organic Chemistry Section, Departament de Química, Univ. Autònoma de Barcelona, 08193 Bellaterra, Spain ^{c)}Faculty of Industrial Sciences & Technology, Universiti Malaysia Pahang, Malaysia

montserrat.lopez.mesas@uab.cat

Since a few decades ago, Environment Persistent Pharmaceutical Pollutants (EPPPs) have been introduced as one type of recalcitrant pollutant sources in water. In this study, the removal of Diclofenac (DCF) has been carried out using Molecularly Imprinted Polymer (MIP), synthesized via bulk polymerization with allylthiourea (AT) as the functional monomer. The DCF detection has been performed by UV spectrophotometer. From the kinetic study in batch mode, approximately 100% of removal is observed, with an initial concentration of 5 mg L⁻¹ of DCF within three minutes, agitated at 25°C (Figure 1). From the total adsorption study using a cartridge pre-packed with 10 mg of MIP a high adsorption capacity of 160 mg DCF/g MIP was obtained (Figure 2). The Scatchard plot also has been determined showing the profile for the homogenous process of adsorption (Figure 3). The similar result also has been observed by C. M. Dai, et al. [1]. All experiments were carried out in triplicate.

Figure 1. Kinetic removal of DCF using MIP

Figure 2. Total adsorption capacity of DCF

Figure 3. Scatchard plot

In order to observe the chemical reaction occurred between monomer and template, the pre-polymerization has also been studied by using ^1H NMR. The shift in the signal observed has been identified with the interactions between amine of AT group with carboxylic acid on DCF (Figure 4).

Fig 4. Pre-polymerization spectral shifted from low to high concentration of monomer, AT (ppm)

As conclusion, the developed MIP works as a good adsorbent in DCF removal. The molecularly imprinted technology has shown to be a promising technology for the removal of pharmaceuticals from water.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank Spanish Project CTM 2015-65414-C2-1-R, Skim Latihan Akademik IPTA (SLAI) by Ministry of Education and Universiti Malaysia Pahang, both from Malaysia, for financial support.

Reference:

- [1] Dai, C.-M.; Geissen, S.-U.; Zhang, Y.-L.; Zhang, Y.-J.; Zhou, X.-F., Selective removal of diclofenac from contaminated water using molecularly imprinted polymer microspheres. *Environ. Pollut.* **2011**, 159, 1660–1666.

Recovery of acidic pharmaceutical compounds via molecularly imprinted polymers from water

Nurlin ABU SAMAH^{a,b}, Xènia RAMIS-CORP^a, Ariadna NOGUERA-SÁEZ^a, Manuel VALIENTE^a, Montserrat LÓPEZ-MESAS^a

^a*Centre Grup de Tècniques de Separació en Química (GTS), Unitat de Química Analítica, Departament de Química, Univ. Autònoma de Barcelona, 08193 Bellaterra, Spain*

^b*Faculty of Industrial Sciences & Technology, Universiti Malaysia Pahang, Malaysia*
montserrat.lopez.mesas@uab.cat

Molecularly imprinted polymers (MIP) have been addressed as one method for the removal and analysis of contaminants. They show selectivity properties, high affinity and robustness. However, in wastewater and natural samples, where other micropollutants are present, deterioration in selectivity properties can be observed. One type of the pollutant sources present in water is the Environment Persistent Pharmaceutical Pollutants (EPPPs). In the present work, the efficiency, selectivity and robustness of MIP for the removal of indomethacin (IDM) and diclofenac (DCF) have been analyzed. Two MIP have been synthesized via bulk polymerization by using the different pharmaceutical compounds as template and allylthiourea (AT) as the functional monomer (MIP-DCF and MIP-IDM).

For the selectivity study, the removal efficiency was carried out in batch mode using different solutions of a mixture of two pharmaceuticals, IDM, DCF or ibuprofen (IBU). Results showed that IBU was not absorbed for any of the MIP in any mixture. MIP-DCF showed significant removal for DCF and IDM corresponding to the intermolecular attraction properties and higher to MIP-IDM.

The morphology of MIP-DCF and non-imprinted polymer (NIP) was studied by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), observing significant differences (Figure 1) due to the presence of the template.

Figure 1. MIP-DCF (a) and NIP (b) surface study using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) at EHT : 1kV and magnificant value 50.00 KX

Original MIP-DCF, and MIP after sorption and desorption cycles were scanned using Infrared – Attenuated Total Reflectance (IR-ATR) in order to see the differences in functional sites of MIP with or without DCF. The results showed significant peak in the original MIP, for N-H stretch at 3000 nm^{-1} and C-N at stretch 1180 nm^{-1} (Figure 2). For the MIP-DCF loaded

with DCF after a sorption process, a hydroxyl & N-H at 3300 nm^{-1} was observed (Figure 3). By comparing the three of them (Figure 4), there was a significant peak at 1650 nm^{-1} representing the C=C from aromatic rings at DCF which was present only in the MIP-DCF loaded with DCF. After desorption process the spectra looks similar to the original one.

Figure 2. Infrared spectral of original MIP-DCF, N-H stretch at 3100 nm^{-1} , C-N at stretch 1180 nm^{-1}

Figure 3. Infrared spectral of MIP-DCF loaded with DCF, -OH & N-H at 3300 nm^{-1}

— Original MIP-DCF
— MIP-DCF with DCF sorpted
— MIP-DCF after desorption of DCF

Figure 4. Comparative IR spectral for original MIP-DCF, loaded with DCF and after the desorption process. C=O functional group came from EDGMA (cross-linker) at 1750 nm^{-1}

For the recycling study, the MIP-DCF showed a $110\% \pm 1\%$ of adsorption for DCF and $98\% \pm 3\%$ of IDM. This value was not significantly decreased up to 10th cycles of loading and desorbing processes.

MIP-DCF has been shown to be an effective MIP for the removal of the pharmaceutical compounds DCF and IDM but not for IBU, probably due to the interactions between the nitrogen atoms at the pharmaceutical with the functional site of the monomers [see previous abstract].

Acknowledgements

The authors thank Spanish Project CTM 2015-65414-C2-1-R, Skim Latihan Akademik IPTA (SLAI) by Ministry of Education and Universiti Malaysia Pahang, both from Malaysia, for financial support

DNA-Binding Properties of Pyridin-3-yl Substituted Water Soluble Phthalocyanines

H. Yasemin YENİLMEZ^{a)}, Maryam MOEINI ALISHAH^{a)}, Zehra Altuntaş BAYIR^{a)}

^{a)} *Istanbul Technical University, Department of Chemistry, 34469, Istanbul, Turkey;*
yenilmez@itu.edu.tr

Phthalocyanines (Pcs) are well known chromophores for their intense absorption in the UV/blue and the red/near IR spectral regions, as well as for their photochemical, electrochemical and thermal stability [1]. This class of compounds has been used in chemical sensors, non-linear optic materials, semiconductors, catalysts, optical data storage materials, electrochromic displays, liquid crystals and photovoltaic cells [2]. Moreover, it is known that water-soluble phthalocyanines used to treat cancer. According to this perspective, the goal of this work is to synthesize quaternized metallo-phthalocyanines which have the potential use for photolysis of DNA in tumor cells.

Our research group has reported about the synthesis of alkynyl-substituted metallophthalocyanines of symmetric and unsymmetric nature [3, 4]. In this study, a novel phthalocyanine precursor bearing pyridin-3-ylethynyl groups and its tetrasubstituted metallo-phthalocyanines at peripheral positions were reported. The synthesis of symmetrically substituted novel metallophthalocyanines bearing four pyridin-3-ylethynyl moieties was achieved by using palladium-catalyzed Sonogashira cross-coupling methodology starting from corresponding tetraiodo-substituted metallophthalocyanines.

References:

- [1] Leznoff, C. C.; Lever, A. B. P., *Phthalocyanines properties and applications*, Vol. 1, VCH Publisher, Weinheim, **1989**.
- [2] Mc Keown, N. B., *Phthalocyanine Materials: Synthesis, Structure and Function*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, **1998**.

- [3] Sevim, A. M.; Yenilmez, H. Y.; Bayır, Z. A., Synthesis and photophysical properties of novel (trifluoromethyl)phenylethynyl-substituted metallophthalocyanines. *Polyhedron* **2013**, 62, 120-125.
- [4] Kalkan, A.; Koca, A.; Bayır, Z. A., New neutral and cationic η^6 -arene ruthenium complexes with phosphine and amine ligands: syntheses and molecular structures of $[(\eta^6\text{-p-cymene})\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)\text{Cl}_2]$, $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{Me}_6)\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_2\text{Py})\text{Cl}_2]$ and $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{Me}_6)\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_2\text{Py})\text{Cl}]^+$. *Polyhedron* **2004**, 23, 3155-3123.

Dna binding of organotin(IV) complexes of meso-tetra (4 sulfonatophenyl) porphine showing cellular activity

Sabriye AYDINOĞLU^{a)}, Tarita BIVER^{b)}, Tiziana FIORE^{c)}, Sonia MONTANARO^{b)}, Claudia PELLERITO^{c)}

^{a)}Department of Analytical Chemistry, Faculty of Pharmacy, Cukurova University, 01330 Adana, Turkey ^{b)}Department of Chemistry and Industrial Chemistry, University of Pisa, Via Moruzzi 13, 56124 Pisa, Italy ^{c)}Department of Physics and Chemistry (DiFC), University of Palermo, Viale delle Scienze, Ed. 17, 90128 Palermo, Italy;
saydinoglu@cu.edu.tr

It was observed that organometallic porphyrin systems, where the Sn(IV) residue is in side chains, coordinated via sulphonatophenyl groups of porphyrin, show interesting and peculiar in vitro activity, in agreement with the anti-tumour activity of organotin complexes[1]. In particular, it has been shown that dibutyl- and tributyl-tin(IV) derivatives of meso-tetra-(4-sulfonatophenyl)porphine are cytotoxic and induce apoptosis in A375 human melanoma cells [2-3]. Moreover, anionic porphyrins are selective G-quadruplex binders with important applications in studies on telomerase inhibition [4]. To contribute to enlighten the possible mechanism of action of these organometallic species, we analysed the interaction of the diorgano- and triorgano-tin(IV) derivatives of meso-tetra-(4-sulfonatophenyl)porphine to natural (calf thymus) DNA. Free meso-tetra-(4-sulfonatophenyl)porphine was also studied for comparison purposes.

Fluorescence and absorbance titrations (Figure, left) with relevant calculation of binding constants and analysis of their temperature dependence (Figure, right), fluorescence quenching and viscometric studies indicate that the drug binding to DNA occurs indeed, this having principally the features of external binding (also in case of the less hindered species). On the other hand, interestingly, the binding produces non negligible viscosity variations that might be related to polynucleotide conformational changes induced by the organometallic derivative.

References:

- [1] Pellerito, C.; Nagy, L.S.; Pellerito L.; Szorcsik A., Biological activity studies on organotin(IV)ⁿ⁺ complexes and parent compounds. *Journal of Organometallic Chemistry* **2006**, 691 (8), 1733-1747.
- [2] Costa, M.A.; Gulino, L.; Pellerito, L.; Fiore, T.; Pellerito, C.; Barbieri, G., Effects of two organotin(IV)(sulfonatophenyl)porphyrates on MAPKs and on the growth of A375 human melanoma cells. *Oncology Reports* **2009**, 21 (3), 593-599.
- [3] Costa, M.A.; Zito, F.; Emma, M.R.; Pellerito, L.; Fiore, T.; Pellerito, C.; Barbieri, G. Apoptosis and cell growth arrest in A375 human melanoma cells by diorganotin(IV) and triorganotin(IV) complexes of [meso-Tetra(4-sulfonatophenyl)porphine] manganese(III) chloride. *International Journal of Oncology* **2011**, 38 (3), 693-700.
- [4] Yaku, H.; Murashima, T.; Miyoshi, D.; Sugimoto, N.; Specific Binding of Anionic Porphyrin and Phthalocyanine to the G-Quadruplex with a Variety of in Vitro and in Vivo Applications. *Molecules* **2012**, 17 (9), 10586-10613.

Coordination of Zn(II) with human and murine Amyloid- β

**Valentina BORGHESANI^{a,b)}, Bruno ALIES^{a,b,c)}, Stéphanie SAYEN^{d)}, Emmanuel GUILLON^{d)},
Peter FALLER^{e)}, Christelle HUREAU^{a,b)}**

^{a)}CNRS, Laboratoire de Chimie de Coordination, 205 Route de Narbonne, 31400 Toulouse

^{b)} Université Toulouse III Paul Sabatier, 31077 Toulouse, France ^{c)} Université de Bordeaux,

ChemBioPharm INSERM U1212 CNRS UMR 5320, Bordeaux, France ^{d)} CNRS Institut de Chimie

Moléculaire de Reims (ICMR), Groupe de Chimie de Coordination, Université de Reims

Champagne-Ardenne, France ^{e)} Institut de Chimie, Biometals and Biological Chemistry

Université de Strasbourg Le Bel, 8eme etage, 4 rue B. Pascal 67081 Strasbourg, France.

valentina.borghesani@lcc-toulouse.fr

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is the most common neurodegenerative disease, with no known cure. In the brain of Alzheimer's patients are present intracellular neurofibrillary tangles and extracellular senile plaques, consisting of insoluble fibrillar aggregates of the amyloid- β peptide (A β). The amyloid cascade hypothesis describes this aggregation; where monomeric A β aggregates first into oligomers and later into fibrils. In the presence of metal ions, this aggregation is modified [1]. Coordination of A β with Cu(II) generally favours the formation of oligomeric species, whereas Zn(II) generally induces fibrillisation of the peptide. A β -Cu(II) oligomers are considered to be more toxic than A β -Zn(II) fibrils [2], because of their capability to produce Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS).

A better understanding of the AD mechanism requires investigations on mouse and rat models. However, the murine A β peptide, which differs from the human A β peptide by three point mutations, do not show amyloid deposition [3]. Consequently, studies are performed on transgenic mice or rats that produce the human A β (hA β) peptide in addition to their own peptide (mA β). The Cu(II) coordination to murine and human peptides differ [3].

Here we want to determine the coordination of Zn(II) on human and murine peptides and their differences. We also want to see whether they have an impact on aggregation. The aggregation of the peptide is evaluated by fluorescence and verified by AFM, while the different coordination is evaluated XANES, ¹H-NMR, affinity constant.

Figure 1. Proposed binding modes of Zn(II) to hA β and mA β .

References:

- [1] Hureau, C., Coordination of redox active metal ions to the amyloid precursor protein and to amyloid- β peptides involved in Alzheimer disease. Part 1: An overview. *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **2012**, 256 (19-20), 2164-2174.
- [2] Cuajungco, M.P.; Goldstein, L.E.; Nunomura, A.; Smith, M.A.; Lim, J.T.; Atwood C.S.; Huang X.; Farrar Y.W.; Perry, G.; Bush A.I., Evidence that the β -Amyloid Plaques of Alzheimer's Disease Represent the Redox-silencing and Entombment of A β by Zinc. *J. Biol. Chem.* **2000**, 275, 19439-19442.
- [3] Eury, H.; Bijani, C.; Faller, P.; Hureau, C., Copper(II) Coordination to Amyloid b: Murine versus Human Peptide. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, **2011**, 50, 901-905.

Interaction of Cu(II) ions with human serum amyloid A

Dorota KĘDZIERSKA^{a)}, Henryk KOZŁOWSKI^{a)}

Faculty of Chemistry, University of Wrocław, F. Joliot-Curie 14, 50-383 Wrocław, Poland;
dorota.kedzierska@chem.uni.wroc.pl

Serum amyloid A (SAA) is a major constituent of secondary amyloidosis diseases resulting from prolonged acute inflammation, for example due to rheumatoid arthritis. N-terminal part of this protein tends to form amyloid fibrils when the structure of the protein is destabilized by proteolytic cleavage. Recent crystallographic structure of SAA revealed that the protein is stabilized by its C-terminal part, forming multiple specific interactions with three out of four core α -helices of SAA [1] (Fig 1). SAA fragment of C-terminal residues 86-104 and its mutants were subject to studies of interactions with copper ions. Coordination of Cu(II) ions [2] by the peptides was characterized with potentiometric and spectroscopic methods.

Figure. 1. Single subunit of human SAA from Protein Data Bank structure 4IP8. Amyloid forming parts in shades of blue, the studied C-terminal fragment in red.

References:

- [1] Lu, J.; Yu, Y.; Zhu, I.; Cheng, Y.; Sun, P.D., Structural mechanism of serum amyloid A-mediated inflammatory amyloidosis. *Proc.Natl.Acad.Sci. USA* **2014**, 111, 5189-5194.
- [2] Kozłowski, H.; Kowalik-Jankowska, T.; Jeżowska-Bojczuk, M., Chemical and biological aspects of Cu²⁺ interactions with peptides and aminoglycosides, *Coordination Chemistry Reviews* **2005**, 249, 2323-2334.

Metal complexes of cysteine containing peptides

Györgyi SZUNYOG^{a)}, Márton LUKÁCS^{a)}, Norbert LIHI^{a)}, Ágnes GRENÁCS^{a)}, Katalin VÁRNAGY^{a)}

^{a)} *Department of Inorganic and Analytical Chemistry, University of Debrecen, Debrecen, Hungary*
szunyog.gyorgyi@science.unideb.hu

The heavy metals (as lead or cadmium) are serious environmental toxins, because they have accumulated in the environment much above the natural level due to the human activity during thousands of years. Based on the soft character of these metal ions, they can bind to the proteins and first of all the side chain thiol groups provide effective binding site for them. As a consequence, these metal ions are able to substitute the essential metal ions (e.g. zinc(II), nickel(II), calcium(II)) in the metalloenzymes and metalloproteins resulting drastic change in their biochemical functions^[1]. The accumulation of toxic metal ions can cause carcinogenic effect or physiological change in the bones, kidneys or indirectly might take part in the development of neurodegenerative disorders.

The goal of our research was the designing and synthesis of peptides with high lead(II) and/or cadmium(II) binding affinity. We synthesised a series of peptides containing one or two cysteine residues. One group of the ligands have free N-terminal amino group and amide group on the C-termini: Ala-Cys-Ser-Ser-Ala-Cys-Ser-NH₂ (ACSSACS-NH₂) and Cys-Ser-Ser-Ala-Cys-Ser-NH₂ (CSSACS-NH₂), while the other group of them are terminally protected peptides: Ac-Ser-Ala-Ala-Cys-NH₂ (Ac-SAAC-NH₂), Ac-Cys-Ser-Cys-NH₂ (Ac-CSC-NH₂) Ac-Cys-Ser-Ser-Cys-NH₂ (Ac-CSSC-NH₂), Ac-Ser-Cys-Cys-Ser-NH₂ (Ac-SCCS-NH₂).

We studied the complex formation processes of these molecules in the presence of toxic cadmium(II) and lead(II) ions and completed those with studies of complexes of essential zinc(II) ions. The stoichiometry and stability constants of the metal complexes were determined by potentiometry, while their structures were supported by means of UV-, MS- and NMR-spectroscopy. In the case of two peptides containing free terminal amino group the thiolate groups are the main binding site, but the coordination of terminal amino group contributes to the formation of stable complexes. Moreover, zinc(II) and cadmium(II) ions are able to induce the deprotonation and coordination of amide nitrogen of Ac-ACSSACS-NH₂ forming (NH₂,N⁻,S⁻) coordinated metal complexes^[2].

Figure 1. Theoretical distribution curves of complexes formed in the Cd(II)-Zn(II)-Pb(II)-ACSSACS-NH₂ =1:1:1:1 (left) and the Cd(II)-Zn(II)-Pb(II)-CSSACS-NH₂ (right) systems.

For the terminally protected tri- and tetrapeptides the thiolate group is the primary binding site. The di-cysteine containing peptides bind metal ions through both thiolate groups resulting in mono- and/or bis(ligand) complexes with high stability. This coordination mode are able to prevent the hydrolysis of cadmium(II) and lead(II) ions and stable mixed hidroxido complexes are formed in equimolar solutions at high pH range. The data reveal that all studied peptides form stable complexes with both cadmium(II) and lead(II) ions and the stability order follows the Cd(II) ~ Pb(II) > Zn(II).

Acknowledgements:

This work was supported by the Hungarian Scientific Research Fund (NKFI-6, K 115480).

References:

- [1] Farkas, E.; Bóka, B.; Szócs, B.; Godó, A.; Sóvágó, I., Effect of the types and arrangements of donor atoms on Pb(II) versus Zn(II) binding preference of selected amino acids, peptides and derivatives. *Inorg. Chim. Acta* **2014**, 423, 242-249.
- [2] Lihi, N.; Grenács, Á.; Tímári S.; Turi, I.; Bányai I.; Sóvágó, I.; Várnagy K., Zinc(II) and cadmium(II) complexes of N-terminally free peptides containing two separate cysteinyl binding sites. *New J. Chem.*, **2015**, 39, 8364-8372.

Analysis of the binding of commercial stains to protein materials used in artworks

Tarita BIVER^{a)}, Ilaria BONADUCE^{a)}, Maria Perla COLOMBINI^{a)}, Lorenzo DI BARI^{a)}, Sibilla ORSINI^{a)}, Marcella VENTURINI^{a)}, Francesco ZINNA^{a)}

^{a)}Department of Chemistry and Industrial Chemistry – University of Pisa – Via Moruzzi 13,
56124 Pisa - Italy

Preservation of works of art is a task that involves chemists and a challenge connected to the development of new approaches and procedures. Still today, the reliable stratigraphic localization of proteins in art samples can be arduous [1,2].

In order to contribute to the optimisation of a reliable protocol for localising proteins in art samples, we have analysed (in water solution) the interaction between some of the fluorescent stains commonly used in gel electrophoresis (Figure 1) and proteinaceous paint binders. Of these, dyes 1 and 3 have also been used to detect proteins in paint cross sections. Dyes 1 and 2 bind to the proteins in a non-covalent way; dyes 3, 4 and 5 undergo covalent binding. As for biosubstrates dried egg white (EW) based on ovalbumin, casein (CAS) from dried cow milk, rabbit skin glue (RSG) based on partially hydrolysed collagen and, as a standard reference, purified chicken egg ovalbumin (OVA) were taken into account. The affinity constants for binding of the fluorescent stains to different protein matrices were obtained by fluorescence titrations in aqueous solution. Moreover, the circularly polarized luminescence (CPL) technique [3,4] was used to analyse the binding features.

Figure 1. The fluorescent stains studied in this work; the red colour emphasizes the reactive group in the case of the covalent fluorescent stains.

The results obtained contribute to our understanding of the different affinity of the dyes for selected proteins and to shed light on the binding mechanism in these complex systems. Moreover, it is demonstrated that CPL spectroscopy can be applied in the analysis of complex matrices of practical interest and that it can give information about the occurrence of an interaction when fluorescence or ECD methods fail.

References:

- [1] Colombini, M. P.; Andreotti, A.; Bonaduce, I. ; Modugno F.; Ribechini, E., Analytical Strategies for Characterizing Organic Paint Media Using Gas Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry. *Accounts of Chemical Research*, **2010**, 43, 715-727.
- [2] Dallongeville, S.; Garnier, N.; Rolando, C.; Tokarski, C., Proteins in Art, Archaeology, and Paleontology: From Detection to Identification. *Chemical Reviews*, **2016**, 116, 2-79.
- [3] Kumar, J.; Nakashima, T.; Kawai, T., Circularly Polarized Luminescence in Chiral Molecules and Supramolecular Assemblies. *Journal of Physical Chemistry Letters*, **2015**, 6(17), 3445-3452.
- [4] Zinna, F.; Di Bari, L., Lanthanide Circularly Polarized Luminescence: Bases and Applications. *Chirality* **2015**, 27(1), 1-13.

Synthetic hexa-His-tags vs. natural His-tag peptides - differences and similarities in metal ion coordination and structural properties.

Joanna WATLY^{a)}, Henryk KOZŁOWSKI^{a)}, Yifat MILLER^{b)c)}, Robert WIECZOREK^{a)}, Magdalena ROWINSKA-ZYREK^{a)}

^{a)} Faculty of Chemistry, University of Wrocław, F. Joliot-Curie 14, 50-383 Wrocław, Poland ^{b)} Department of Chemistry, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Beer-Sheva 84105, Israel ^{c)} Ilse Katz Institute for Nanoscale Science and Technology, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Beer-Sheva 84105, Israel
joanna.watly@chem.uni.wroc.pl

The imidazole nitrogen in the side chain of histidine in peptides offers the primary coordinating ligand to metal ions such as: Zn(II), Cu(II), Ni(II) [1]. Huge number of metalloproteins consisting histidine-rich domains were found in species from all kingdoms and play role e.g. in metal transport, storage, or detoxification [2]. The special group of His-rich proteins are those which contain His-tag motifs. This motif is characterised by different number of consecutive histidines, often from three to even twelve. The name of 'His-tag' is taken from synthetic tag commonly used in Immobilized-metal affinity chromatography for purification of recombinant proteins [3]. Usually, in this technique are used hexa-His-tags, which are connected to N- or C- terminus of purified protein, and free sites of immobilized metal ions e.g. Ni(II) interact with histidine residues in His-tag. Examples of natural proteins with His-tag motifs are: HypB from *B. japonicum* (HAHDHHHDHGHDHDHGHDGHHHHHHGHDQDHHHHHDHAH), Hpn from *H. pylori* (MAHHEEQHGHHHHHHHTHHHHYHGGEGHHHHHSSHHEEGCCSTSDSHHQEEGCCHGHHE) [4], pHpG from *A. squamigera* (EDDHHHHHHHHHGVGGGGGGGGG) [5] or cyclin T1 from human genome (HPSNHHHHHNHSHKHS) [6]. Biological function and mechanism of activity of these proteins is not yet fully.

Recently, the study of synthetic hexa-His-tag and natural nona-His-tag from snake venom of *Atheris squamigera* were performed by using experimental and computational techniques. Detailed analysis have shown that the multiple His residues along poly-His-tag domain bind metal ions in very effective way, forming polymorphic states. Metal ions, e.g. Cu(II) can bind various sets of imidazoles depending on the number of histidine residues that are located in these domains with different efficiencies. In hexa-His-tag, metal ion is coordinated by maximum two His residues and form six different binding states. Model, in which copper is bound to first and fifth imidazole nitrogen, presents the most stable complex. MD and DFT calculations shown that metal ion induces the formation of regular α -helix structure in this complex [7]. Similar effects were observed in case of nona-His-tag from pHpG peptide (pHG), but either the number of polymorphic states, stability of complexes and impact on the formation of secondary structure are much more higher than in hexa-His-tag [8]. There is a pronounced correlation between the number of histidines in His-tag and secondary structure formation, polymorphic states and thermodynamic stability of these

complexes. It is also interesting, that peptides with His-tag motifs form extremely stable complexes in comparison with other peptide very rich in histidine residues, but without poly-histidyl string (Fig. 1) [7-9].

Figure 1. Competition plots for Cu(II) complexes with peptides containing His-tag motifs and domains rich in histidine residues: a) hexa-His-tag and Hpn fragment, b) hexa-His-tag and zebrafish prion protein (zp-PrP63-87), c) hexa-His-tag and pHG, d) pHG and its mutated derivative.

Acknowledgements:

The work was supported by the National Science Centre (nr UMO-2014/13/D/ST5/02868)

References:

- [1] Liao, S.-M.; Du, Q.-S.; Meng, J.-Z.; Pang, Z.-W.; Huang, R.-B., *Chemistry Central Journal* **2013**, *7*.
- [2] Rowinska-Zyrek, M.; Witkowska, D.; Potocki, S.; Remelli, M.; Kozlowski, H., *New Journal of Chemistry* **2013**, *37*, 58-70.
- [3] Knecht, S.; Ricklin, D.; Eberle, A. N.; Ernst, B., *Journal of Molecular Recognition* **2009**, *22*, 270-279.
- [4] Kozlowski, H.; Potocki, S.; Remelli, M.; Rowinska-Zyrek, M.; Valensin, D., *Coordination Chemistry Reviews* **2013**, *257*, 2625-2638.
- [5] Favreau, P.; Cheneval, O.; Menin, L.; Michalet, S.; Gaertner, H.; Principaud, F.; Thai, R.; Menez, A.; Bulet, P.; Stocklin, R., *Rapid Communications in Mass Spectrometry* **2007**, *21*, 406-412.
- [6] Salichs, E.; Ledda, A.; Mularoni, L.; Alba, M. M.; de la Luna, S., *Plos Genetics* **2009**, *5*.
- [7] Watly, J.; Simonovsky, E.; Wieczorek, R.; Barbosa, N.; Miller, Y.; Kozlowski, H., *Inorganic Chemistry* **2014**, *53*, 6675-6683.
- [8] Watly, J.; Simonovsky, E.; Barbosa, N.; Spodzieja, M.; Wieczorek, R.; Rodziewicz-Motowidlo, S.; Miller, Y.; Kozlowski, H., *Inorganic chemistry* **2015**, *54*, 7692-702.
- [9] Brasili, D.; Watly, J.; Simonovsky, E.; Guerrini, R.; Barbosa, N. A.; Wieczorek, R.; Remelli, M.; Kozlowski, H.; Miller, Y., *Dalton transactions (Cambridge, England : 2003)* **2016**, *45*, 5629-39.

Metallophores as Mediators for Metal Cycling: L- α -amino-acid residue ligands as new molybdenum buffers

Sofia GAMA^{a)}, Markus HILGER^{a)}, Winfried PLASS^{a)}

^{a)}Institut für Anorganische und Analytische Chemie, Friedrich-Schiller-Universität Jena,
Germany
sofia.gama@uni-jena.de

Nitrogen fixation, the reaction responsible for the transformation of atmospheric nitrogen into bioavailable ammonia, is mediated in nature by the nitrogenase enzyme in N₂-fixing bacteria. Nitrogenases have three isoforms, depending on the metal cofactor (Mo-, V- and Fe-only nitrogenase). Their activity depends on the acquisition of metals for the corresponding cofactor synthesis, which is the reason why metal bioavailability limits nitrogen fixation in natural ecosystems [1].

Unlike iron oxides, molybdenum is present either as molybdate (MoO₄²⁻) or attached to organic matter and/or mineral surfaces. Both forms lead to limited bio-availability of molybdate in nature [2], as either leaching or low solubility characterize these metal sources. Common laboratory culture media do not reflect these natural limiting conditions, since molybdenum is used as molybdate in excess within a closed system as the solutes are concerned.

In view of that, we aim to develop libraries of synthetic molybdenum chelating agents to mimic natural metal sources in artificial media, providing non-toxic cis-dioxidometallate complexes, which are stable under various physiological conditions, and not taken up by bacteria, functioning as a *Mo-buffer*. Those complexes would be the only source of metal in the culture medium improving the ecological relevance of further laboratory studies. Furthermore, the use of metal ion-buffers in controlled biosystems may also increase the knowledge and understanding on metal acquisition mechanisms.

In this communication, we will present the study of an L- α -amino-acid residue family of ligands and its molybdenum complexes, as new candidates for Mo-buffer.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to acknowledge the support by the Collaborative Research Centre ChemBioSys (CRC 1127) which is funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG).

References:

- [1] a) Bellenger, J.; Wichard, T.; Kustka, A.; Kraepiel, A., Uptake of molybdenum and vanadium by a nitrogen-fixing soil bacterium using siderophores. *Nat. Geosc.* **2008**, 1(4), 243-246; b) Cornish, A.; Page, W., *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* **2000**, 66 (4) 1580-1586.
- [2] a) Cruywagen, J.; Draaijer, A.; Heyns, J.; Rohwer, E., Molybdenum(VI) equilibria in different ionic media. Formation constants and thermodynamic quantities. *Inorg. Chim. Acta* **2002**, 331, 322-329; b) Wichard, T.; Mishra, B.; Myneni, S.; Bellenger, J.; Kraepiel, A., Storage and bioavailability of molybdenum in soils increased by organic matter complexation. *Nat. Geosc.* **2009**, 2, 625-629.

Evaluation of the adsorption capacity of antimony from aqueous solution by using cork as bio(adsorbent)

Manel Domínguez^{a)}, Lorenzo Massimi^{b)}, Verónica Verdugo^{a)}, Cristina Palet^{a)}

a) Centre Grup de Tècniques de Separació en Química, Unitat de Q.Analítica, Departament de Química, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 08193 Bellaterra, Catalunya, Spain *b) Sapienza University of Rome, Department of Chemistry, Rome, Italy*
manel.dr@gmail.com

Nowadays many products are dumped into waters causing serious pollution problems, such as the spill of heavy metals like iron, lead, cadmium and others. Adsorption is one of the most useful methodology to remove metals and metalloids from wastewaters. In recent years many researchers have studied the capabilities of low cost biomass materials as biological adsorbents such as food wastes, leathers, cork, hairs, chicken feathers, degreased wool,[1] biochar obtained from different original biomasses, and sponges.

Cork (*Quecur suber L.*) has been chosen in the present work as bio(adsorbent) to remove antimony (Sb) from aqueous solutions. This low cost material is the outer bark of the oak tree and it is industrially used for several purposes, principally the manufacturing of wine stoppers. Cork has high biosorption efficiencies because of its physical characteristic like elasticity and impermeability as well as its chemical composition (a complex mixture of fatty acids and heavy organic alcohols $\approx 45\%$ w/w, tannins $\approx 6\%$ w/w, polysaccharides $\approx 12\%$ w/w, lignin $\approx 27\%$ w/w, alkanes, mineral content $\approx 5\%$ and the most abundant element Ca 0.038–0.625% w/w).[2]

Antimony is a metalloid, naturally present in the environment but also introduced by human activities. It is classified as a minor metal, growing in strategic importance because of its use in flame-retardants, plastics and semiconductors. Sb is toxic and carcinogenic with no known biological function.[3] So, its removal from water is of unquestionable importance as well as its recovery due to the growing interest in antimony by the industry. The aim of this work is to evaluate the adsorption capacity of Sb (III) and Sb (V) by this innovative bio(adsorbent).

In order to evaluate the cork adsorption capacity, kinetics and isotherm behaviour is checked. Corresponding batch experiments have been performed, also to determine the influence of the aqueous antimony speciation. So, 25 mg of cork were stirred in presence of 2.5mL of Sb (III) and/or Sb (V) synthetic solutions at pH 5. At this pH the Sb(III) is dissolved in its corresponding neutral form, $\text{Sb}(\text{OH})_3$, and Sb(V) is present as its anionic form, $\text{Sb}(\text{OH})_6^-$.

First, cork has been shown as a good bio(adsorbent) for antimony from weak acidic aqueous solutions. The kinetic study shows that cork adsorbs Sb(III) faster than Sb(V), reaching the equilibrium uptake at 6 h in both cases. The form of the active sites of the cork adsorbent surface, with carboxylic and phenolic groups, could explain this phenomenon. So, cork preferably interacts with the neutral form of Sb(III) instead with the anionic form of Sb(V). These results are complemented by the isotherm profile, which shows higher total sorption capacity for Sb(III) than Sb(V).

Adsorption kinetic curves of Sb (III) and Sb (V) by cork.

Acknowledgements:

This work has been financially supported by the project CHEMNEXUS (Ref: CTM2015-65414-C2-1-R) from the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (MINECO) and the European Regional Development Fund (FEDER). Verónica Verdugo is grateful to the Catalan Government for her predoctoral fellowship, FI-DGR 2015.

References:

- [1] Helan Zhang PhD, Biosorption of heavy metals from aqueous solutions using keratin biomaterials, July **2014**, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona.
- [2] López-Mesas, M.; Navarrete, E.; Carrillo F.; Palet, C., Bioseparation of Pb(II) and Cd(II) from aqueous solution using cork waste biomass. Modeling and optimization of the parameters of the biosorption step, *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2011**, 174, 9–17.
- [3] Navarro, P.; Alguacil, F. J., Adsorption of antimony and arsenic from a copper electrorefining solution onto activated carbon. *Hydrometallurgy* **2002**, 66, 101–105.

Study of the effect of the pyrolysis and post-treatment procedures in the adsorption of heavy metals by biomass application to soil

**Cristina Wei LI^{a)}, Jing Jing ZHAO^{a)}, Montserrat RESINA-GALLEGO^{a)}, Josep Maria ALCAÑIZ^{b)},
Xavier DOMENE^{b)}, Cristina PALET^{a)}**

^{a)} Centre Grup de Tècniques de Separació en Química, Unitat de Q. Analítica, Departament de Química, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 08193 Bellaterra, Catalunya, Spain ^{b)} CREAM, Campus de Bellaterra (UAB), Edifici C, 08193 Bellaterra, Catalunya, Spain
cristina.li.ye@gmail.com

Waste biomaterials are considered ideal alternatives as suitable surrogates in the field, and as novel bio(adsorbents) due to the low relatively cost-effective ratio and the high efficient adsorption capacities for heavy metals [1]. Among them, pyrolyzed biomass (Biochar) could be useful for this purpose.

Biochar can be used as soil amendment to enhance soil water and nutrient retention which would lead them to be more bioavailable for plants [2], but it can also adsorb elements such as heavy metals (Cu, Pb, Cd, Cr, among others), potentially reducing its bioavailability, which is the main aim of this investigation. The aim of the present investigation was studying how pyrolysis procedure influences the adsorption capacity of different biomass feedstocks and derived biochars with or without post-treatments.

Original feedstock: granulated pine

Biochar obtained by gasification procedure of granulated pine

For this purpose, three different biomass feedstocks (pine, corn and populus) were prepared by three different pyrolysis procedures [3] (fast and slow pyrolysis, and by a gasification procedure). Biochars were sieved to 2 mm and the absorption tested with no additional treatment or treated (washing) by two different cleaning procedures (Milli-Q water or with a 0.1M nitric acid solution). Each adsorption trial was performed with 25 mg of each unwashed/washed material stirred for 24h in presence of 2.5mL of solutions containing either individual or mixed metal solutions of Cu, Pb, Cr or/and Cd at pH 4. Kinetics profiles are checked. Furthermore, the presence of organic contaminants such as Polycyclic Aromatic

Hydrocarbons (PAHs) has been evaluated for each pyrolysis procedure, due to their potential bioavailability for plants [4].

The kinetic study shows faster adsorption when using biochar prepared by gasification procedure, and with higher adsorption percentages compared with the corresponding feedstocks.

Adsorption Kinetics of Biochar obtained by gasification procedure of granulated pine for Cr, Cu, Cd and Pb

In general, the biochars without cleaning treatment presented higher metal adsorption capacity than the other materials tested (feedstock biomass or washed biochars by water or nitric acid). Furthermore, the effect of the pyrolysis on such adsorption was feedstock-dependent. In the case of the biochar obtained by gasification procedure, higher presence of PAHs was found which also correlates with higher metal adsorption capacity.

Acknowledgements:

This work has been financially supported by the project CHEMNEXUS (Ref: CTM2015-65414-C2-1-R) from the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (MINECO) and the European Regional Development Fund (FEDER). Jingjing Zhao thanks to the China Scholarship Council for her grant.

Reference:

- [1] Ahalya, N.; Ramachandra T.V.; Kanamadi, R.D., Biosorption of heavy metals, *Res. J. Chem. Environ.* **2003**, 7, 71–79.
- [2] Lehmann, J.; Stephen J., *Biochar for Environmental Management: Science and Technology*. Earthscan: London, **2009**, 1, 1-6.
- [3] Song, X.d.; Xue, X.y.; Chen, D.z.; He, P.j.; Dai, X.h., Application of Biochar from Sewage Sludge to Plant Cultivation: Influence of Pyrolysis Temperature and Biochar-to-soil Ratio on Yield and Heavy Metal Accumulation. *Chemosphere* **2014**, 109,213-220.
- [4] Hale, S.E.; Lehmann, J.; Rutherford, D; Zimmerman, A.R.; Bachmann, R.T.; Shitumbanuma, V.; O'Toole, A.; Sundqvist, K.L.; Arp, H.P.H.; Cornelissen, G., Quantifying the Total and Bioavailable Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons and Dioxins in Biochars. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2012**, 46 (5), 2830-2838.

New photo-switchable Pt-azobenzene complexes as potential anticancer drugs

Katia G. SAMPER^{a)}, Julia LORENZO^{b)}, Mercè CAPDEVILA^{a)}, Pau BAYÓN^{a)}, Òscar PALACIOS^{a)}

^{a)} Dept. Química, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 08193, Cerdanyola del Vallès (Barcelona) ^{b)} Institut de Biotecnologia i Biomedicina, Dept. Bioquímica i Biologia Molecular, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 08913, Cerdanyola del Vallès (Barcelona)
Katia.Ghannadzadeh@uab.cat

Platinum complexes are widely used as chemotherapy due to its anticancer activity. The first platinum-drug used in chemotherapy, cisplatin, was discovered some decades ago. Although it is still used, side effects and the loss of the complex before arriving to the DNA target, due to drug resistance in some tumours or non-desired protein interactions, are some problems that must be improved. Phototherapy appeared as an innovative strategy in order to avoid these problems. Several photosensitive-molecules are described in the literature, such as azobenzene, which presents a well-known and characteristic *cis* - *trans* isomerization easily controllable by UV-vis light, heat or ultrasounds, being very useful for medicinal applications. Isomerization of azobenzene as metal-ligand in platinum-complexes can be used to modulate the reactivity of the drug when interacting with the desire target.

In this work, we studied the interaction of the several platinum-azobenzene complexes with proteins and oligonucleotides by means of ESI-TOF MS and their intercalating properties with ct-DNA by fluorescence. Cell cultures of these complexes have also been carried out in order to check the differential toxicity of these complexes. A deep knowledge of the reactivity of these compounds would provide valuable information to future design of novel photo-switchable anticancer drugs.

Acknowledgements

The financial support received from MINECO-FEDER (Projects BIO2015-67358-C2-2-P and CTQ2015-70371-REDT) is acknowledged. K.G.S. acknowledges Departament de Química from UAB for the financial support of PIF scholarship.

“Old” Cu(II) complexes with “new” anticancer properties. An interesting approach

Quim PEÑA^{a)}, Jalila SIMAAN^{b)}, Julia LORENZO^{c)}, Olga IRANZO^{b)}, Mercè CAPDEVILA^{a)}, Òscar PALACIOS^{a)}

a) Departament de Química, Facultat de Ciències, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 08193-Cerdanyola del Vallès (Barcelona, Spain)

b) Institut des Sciences Moléculaires de Marseille, ISM2/BioSciences UMR CNRS, Aix-Marseille Université, Campus Scientifique de Saint Jérôme, F-13397-Marseille Cédex (Marseille, France)

c) Institut de Biotecnologia i Biomedicina, Dept. Bioquímica i Biologia Molecular, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 08193-Cerdanyola del Vallès (Barcelona, Spain)

Joaquim.Pena@uab.cat

Nowadays, cancer is a widespread disease, being the leading cause of death in developing countries. The serendipitous discovery of cisplatin in the 20th century and its high cytotoxic effect heralded a new era that promoted Medicinal Inorganic Chemistry to the front of the fight against cancer.[1] Nonetheless, cisplatin has several side effects owing to the reactivity of Pt with proteins. In order to overcome them, new tendencies are driving the research towards new non-Pt drugs (Au, Ir, Ru, Cu and Ti).[2] Copper takes a special role among all of them due to its intrinsic nature as an essential metal and its interesting Cu(II)/Cu(I) redox pair. This may generate fewer side effects than other reported metal drugs. This Cu(II)/Cu(I) redox pair has been reported to biologically generate ROS (reactive oxygen species), which are able to cause cell damage through oxidative mechanism.[3]

Herewith we report the study of the anticancer properties of four existing Cu(II) complexes bearing *N*-donor ligands -which appear to enable Cu complexes to interact with biomolecules-, previously used for a totally different purpose. Cytotoxic studies and interactions towards DNA have been assessed, studying both covalent and non-covalent modes of binding via MS, UV-VIS and fluorescence, as well as evaluating the DNA cleaving properties of the assayed compounds.

The obtained results have demonstrated that three, and especially two of them, of the assayed complexes exhibit DNA interaction and high antiproliferative activity in HeLa cells giving rise to IC₅₀ values around, or even better, than cisplatin. Moreover, achieved results also suggest a redox-dependent mechanism, being the oxidative cleavage one of the most important pathways for these Cu(II) compounds. The presence of many redox processes, either on the metal centre or on the ligand, and the biologically available Cu(II)/Cu(I) redox potentials apparently seem to be related to their oxidative damage, and hence, to their cytotoxicity. These compounds have shown an interesting “new” and beneficial role for cancer therapy, which will allow the design of specific ligands for Cu(II) that may improve the anticancer activity of the existing drugs.

Acknowledgements

The financial support received from MINECO-FEDER (Projects BIO2015-67358-C2-2-P and CTQ2015-70371-REDT) is kindly acknowledged. QP also acknowledges *Ministerio de Educación, Cultura y Deporte* for the financial support of a FPU scholarship.

References:

- [1] Guo, Z.; Sadler, P. J., Metals in Medicine. *Angew. Chemie Int. Ed.* **1999**, *38*, 1512–1531.
- [2] Muhammad, N.; Guo, Z., Metal-based anticancer chemotherapeutic agents. *Curr. Opin. Chem. Biol.* **2014**, *19*, 144–153.
- [3] Schumacker, P. T., Reactive oxygen species in cancer cells: live by the sword, die by the sword. *Cancer Cell* **2006**, *10*, 175–176.

Acknowledgements

The financial support received from MINECO-FEDER (Projects BIO2015-67358-C2-2-P and CTQ2015-70371-REDT) is kindly acknowledged. JB also acknowledges Departament de Química at the UAB for the PIF scholarship.

References:

- [1] Müller, C.; Schibli., Prospects in folate receptor-targeted radionuclide therapy. *Frontiers in Oncology*. **2013**, 3, 249.
- [2] Lecina, J.; Carrer, A.; Álvarez-Larena, A.; et al., New Bioconjugated Rhenium Carbonyls by Transmetalation Reaction with Zinc Derivatives. *Organometallics* **2012**, 31, 5884-5893.
- [3] Baier, G.; Baumann, D.; Siebert, J. M.; et al. Suppressing Unspecific Cell Uptake for Targeted Delivery Using Hydroxyethyl Starch Nanocapsules. *Biomacromolecules*. **2012**, 13, 2704-2715.
- [4] Schneider, R.; Schmitt, F.; Frochot, C.; et al. Design, synthesis, and biological evaluation of folic acid targeted tetraphenylporphyrin as novel photosensitizers for selective photodynamic therapy. *Bioorg. Med. Chem.* **2005**, 13, 2799-2808.

Biomimetic siderophores for iron(III) tracking and sensing purposes

Karolina ZDYB^{a)}, Evgenia OLSHVANG^{b)}, Abraham SHANZER^{b)}, Elzbieta GUMIENNA-KONTECKA^{a)}

^{a)} Faculty of Chemistry, University of Wrocław, Wrocław, Poland, ^{b)} Weizmann Institute of Science, Rehovot, Israel

karolina.zdyb@chem.uni.wroc.pl

Iron is one of the most essential elements for living organisms, being responsible for processes such as oxygen metabolism and DNA synthesis. Despite the crucial importance, both its deficiency or excess cause considerable disruption of homeostasis. The problem of iron uptake comes from its low bioavailability due to low solubility of ferric hydroxy-compounds in the environment and, in case of microorganisms, formation of stable complexes with bioligands of the host organism. To acquire iron, and at the same time overcome the toxic iron side-effects, microorganisms use siderophores - low molecular weight molecules with high binding affinity for ferric iron.

The difficulties in synthesis of structurally complicated natural siderophores have directed the siderophore research towards biomimetic chemistry, aiming at mimicking or reproducing the *function* of the natural product rather than its detailed *structure*. This approach allowed to diversify the arsenal of biologically active siderophore-type molecules, introduce additional desired chemical and/or physical properties, and provide means to identify general motifs governing an interplay between structure and function in biological activity.

Following these principles, we have been working on characterization of novel biomimetic compounds, artificial siderophores, in terms of iron complex formation and stability, for the construction of structural probes of microbial iron uptake processes [1, 2] and iron sensors [3].

Over the years, we were able to couple iron binding or its release with a signaling component in order to elicit spectrophotometric signals. Attaching a fluorescent 6-aminonaphthalimide group at the carboxyl terminus of desferrioxamine biomimetic analogue provided a tool to track the path of the iron from the environment to the cells of *Yersinia enterocolitica* [2]. Moreover, inspired by L-vulnibactin - microbial siderophore from *Vibrio vulnificus*, we fused the iron(III) binding site with a fluorescent probe into a single functionality, and studied tripodal phenoloxazoline-based ligands. Due to their fluorescent properties, the Fe(III) coordination event could be easily monitored, with detection limits in the low ng/mL range [3].

Here we will present the Fe(III) binding properties of novel artificial siderophores in the perspective of using the compounds as tools for investigating iron uptake by

siderophore-utilizing organisms. We will also discuss abilities of these biomimetics to coordinate La(III) ions in order to use them for iron detection via an assay displacement approach.

Acknowledgements

Financial support by Wroclaw Centre of Biotechnology (The Leading National Research Centre Program, KNOW, 2014–2018) is gratefully acknowledged.

References:

- [1] Olshvang, E.; Szebesczyk, A.; Kozłowski, H.; Hadar, Y.; Gumienna-Kontecka, E.; Shanzer, A., Biomimetic ferrichrome: structural motifs for switching between narrow- and broad-spectrum activities in *P. putida* and *E. coli*. *Dalton Transactions* **2015**, 44, 20850-20858.
- [2] Kornreich-Leshem, H.; Ziv, C.; Gumienna-Kontecka, E.; Arad-Yellin, R.; Chen, Y.; Elhabiri, M.; Albrecht-Gary, M.-A.; Hadar, Y.; Shanzer, A., Ferrioxamine B Analogues: Targeting the FoxA Uptake System in the Pathogenic *Yersinia enterocolitica*. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2005**, 127, (4) 1137–1145.
- [3] Kikkeri, R.; Traboulsi, H.; Humbert, N.; Gumienna-Kontecka, E.; Arad-Yellin, R.; Melman, G.; Elhabiri, M.; Albrecht-Gary, A.-M.; Shanzer, A., Toward Iron Sensors: Bioinspired Tripods Based on Fluorescent Phenol-oxazoline Coordination Sites. *Inorg. Chem.* **2007**, 46, 2485–2497.

Segregation of metal ions in multimetallic solutions by using sorption/desorption cycles. A green separation process

Bas STEVENS^{a)}, Pieter BUSSCHAERT^{a)}, Núria FIOL^{b)}, Jordi POCH^{b)}, Florencio DE LA TORRE^{b)}, Isabel VILLAESCUSA^{b)}

^{a)} ODISEE University college. Gebroeders De Smetstraat 1, B-9000 Gent, Belgium ^{b)} Escola Politècnica Superior. Universitat de Girona. Campus Montilivi. 17071 Girona, Spain
nuria.fiol@udg.edu

For separation of a particular metal, an effective extracting agent must be chosen that has the capability of providing high distribution coefficients and high organic phase loadings. With feed streams that contain several metals, selectivity may be a major concern. In this paper, isolation of an individual metal from a multimetallic mixture is accomplished by using an environmentally friendly “green” separation technology.

The results of our previous works dealing with metal biosorption by using agro-food wastes highlighted the fact that sorbents have different affinity for each of the metals in the mixture. The results also showed that the sorbed metals could be desorbed by using appropriate desorbing agents. Our study of Cu(II), Ni(II), Cd(II) and Pb(II) sorption onto grape stalks [1] showed the affinity pattern Pb(II)>Cu(II)>>Cd(II)>Ni(II). The different affinity of the sorbent for these metals is the base of the metal segregation process studied in this work.

As a first step, metal separation of Pb(II)+Cd(II) or Ni(II)+Cu(II) in binary mixtures was undertaken. Sorption experiments were carried out in packed columns filled of grape stalks of 250-500 µm particle size. The influence of metal concentration ratio in the studied mixtures was studied by using a fixed concentration of cadmium (0.5mM) and nickel (2.5mM) and varying the concentration of the other metal (cadmium and copper) in the respective binary mixture. The minimum bed length necessary for an effective individual metal separation was investigated by varying bed length between 1.75 and 7.0 cm. Desorption experiments were carried out by using different desorbing agents: HCl, NaCl and CaCl₂.

The results of this work shows that biosorption is effective to segregate Cd(II) to a single solution from a Pb+Cd mixture, and Ni(II) from a Ni+Cu mixture when working at optimal conditions. At the fixed Cd(II) and Ni(II) concentration studied and a bed length of 7 cm, cadmium could be effectively separated when Pb(II) in the binary mixtures was lower than 0.2mM; and nickel when Cu(II) concentration was lower than 1.2 mM.

The most appropriated desorbing agent for selectively desorbing lead and copper from the respective columns was found to be HCl at 0.0078M (pH:2.11).

As seen in Figure 1, lead was totally sorbed during 25 hours of operation while cadmium was retained during the first 6 hours and from this time its concentration is increasing with time in the outflow solution. Thus, cadmium remains the only metal present in the outflow solution within the operation time elapsed between 6h and 25h. Figure 2 shows that the desorbing agent is able to elute separately both metals previously sorbed onto grape stalks. Cd (II) is desorbed very fast while Pb (II) is desorbed much slower and remains the only metal present in the outflow solution within the time of desorbing operation elapsed between 2h and 25h. The results obtained in this study demonstrate that it is possible to segregate metal ions from multimetallic solutions by using a “green” sorption process and the appropriate desorbing agent.

Figure 1. Breakthrough curves of binary mixture of Cd(II)-Pb(II) sorption onto grape stalks. Bed length: 7 cm. Flow rate: 30ml/h. C_0 Cd(II): 0.5mM and C_0 Pb(II): 0.4mM.

Figure 2. Desorption curves of Cd(II)-Pb(II) by HCl at 0.0078M. Bed length: 7 cm. Flow rate: 30ml/h.

Furthermore, the use of grape stalks as sorbents gives value to this waste material and allows a selective recovery of valuable metals from a multimetallic solution.

Acknowledgement:

This research was funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation as part of the project CTM2012-37215-C02-01.

References:

- [1] Escudero, C.; Poch, J.; Villaescusa, I., Modelling of breakthrough curves of single and binary mixtures of Cu(II), Cd(II), Ni(II) and Pb(II) sorption onto grape stalks waste. *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2013** 217,129-138.

Evaluation of the adsorption capacities of elements from polluted aqueous solutions by food wastes

Lorenzo MASSIMI^{a)}, Antonella GIULIANO^{a)}, Silvia CANEPARI^{a)}

*^{a)} Sapienza University of Rome, Department of Chemistry, Rome, Italy
lorenzomassimil@gmail.com*

Many industrial processes produce wastewaters particularly rich in heavy metals and toxic elements. High concentrations of these pollutants in water are directly responsible for the life cycles of plants, animals and humans. The removal of metals and metalloids from wastewaters is one of the main objectives of environmental remediation; there are several physico-chemical methods to remove inorganic pollutants from aqueous solutions but most of these are expensive and inadequate. Adsorption is now recognized as an effective and economic method for heavy metal wastewater treatment. The adsorption process offers flexibility in design and operation and in many cases will produce high-quality treated effluent [1]. In recent years several researchers have studied the potential of food wastes as low cost adsorbent materials. The operating conditions that they used for the adsorption experiments are very inhomogeneous so it's impossible to compare the efficiencies of the individual adsorbents. The aim of this study is to evaluate the adsorption capacities of 12 food wastes, assessing their capabilities to remove more than 30 elements (for most of whom the adsorption capacities have never been evaluated) from the same polluted aqueous solutions. Maintaining consistent experimental conditions gives the possibility to make a comparison between the different adsorbent capacities and properly assesses their efficiencies. The powders of each food waste have been included in the polluted solutions in gradually increasing doses to increase the number of available active sites and to study the effects of competition between the elements. The 12 food wastes (banana peels, eggplant peels, apple peels, lemon peels, potato peels, grape wastes, tomato peels, orange peels, watermelon peels, carobs and coffee wastes) have been dried, pulverized and washed before use. The adsorption capacities of several elements (Ag, Al, As, Ba, Be, Bi, Cd, Ce, Co, Cr, Cs, Cu, Fe, Ga, In, La, Mn, Mo, Nb, Ni, Pb, Sb, Sn, Sr, Th, Ti, Tl, U, V, W, Zn) from synthetic solutions at pH 2 and pH 5.5 have been studied. For each element the solubility curve as a function of pH has been verified to evaluate the hydroxides precipitation equilibria and their possible interference in the adsorption processes. The adsorption percentages of elements from the contaminated solutions have been calculated from the data obtained by inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry and by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-OES, ICP-MS). As can be seen from Figure 1, the food wastes can be effectively used for the removal of many elements from polluted solutions even at acid pH. Maintaining homogenous experimental conditions gives the possibility to make a comparison between the different adsorbent capacities and to note that each of them has a propensity to adsorb in its own active sites certain elements rather than others. The statistical

processing of the data obtained has allowed to group the materials examined according to the type of active sites present on the adsorbent surfaces.

To refine the classification of adsorbents there are further studies in progress with electron microscopy and IR spectroscopy.

Figure.1 – Adsorption percentages of elements from synthetic solutions at pH 2 by banana peels, grape wastes and coffee wastes.

The potentialities of food wastes as adsorbent materials have also been verified on real polluted matrices, evaluating the removal of heavy metals from wastewaters produced in a hydro-metallurgical process for the recovery of valuable elements by electronic cards (pH 5.5). Figure 2 shows how the excellent efficiencies of these materials are also confirmed on real matrices.

Figure.2 – Adsorption percentages of Cu, Ni, Pb and Zn from wastewaters produced in a hydro-metallurgical process (pH 5.5) by food wastes.

References:

[1] Fu F.; Wang Q., Removal of heavy metal ions from wastewaters: A review. *J. Environmental Management* **2011**, 92, 407-418.

Effective removal of antimony from aqueous solution using Forager Sponge[®] and SPION-loaded onto Forager Sponge[®]

**Verónica VERDUGO^{a)}, Lorenzo MASSIMI^{b)}, Ahmad ABO MAKEB^{c)}, Amanda ALONSO^{c)},
Cristina PALET^{a)}, Manuel VALIENTE^{a)}**

a) Centre Grup de Tècniques de Separació en Química, Unitat de Q.Analítica, Departament de Química, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 08193 Bellaterra, Catalunya, Spain *b) Sapienza University of Rome, Department of Chemistry, Rome, Italy* *c) Centre BIO-GLS, Departament D'Enginyeria Química, Biològica i Ambiental, Escola d'Enginyeria, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 08193 Bellaterra, Catalunya, Spain*
Veronica.Verdugo@uab.cat

There is a growing interest in antimony (Sb) recovery due to the fact that over 90% of the supplies of this metalloid comes from China, so the European Union and EE.UU are import-dependent of this product. Furthermore, antimony is also a non-desirable product in copper refining processes, creating important problems in the electrorefining plants [1]. Therefore, Sb recovery is essential to the proper treatment of copper ores, and for the production of flame retardants, plastic and semiconductor in the European industry.

New materials based on nanoparticles have been developed with the main objective of improving Sb sorption capacity and make possible its effective recovery. The system that has been used in this work is based on SuperParamagnetic Iron Oxide Nanoparticles (SPION) onto a Forager sponge[®]. This sponge is an open-celled cellulose sponge with weak amine groups, which is able to effectively remove different metals in a selective manner from solutions. The advantages of the use of this sponge are well known [2], so to enhance its sorption capacity and its selectivity, SPION has been loaded on the sponge, which has been shown as an appropriate system to heavy metals sorption [3,4].

The aim of the present work is to evaluate the sorption capacity of Sb, as Sb(III) and Sb(V), in the Forager sponge[®] and in the SPION-Forager sponge[®] systems and their possible application to the recovery and removal of this metalloid in the best selective way from wastewaters.

Different SPION synthesis pathways for its proper loading onto the Forager sponge[®] have been checked. In order to evaluate the sorption capacity kinetic and isotherms, studies have been performed. Afterwards, different batch experiments were run to compare both adsorption material systems, and to determine the influence of the aqueous antimony speciation. So, 25mg of each adsorbent material were agitated in the presence of 2.5mL of Sb(III) and/or Sb(V) synthetic solutions at pH 5. At this pH, the Sb(III) is dissolved in its corresponding neutral form, Sb(OH)₃, and Sb(V) is present in its anionic form, Sb(OH)₆⁻.

Preliminary results show that the presence of SPION in the sponge change the selectivity of this material, increasing the adsorption capacity from 31 to 40 mg of Sb/g of

the adsorbent for Sb(V). On the contrary, Sb(III) decrease its adsorption capacity from 40 to 30 mg of Sb/g of adsorbent. Different electrical surface characteristics of both sponges can give such differences on their behaviour onto Sb(III) and Sb(V) separation, giving some different selectivity depending if using the original sponge or the SPION-loaded one.

Figure 1. Sorption capacity of Sb(III) and Sb(V) in the Forager sponge[®] and the Spion-loaded Forager sponge[®]

Acknowledgements:

This work has been financially supported by the project CHEMNEXUS (Ref: CTM2015-65414-C2-1-R) from the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (MINECO) and the European Regional Development Fund (FEDER). Verónica Verdugo is grateful to the Catalan Government for her predoctoral fellowship, FI-DGR 2015.

References:

- [1] Navarro, P.; Alguacil, F. J., Adsorption of antimony and arsenic from a copper electrorefining solution onto activated carbon. *Hydrometallurgy* **2002**, 66, 101–105.
- [2] Muñoz, J. A.; Gonzalo, A.; Valiente, M., Arsenic adsorption by Fe(III)-loaded open-celled cellulose sponge. Thermodynamic and selectivity aspects. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2002**, 36, 3405–3411.
- [3] Muñoz, J. A.; Gonzalo, A.; Valiente, M., Kinetic and dynamic aspects of arsenic adsorption by Fe(III)-loaded sponge. *J. Solution Chem.* **2008**, 37, 553–565.
- [4] Morillo, D.; Pérez, G.; Valiente, M., Efficient arsenic(V) and arsenic(III) removal from acidic solutions with Novel Forager Sponge-loaded superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles. *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* **2015**, 453, 132–141

Analysis of Isothermal Titration Calorimetry data with ITC_Cal

José Luis BELTRÁN^{a)}, Elisabet BOSCH^{a)}, Clara RÀFOLS^{a)}

^{a)} *Departament de Química Analítica and Institut de Biomedicina (IBUB), Universitat de Barcelona. 08028 Barcelona, SPAIN; jibeltran@ub.edu*

Isothermal Titration Calorimetry (ITC) is a powerful technique to measure the interaction parameters of a chemical process, allowing to the simultaneous determination of the binding constant, reaction stoichiometry and enthalpy change of the investigated reaction. These features make ITC a much appreciated technique in studies of biochemical significance, as drug–protein and drug-RNA interactions, or drug discovery and supramolecular chemistry [1, 2].

In general, ITC experiments are carried out by incremental titration, whereby a volume of titrant (about 5–10 μL) is added to a titrand solution at discrete time-intervals, as shows the thermogram plotted in Figure 1, corresponding to the isothermal titration of EDTA with Ca^{2+} in pH=5.5 acetate buffer [3]. The peak integration provides the heat exchange (ΔQ_i) for each titrant addition. The experimental data are then transformed usually to $\Delta Q_i/\text{mole}$ of titrant vs. the molar ratio, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1

The determination of the binding thermodynamic parameters is carried out by fitting the data to a given model by using non-linear regression procedures [4]. The models involve one or more independent binding sites, or sequential binding to multiple sites [2]. However, in most of the available software for ITC data treatment, the model selection is very limited, owing to the use of predefined equations for defining the metal/ligand or receptor/ligand interactions.

The procedure presented in this communication (ITC_Cal) uses a different approach, in a more flexible way to define the interaction model. ITC_Cal has been written in VBA (Visual Basic for Applications), for use under the MS-EXCELTM spreadsheet. It consists of a user-defined function (*DeltaH*), developed to determine the heat change in each titrant addition to a cell containing the titrand solution; this is allowed taking into account the concentration of the different species (*ns*) before and after the titrant solution, together with their corresponding formation enthalpies, as indicates the following equation:

$$\Delta Q_{i,calc} = V_0 \sum_{j=1}^{ns} (C_{j,i} - C_{j,i-1}) \Delta H_j$$

Where V_0 is the cell working volume, and $C_{j,i-1}$ and $C_{j,i}$ represent the calculated concentration of the j -species before and after the titrant addition, respectively. In this way, the heat changes are calculated from the total concentration of components and the guessed chemical model (equilibrium constants, stoichiometry and formation enthalpies).

Additionally, an optimization subroutine, based on the Levenberg–Marquardt algorithm, is used to optimize the model parameters by minimizing the differences between calculated and experimental heat exchange.

Figure 2 shows the fit of the calculated titration curve (solid line) to the experimental data (O) in the Ca^{2+} -EDTA system, using this procedure.

Figure 2

ITC_Cal has been tested with different ITC systems, giving interaction parameters in good accordance with the previously obtained values. Moreover, ITC_Cal can handle several ITC curves simultaneously, with concurrent acid-base and complex equilibria.

References:

- [1] Draczkowski, P.; Matosiuk, D.; Jozwiak, K., Isothermal titration calorimetry in membrane protein research. *J. Pharma. Biomed. Anal.* **2014**, 87, 313-325.
- [2] Grosseohme, N.E.; Spuches, A.M.; Wilcox, D.E., Application of isothermal titration calorimetry in bioinorganic chemistry. *J. Biol. Inorg. Chem.* **2010**, 15, 1183–1191.
- [3] Ràfols, C.; Bosch, E.; Barbas, R.; Prohens, R., The Ca^{2+} -EDTA chelation as standard reaction to validate Isothermal Titration Calorimeter measurements (ITC). *Talanta* **2016**, 154, 354-359.
- [4] Freyer, M.W.; Lewis, E.A., Isothermal Titration Calorimetry: Experimental Design, Data Analysis, and Probing Macromolecule/Ligand Binding and Kinetic Interactions. *Methods in Cell Biology* **2008**, 84, 79–113

Positive influence of metal complexing properties of surface chemical functions of carbon nanotubes on the preparation of metal nanoparticles

M.L. GODINO-SALIDO^{a)}, M.D. GUTIÉRREZ-VALERO^{a)}, P. ARRANZ-MASCARÓS^{a)}, R. LÓPEZ-GARZÓN^{a)}, C. GARCÍA-GALLARÍN^{a)}, M.D. LÓPEZ DE A TORRE^{a)}, A. COLMENERO-PUERTOLLANO^{a)}, M. PÉREZ-MENDOZA^{b)}

^{a)} Dpto. Química Inorgánica y Orgánica. Facultad de Ciencias Experimentales. University of Jaén. 23071-Jaén (Spain) ^{b)} Dpto. Química Inorgánica. Fac. de Ciencias. University of Granada, 18071-Granada (Spain)
mlgodino@ujaen.es

Metal nanoparticles have attracted considerable attention due to their unique chemical, physical, electronic and optical properties compared to their corresponding bulk materials [1]. Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are one of the most intensively explored nanostructured materials. In particular, carbon nanotubes are unique and ideal templates onto which to immobilize nanoparticles allowing the construction of designed nanoarchitectures that are extremely attractive as supports for heterogeneous catalysts and other technological applications. There are many ingenious methods of depositing metal nanoparticles onto CNTs substrates in the literature [2], each offering varying degrees of control of particle size and distribution along the CNTs.

Here we present our results on the preparation of Pd(0) nanoparticles (NPs) supported on multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) through a method which draws on the positive influence of the metal complexing properties of the surface chemical functions of the MWCNTs to achieve metal NPs. This method consists of three steps: 1) MWCNTs non-covalent functionalization based on the attachment of appropriate ionic receptors on the arene centres of the low-functionalized MWCNTs, *via* irreversible π -stacking interactions; 2) Binding of controlled amounts of Pd(II) ions on the functionalized MWCNTs, through the formation of Pd(II)-complexes by the surface chemical functions of MWCNTs; 3) Metal ion reduction to form the Pd(0) NPs. Thus, homogeneously distributed Pd(0) NPs supported on the MWCNTs have been obtained. The suitable complexing properties of the surface chemical functions of MWCNTs have played a double role: by one hand, they coordinated to the Pd(II) ions, improving the Pd(II) adsorption capacity of the support and leading to a homogeneous distribution of Pd(II) ions on the MWCNTs surface; and on the other hand, after Pd(II) reduction, they stabilize the Pd(0) NPs by complexing the zerovalent atoms of the nanoparticles.

References:

- [1] Johnston, R. L.; Wilcoxon, J. P., *Metal Nanoparticles and Nanoalloys*, Elsevier: Amsterdam, **2012**.
- [2] Wildgoose, G. G.; Banks, C. E.; Compton, R. G., Metal Nanoparticles and related materials supported on carbon nanotubes: Methods and Applications. *Small* **2006**, 2(2), 182-193.

Rh(III) and Ir(III)-cyclopentadienyl-pyridinyl-quinoline complexes: solution properties and polynucleotides binding

**Tarita BIVER^(a), Natalia BUSTO^(b), Gustavo ESPINO^(b), Begoña GARCIA^(b), Felix JALON^(c),
Giuliana LUMINARE^(a), Blanca MANZANO^(c), Jesús VALLADOLID^(b), Sergio VIGNALI^(a)**

^{a)}Department of Chemistry and Industrial Chemistry – University of Pisa, Via Moruzzi 13, 56124 Pisa – Italy ^{b)}Department of Chemistry – Universidad de Burgos, Plaza Misael Bañuelos s.n., 09001, Burgos – Spain ^{c)}Department of Inorganic and Organic Chemistry and Biochemistry – University of Castilla-La Mancha, Avda. Camilo José Cela 10, 13071-Ciudad Real – Spain
tarita.biver@unipi.it

Nowadays, an active research area is focused on the development of new metallodrugs capable of interacting with DNA, and organometallic complexes are promising candidates to this aim.

In the frame of our long lasting collaboration and of the study of the interaction of small molecules with DNA and RNA, the binding of newly synthesized Ru-arene complexes to biosubstrates was already analysed [1,2].

This contribution reports on the preliminary analysis of the binding of the rhodium and iridium complexes shown in Figure 1 to biosubstrates as, in particular, double stranded DNA and RNA.

Figure 1. The metal complexes used in this study $[M(\eta^5\text{-Cp}^*)\text{Cl}(\text{quinpy})]\text{Cl}$ (quinpy = (E)-1-(pyridin-2-yl)-N-(quinolin-3-yl)methanimine): the M ion can be either rhodium(III) or iridium(III).

First, the properties of the metal complexes themselves were analysed, with particular focus on the chloride exchange process to give the M-H₂O species and on the evaluation of the pK_A of the M-H₂O ⇌ M-OH equilibrium. Then, analysis of the possible binding reaction of M-H₂O and M-OH towards polynucleotides is done using spectrophotometry, viscometry,

circular dichroism and stopped-flow kinetics. The preliminary results obtained suggest different binding features that will be discussed.

References:

- [1] Aliende, C.; Jalon, F. A.; Manzano, B. R.; Rodriguez, A. M.; Gaspar, J. F.; Martins, C.; Biver, T.; Espino, G.; Leal, J. M.; García, B., Preparation of organometallic ruthenium-arene-diaminotriazine complexes as binding agents to DNA. *Chemistry an Asian Journal*, **2012**, 7, 788–801.
- [2] Busto, N.; Valladolid, J.; Martínez-Alonso, M. ; Lozano, H. J.; Jalón, F. A.; Manzano, B. R.; Rodriguez, A. M.; Carrión, M.C. ; Biver, T. ; Leal, J.M., Espino, G.; García, B., Anticancer Activity and DNA Binding of a Bifunctional Ru(II) Arene Aqua-Complex with the 2,4-Diamino-6-(2-pyridyl)-1,3,5-triazine Ligand. *Inorganic Chemistry*, **2013**, 52, 9962–9974.

Advanced oxidation processes for the tooth bleaching enhancement

Clara BABOT^{a)}, Daniel SANCHEZ^{a)}, Manuel VALIENTE^{a)}

*a) Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona Dept de Química. Centre GTS.
08193 Bellaterra (Barcelona) Spain
clara.babot@uab.cat*

It's hard not to notice that having a white smile is of a great importance in the modern society, being one of the standards of the perfect image, thus there is high demand of treatments for teeth whitening enhancement. For this purpose both, clinical procedures and OTC products can be applied. Most of them are based on hydrogen or carbamide peroxide at different concentration levels (from 0,1 to 35%) that achieve the whitening effect by the oxidation of the aromatic molecules (such as tannins proceeding from coffee, tea or wine) as responsible for the teeth decolourisation.

Normally, whitening treatments require long application times (over two to four weeks,)) that can lead to side effects such as sore throat or white patches on the gum line. One of the most commonly observed clinical side effect during or after the bleaching of vital teeth is tooth hypersensitivity, with an incidence up to 50% [1]. The persistant contact of the whitening products with the tooth surface can lead to the degradation of the enamel, exposing the dentinal tubulies to the external enviroment [2]. When the fluid within the dentinal tubules, absent of a smear layer, is subjected to thermal, chemical, tactile or evaporative stimuli, the movement of the fluid stimulates the mechanical receptors which are sensitive to fluid pressure, resulting in the transmission of the stimuli to the pulpal nerves ultimately causing a pain response [3].

Image 1 SEM photomicrographs of an enamel surface without (A) and with (B) exposure to a bleaching procedure. The enamel microstructure of the bleached-enamel surface (B) illustrates an obvious enamel etch caused by the bleaching agent, compared with the unbleached surface (A) [2].

It is well known that the hydroxyl radical (OH[·]) have a higher reduction potential than H₂O₂ [4]. In this work, we intend to improve the oxidation effect of whitening treatments using hydroxyl radicals generated as a product of an advanced oxydation procedure, the Fenton Reaction [R1].

Previous research [5] in GTS group (UAB) showed how using heterogeneous Fenton process provided good performance (higher than 99%) in the decolourization treatment of a commercial dye, in a time of 6 minutes.

Our goal is to avoid the side effects of the bleaching treatment by the reduction of the time required to achieve decolourisation. For this purpose, as a first approach we intend to optimize the conditions of a heterogeneous Fenton process, using a natural zeolite as a support for the ferrous ions, to catalyze the oxidation a dye in batch solution; the decolourization will be monitored by UV-VIS spectrophotometry. After that, we will apply the catalyst (in the previous optimized conditions) in a commercial whitening gel previously stained with the tested dye, in order to confirm the diffusion of the hydroxyl radicals through the gel medium. Finally, we will perform a whitening treatment with cow incisors as a model, using, for the first time, a commercial whitening gel in which we will mix the iron catalyst. The whitening effect will be monitored measuring the colour of the teeth surface with a colorimeter.

The future expectations are to make this process suitable for its application in commercial whitening products, in order to improve the existing treatments. The obtained results of the above exposed experimentation plan will be presented.

Acknowledgement:

This work has been financially supported by the project CHEMNEXUS (Ref: CTM2015-65414-C2-1-R) from the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (MINECO) and the European Regional Development Fund (FEDER).

References:

- [1] Li, Y.; Greenwall, L., Safety issues of tooth whitening using peroxide-based materials, *Br Dent J* **2013**, 215 (1), 29-34.
- [2] Dahl, J.E., Tooth bleaching: a critical review of the biological aspects, *Crit Rev Oral Biol Med* **2003**, 14 (4), 292-304.
- [3] West, X.; Lussi, A.; Seong, J.; Hellwig, E., Dentin hypersensitivity: pain mechanisms and aetiology of exposed cervical dentin, *Clin Oral Invest* **2013**, 17 (Suppl 1), 9–19.
- [4] Ohara A.; Sayuri M., *Oxygen Radicals and Related Species*, Nova Science Publishers: Montreal, **2011**; vol 1, pp.19-42.
- [5] Idel-aouada R.; Valiente M.; Yaacoubib, A.; Tanoutic B.; Lopez-Mesasas, M., Rapid decolourization and mineralization of the azo dye C.I. Acid Red 14 by heterogeneous Fenton reaction, *J Hazard Mater* **2011**, 186, 745–750.

Synthesis of reference samples of kidney stones for synchrotron studies

Iris H.VALIDO^{a)}, Albert PELL^{a)}, Maria Angels SUBIRANA-MANZANARES^{a)}, Montserrat RESINA-GALLEGO^{a)}, Manuel VALIENTE^{a)}, Montserrat LÓPEZ-MESAS^{a)}

a)Centre GTS. Unitat de Química Analítica. Departament de Química. Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona. Facultat de Ciències. Edifici CN. 08193. Bellaterra, Barcelona, Spain

Montserrat.Lopez.Mesas@uab.cat

Calcium is one of the most abundant metals in the human body, where it is an important cellular ionic messenger, with many other functions, such as the formation of barely soluble salts. This, in the form of calcium phosphate, is the main component of bones and teeth. Furthermore, it can also precipitate in the form of carbonapatite (CAP) and oxalates in the kidney to form renal calculi (Figure 1).

Figure 2: Kidney Stone of: a) CAP(carbonapatite), b) COM (calcium oxalate monohydrate, and c) COD (calcium oxalate dihydrate)

Our research is focused on Renal Nephrolithiasis, a clinical condition that implies the formation microcrystals aggregates on the kidney, commonly known as kidney stones. This disease affects approximately 12% of men and 6% of women, and has a recurrence rate around 40%. The 66% of the renal calculi are represented by calcium oxalate stones, considering the mono (COM) and the dihydrate (COD) forms[1]. The study of the formation of this kind of stones and the interaction between phases is important in order to understand the pathophysiology, plan a therapy and prevent the recurrence.

Following the published protocols we cannot obtain references with the required purity in order to make a proper characterization of these samples, so we optimized it for the synthesis of the two calcium oxalate hydrates (COM[2] and COD[3,4]). This is a difficult task due to the equilibrium between both species (COM is the thermodynamically stable while COD is the kinetically favoured). The optimizing process was focussed on the media conditions: temperature; the pH of the solutions; the concentration of inhibitors; and, on the other hand, the addition rate to perform the crystallization.

The characterization of the synthetic references was carried out by X-ray Diffraction technique (XRD) and by X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) using synchrotron radiation on the beamline CLAEISS of the Synchrotron ALBA.

As an example of the results, the normalized spectra of both species on the XANES (X-ray Absorption Near Edge Structure) region is shown on Figure 2. Moreover, as shown on Figure 3, it is possible to differentiate these compounds and apply the technique to real samples.

Figure 3: XANES spectra of the two pure calcium oxalate hydrates

Figure 4: Difference between the XANES spectra of both pure oxalates

References:

- [1] Blanco Lucena, F.; Valiente Malgramo, M.; López-Mesas, M., *Chemical speciation on urinary lithiasis. Image analysis and separation techniques for the study of lithogenesis*. Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona: Cerdanyola del Vallès, **2014**, 278.
- [2] Kontoyannis, C. G.; Bouropoulos, N. C.; and Koutsoukos, P. G., Raman spectroscopy: A tool for the quantitative analysis of mineral components of solid mixtures. The case of calcium oxalate monohydrate and hydroxyapatite. *Vib. Spectrosc.* **1997**, 15(1), 53–60.
- [3] Yuzawa, M.; Tozuka, K.; and Tokue, A., *Effect of citrate and pyrophosphate on the stability of calcium oxalate dihydrate*. *Urol. Res.* **1998**, 26 (2), 83–88.
- [4] Grases, F.; Millan, A.; and Conte, A., *Production of calcium oxalate monohydrate, dihydrate or trihydrate - A comparative study*. *Urol. Res.* **1990**, 18 (1), 17–20.

Acknowledgements: This work has been financially supported by the project CHEMNEXUS (Ref: CTM2015-65414-C2-1-R) from the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (MINECO) and the European Regional Development Fund (FEDER).

Determination of the distribution of Selenium chemical species in wheat plants to elaborate functional food

**Nerea MOTA HINCHADO^{a)}, Maria Àngels SUBIRANA MANZANARES^{A)}, Mercè LLUGANY^{b)},
Manuel VALIENTE^{a)}**

a) Departament de Química, Facultat de Ciències, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 08193, Cerdanyola del Vallés, Barcelona *b) Departament de Biologia Animal, de Biologia Vegetal i d'Ecologia, Facultat de Ciències, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 08193, Cerdanyola del Vallés, Barcelona*

mariaangels.subirana@uab.cat

Selenium is an essential element for humans and animals, provided that the tolerable upper level of intake is not exceeded. The amount of selenium required by the body is very small but essential for various body processes. Among the benefits of selenium, when consumed in appropriate proportions, it should be cited its antioxidant action associated with vitamin E. Selenium helps cells defensive system and relieves oxidative stress, besides slowing down many degenerative diseases. In addition selenium is essential for the health and the good formation of hair and nails.

The chemical speciation of Selenium in the system is crucial, since the properties of Se are strongly dependent on the form in which it is found.

Native Selenium is not common and it is difficult to isolate and purify. In addition, the Selenium containing minerals (in the forms of selenide, selenite or selenate) are also rare; therefore, Se is normally obtained from selenide existing as an impurity in sulfide ores. In soil, a short number of inorganic Se species like selenite and selenate are typically found. However, the beneficial forms for humans are selenoaminoacids, which are not toxic and more readily incorporated into proteins. However, mammals are not able to synthesize them and need to intake them from the diet.

Selenium enters the food-chain through plants, but Se-poor soils around the world produce Se-deficient crops resulting in deficient food for humans. Soil Se enrichment in edible plants has been proposed as a solution for this problem, and wheat has been chosen as an ideal candidate. Wheat is one of the most widely consumed cereals worldwide. Thus, it's an appropriate material to develop a functional food, in order to contribute to human welfare by increasing the amount of selenium consumed to the optimum level.

Figure 1. Hydroponic growth

The proposed research is to characterize the chemical speciation and plant distribution of Selenium uptaken by wheat from Se enriched hydroponic growth. Once the Selenium is incorporated to the plant root, the metabolic process starts, producing selenoaminoacids. Selenocysteine (Se-Cys) and selenomethionine (Se-Met) are the most common species produced by cereals. The challenge of this work is to implement and optimize a technique based on the hyphenation of HPLC-ICP-MS in order to determine the selenium species present in wheat tissues, and to characterize the proportion of selenoamino acids depending on the species of inorganic selenium that have been added to the cultivation medium, in a novel chemical tuning system.

Acknowledgements:

This work has been financially supported by the project CHEMNEXUS (Ref: CTM2015-65414-C2-1-R) from the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (MINECO) and the European Regional Development Fund (FEDER). M Angels Subirana Manzanares is grateful to the Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (MINECO) for the predoctoral fellowship: Ayudas para contratos predoctorales para la formación de doctores 2013.

References:

- [1] Guerrero B.; Llugany, M.; Valiente, M., Method to enrich plant selenoaminoacids by chemical tuning. Patent EP13172305, **2013**
- [2] Rayman, M.P., The importance of selenium to human health, *The Lancet* **2000**, 356, 233-241
- [3] Bodnar, M.; Konieczka, P., Evaluation of candidate reference material obtained from selenium-enriched sprouts for the purpose of selenium speciation analysis. *LWT - Food Science and Technology* **2016**, 70, 286–295.

Interaction of Human Serum Albumin (SHA) with an Ir(III) complex.

Laura ALVAREZ^{a)}, Natalia BUSTO^{a)}, Chiara TIRIBILLI^{a)}, Javier SANTOLAYA^{a)}, José M. LEAL^{a)},
Félix JALON^{b)}, Blanca R. MANZANO^{b)}, Marta MARTINEZ^{a)}, Gustavo ESPINO^{a)}, Begoña
GARCIA^{a)}

^{a)}Chemistry Department, University of Burgos, Plaza Misael Bañuelos s/n, 09001 Burgos,
Spain ^{b)}Inorganic Chemistry Department, Organic and Biochemistry, University of Castilla La
Mancha, Avenida Camilo J. Cela 10, 13071 Ciudad Real, Spain

jmleal@ubu.es

The synthesis and study of new compounds able to selectively alter the behaviour of certain biomolecules is a key target in Medicinal Chemistry. In this context, organometallic complexes have aroused growing attention, as these compounds are endowed with properties that turn them into suitable candidates to interact with different biomolecules. Ir(III) complexes have shown to be useful for the OLED (organic-light-emitting diode) technology, due to their luminescent properties or as catalysts [1]. On the other hand, different studies have addressed the intercalation of “half-sandwich” Ir(III) complexes into DNA of cancer cells, affording promising results [2]. Additionally, it has been shown that their pronounced activity may be altered easily by the action of certain ligands attached to the metal centre, because a small variation in their structure can entail large changes in their biological activity.

Although in many cases DNA has been the target molecule for drugs based on transition metals, the study of the interaction of metal complexes with certain proteins of blood plasma is essential. Such an interaction is directly related to the transport and elimination of the drug. In blood, drugs may stay in two forms, either free or as a ligand, the free fraction exhibiting pharmacological effects and can be either metabolized or expelled. Therefore, the study of the drug-protein binding can help to control the concentration of the free drug, thus prolonging the operational time of the drug and influencing its distribution, absorption and metabolism.

Figure 1. Left) Structure of Ir(III)[(2-(hydroxy)phenyl)benzimidazole](pentamethylcyclopentadienyl)(Cl)] complex Right) Human Serum Albumin.

Human seroalbumin (HSA) is the most abundant protein in human plasma, thereby the study of its interactions with different metal complexes has aroused great attention. In view of the importance of Iridium complexes for cancer research and the interest of drug-proteins interaction, we have studied the interaction of the Ir (III) complex [(Cp*)Ir(hphbzIm)] (Figure 1, Left) with potential biological activity with HSA (Figure 1, right).

References:

- [1] a) Lo, K.K.W.; Louie, M.W.; Zhang, K.Y. *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **2010**, 254 (21-22), 2603-2633; b) Chi, Y.; Chou, P.T., Transition-metal phosphors with cyclometalating ligands: fundamentals and applications. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2010**, 39, 638-655; c) Wong, W.Y.; Ho, C.L., Heavy metals organometallic electrophosphors derived from multi-component chromophores. *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **2009**, 253, 1709-1758
- [2] a) Kumar, A.; Kumar, A.; Gupta, R. K.; Paitandi, R. P.; Singh, K. B.; Trigun, S. K.; Hundal, M.S.; Pandey, D.S., Cationic Ru(II), Rh(III) and Ir(III) complexes containing cyclic π -perimeter and 2-aminophenyl benzimidazole ligands: Synthesis, molecular structure, DNA and protein binding, cytotoxicity and anticancer. *J. Organomet. Chem.* **2016**, 801, 68-79; b) Qi, Y.; Liu, Z.; Li, H.; Sadler, P. J.; O'Connor, P. B., You have full text access to this content Mapping the protein-binding sites for novel iridium(III) anticancer complexes using electron capture dissociation. *Rapid Commun. Mass Spectrom.* **2013**, 27 (17), 2028–2032; c) Vicente, C.; Haro, C.; Bautista, D.; Ruiz, J., Novel Bis-C,N-Cyclometalated Iridium(III) Thiosemicarbazide Antitumor Complexes: Interactions with Human Serum Albumin and DNA, and Inhibition of Cathepsin B. *Inorg. Chem.* **2013**, 52(2), 974–982; d) Mukherjee, T.; Mukherjee, M.; Sena, B.; Banerjee, S.; Hundal, G.; Chattopadhyaya, P., Synthesis, characterization, interactions with DNA and bovine serum albumin (BSA), and antibacterial activity of cyclometalated iridium(III) complexes containing dithiocarbamate derivatives. *J. Coord. Chem.* **2014**, 67(15), 2643–2660, e) Paitandi, R. P.; Gupta, R. K.; Singh, R. S.; Sharma, G.; Koch, B.; Pandey, D. S., Interaction of ferrocene appended Ru(II), Rh(III) and Ir(III) dipyrinato complexes with DNA/protein, molecular docking and antitumor activity *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* **2014**, 84, 17-29.

Leaching Processes of Beachrock outcrops located close to estuarine areas

Soraya SALINAS^{a)}, Ane ITURREGUI^{a)}, Ainhoa MESA^{a)}, Nikole ARRIETA^{a)}, Irantzu MARTINEZ-
ARKARAZO^{a)}, Marian OLAZABAL^{a)}

^{a)}*Department of Analytical Chemistry, University of the Basque Country (EHU/UPV), P.O. Box 644, 48080 Bilbao, North of Spain; Marian.olazabal@ehu.eus*

Beachrocks are consolidated coastal sedimentary formations resulting from early intergranular carbonate cement precipitations in the intertidal zone, resulting on rock units. Given the anthropogenic influence in the phenomenon formation, several materials are trapped in its matrix such us plastic and escoriaceous matter.

Once the metal content were studied in previous a work [1], the contamination parameters (contamination factor, Cf and Degreee of Contamination, Cd) were compared with the current legislation, finding out that the environment potential risk of the beachrock could be classified as a moderate or high, depending on the metal studied. Therefore, it is necessary to know the real amount that could be released to the environment as consequence of the natural agents as rainwater, marine currents, wave and tidal movements. Moreover, taking into account that nowadays the beachrock formation are suffering a disintegration process, in this study the origin of the reverse phenomenon as well as its effect on the environment was also studied.

In this sense, mobility assays were carried out to determine the real leaching capacity of nature agents. For that purpose, the process was simulated applying the Norm DINV (ISO 19730), in which marine and rain water were used as extractants.

For that purpose, several beachrock samples were taken at two different beaches located on the Nervion-Ibaizabal estuary following the longitudinal and transverse transects. Besides, in order to simulateas much as possible the real conditions occurred in the environment, the raw samples were used without any physical pre-treatment process, using as extractants sea and rain water collected in situ. In this way, the metal content (Ca, Mo, Sr, Cd, Ni, Ag, As, Cr, Na, Tl, Ba, K, Co, Mg, Ti, Al, V, Pb, Cu, Mn, Zn, Sn, Fe, Hg, Sb and Se) was analyzed by ICP-MS and the results were compared with the pseudototal elementcontent (the extractable fraction under aqua regia conditions) of the samples. Moreover, a principal component analysis was performed to interpret the data as well as to identify the most significant elements of the system.

According to the results, although the pH of the rainwater (pH= 6.8) is slightly lower than the sea water values (pH= 8.1), the leaching tests performed in the laboratory evidenced a higher extractant capacity of seawater. In fact, in the leaching experiments performed using rainwater, the concentration levels determined by most of the metals were lower than the detection limits, except for the majorelements (Na, Mg, K, and Ca) and (Li, Al, Sr, Mn and Tl) among the minorities elements. Nevertheless, in the case of the seawater, a

higher concentration for all of the elements was shown, with concentration levels from 0.2 ng.g-1 of Cd to 1 µg.g-1 of Al, among minor elements.

In conclusion, the pH was not the main factor influencing the metal leaching, as the main cause of the process could be the inorganic ligands and/or the organic matter present in seawater. As a matter of fact, the organic matter, such as humic, fulvic and hydrophilic acids, is known to induce the complex formation with transition metals [2].

In addition, a different behaviour related to the movable element content was observed between the samples of both beaches, which could suggested a worse cementation state in the beach that showed higher leaching values. For that reason, in order to analyze the influence of the physical state of the sample, the leachable content of raw and powdered samples was compared, finding out that the extraction efficiency increases in grinded samples, being this effect higher when using seawater as leaching agent.

References:

- [1] Iturregui, A, Arrieta N., De Diego A., Olazabal M.A., Martinez- Arkarazo I., Madariaga J.M., Distribution of metals in Temperate Beachrocks. Acta of the International Symposia on Metal Complexes, ISMEC GROUP SERIES, Volume5, Year **2015**, ISSN 2239-2459, <http://mat520.unime.it/ismecacta>
- [2] Domènech, X.; Peral, J., *Química Ambiental de Sistemas Terrestres*. Reverte: Barcelona, **2006**.

Acknowledgments:

This work has been financially supported by the project PRIACE (Ref: CTM2012-36612) from the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (MINECO) and the European Regional Development Fund (FEDER). Ane Iturregui is grateful to the Basque Government for her predoctoral fellowships.

Multianalytical methodology based on in situ spectroscopic assessment to diagnose the chemical attack in building materials: DRIFT implementation

Olivia GÓMEZ-LASERNA^{a)}, Nagore PRIETO-TABOADA^{a)}, María Ángeles OLAZABAL^{a)}, Juan Manuel MADARIAGA^{a)}

^{a)} *Department of Analytical Chemistry, University of the Basque Country (EHU/UPV), P.O. Box 644, 48080 Bilbao, North of Spain
olivia.gomez@ehu.eus*

Nowadays, the usefulness of in situ spectroscopic assessment, and the added benefits of its combination with analytical methodologies for the conservation diagnosis of building materials are widely recognized. Nevertheless, this type of matrix often contains chromophore compounds that can produce a great fluorescence in Raman signal, hampering the in situ analysis. In this sense, although, some techniques like photobleaching can help to reduce this effect, the reality is that the options that could be taken in field analysis are complex to accomplish.

Therefore, with the goal of reducing the drawbacks of the in situ analysis, often based on Raman spectroscopy, it was complemented by Diffuse Reflectance Infrared Fourier Transform (DRIFT) Spectroscopy. For that purpose, its usefulness as diagnostic tool to find out the origin of pathologies, mainly caused by environmental stressors, was evaluated. In this regard, given that the current handheld devices cannot separate the diffuse component of the reflectance from the specular one, the spectral distortions were expected and reduced by means of mathematical algorithms [1]. Then, in order to corroborate the in situ results, a non invasive sampling method using cellulose patches was applied to extend the study to the laboratory. In this manner, spatial patterns models of salt distribution were obtained by ion chromatography (IC). Finally, thanks to spectroscopic information and quantitative data, the thermodynamic models of the chemical degradation processes were established and thoroughly discussed.

According to the results, the most severe decay process was suffered by the sandstone material as cause of atmospheric attack. The loss of its cement matrix, mainly composed by hematite (α -Fe₂O₃) and quartz (α -SiO₂), starts with a drop in pH, allowing the precipitation of crystalline lepidocrocite (γ -FeOOH) and magnetite (Fe₂O₄) during the drying stage. In turn, as Pourbaix diagram indicates, lepidocrocite could be transformed into maghemite (γ -Fe₂O₃) by deshydroxilation and/or into the amorphous ferric oxyhydroxide (FeO_x(OH)_{3-2x}) by a dissolution-precipitation processes. All these compounds are poorly crystallized and quite unstable. In this way, they tend to transform into goethite (α -FeOOH), the most thermodynamically stable mineral phase. Besides, iron salts such as coquimbite (Fe₂(SO₄)₃·9H₂O) and siderite (FeCO₃) were also detected, explaining the disaggregation presented by the ashlar as direct consequence of the cement dissolution and the volume changes occurred during the chemical transformations.

In addition to this, a vertical zoning salt distribution was observed in the load-bearing wall as a result of the infiltration water attack. In accordance with Arnold and Zehnder's model [2], the sulphated salts such as gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$), thenardite (Na_2SO_4) and epsomite ($\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were accumulated in low (0-0.2 m) and middle zones (0.4-0.6 m) whereas nitrates, mainly niter (KNO_3) and nitratine (NaNO_3), were only concentrated in the lowest zone and at the top (1.6 m) (Fig. 1). As it is usual in case of rising damp, the capillary rise and evaporation of the acid water allow the leached content from the soil to pass through the ashlars, causing an important loss of stability owing to the dissolution, hydration and crystallization processes that are continuously taking place.

Figure 1. In situ DRIFT spectra: a) gypsum and epsomite identified in the low and middle zones, and b) nitratine and niter collected in the lowest zone and/or at the top of the zoning salt distribution, as main decaying compounds.

In view of the results obtained, the multianalytical methodology carried out allows us to determine the main chemical mechanisms of decay, highlighting the advantages of DRIFT analysis as useful tool to the identification of compounds and salt zoning distribution. The complementation of both spectroscopic techniques significantly minimizes the handicaps presented in Raman spectroscopy by fluorescent effect in this type of samples.

References:

- [1] Arrizabalaga, I.; Gómez-Laserna, O.; Aramendia, J.; Gorra, A.; Madariaga, J.M, Applicability of a diffuse reflectance infrared Fourier transform handheld spectrometer to perform in situ analyses on Cultural Heritage Materials. *Spectrochimica Acta Part A* **2014**, 129, 256-267.
- [2] Agudo, E.R.; Lubelli, B.; Sawdy, A.; Hees, R.V.; Price, C.; Navarro, C.R., An integrated methodology for salt damage assessment and remediation: the case of San Jerónimo Monastery (Granada, Spain). *Environmental Earth Sciences* **2011**, 63, 1475-1486.

Acknowledgements:

This work has been financially supported by the project DISILICA-1930 from the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (MINECO) (ref: BIA2014-59194). O. Gómez-Laserna and N. Prieto-Taboada acknowledges their post-doctoral contracts (UPV-EHU).

ISMEC 2016

INTERNATIONAL SYMPOSIUM OF METAL COMPLEXES.
A TOTAL BROKERAGE EVENT

ALBA Synchrotron

Equilibria

Therapies

Brokerage Session

Nanostructures

Plenary Lectures

Coordination

Biomolecules

Fernando Pulidori Price

Complexes

Thermodynamics

Sponsors:

AMPHOS²¹
SCIENTIFIC AND STRATEGIC ENVIRONMENTAL CONSULTING

Gomensoro

